

**Agriculture and
Livestock Training
Manual:
Towards Climate Resilience
Practices**

**Developed by the Centre for Dryland
Agriculture, Bayero University Kano
March, 2020**

Edited by Murtala Muhammad Badamasi (PhD)

List of contributors

SECTION I: LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION PRACTICES

Dr Nuhu Bello Rano
Dr Aminu Nasiru

SECTION II: BEST PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SOME FOOD CROPS

Dr Abraham Shittu
Mrs Zainab Lawan Miko
Dr Aminu Alhassan Fagge
Hassan Ibrahim
Mrs Fatima Zahra Buhari

SECTION III: POSTHARVEST ACTIVITIES OF CROPS

Dr Abraham Shittu
Mrs Zainab Lawan Miko
Dr Aminu Alhassan Fagge
Hassan Ibrahim
Mrs Fatima Zahra Buhari

SECTION IV: CROP PROTECTION

Dr Salisu Gombe Haruna
Dr Nafiu Umar Sanda
Dr Hassan Sule
Dr Baba Sani Wudil

SECTION V: VALUE ADDITION TO AGRICULTURAL COMMODITIES

Professor Amina Mustapha
Professor Aminu Suleiman
Dr Ali Abdullahi
Dr Amina Lawan Mustapha

SECTION VI: NATURAL RESOURCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

Dr Garba Omar
Dr Muhammad Nuraddeen Danjuma
Dr Murtala Muhammad Badamasi
Mrs. Amina Sheikh Abdullahi
Dr Ridwan Mukhtar Bunza
Dr Mansur Abdu Mohammed

Sharfaddeen Kamilu Ilah
Mrs Halima Abdulkadir Idris
Yusuf Ahmed Yusuf
Dr Tasiu Rilwan Yalwa

Forward

Agriculture is an important sector of Nigerian Economy as more than half of its population relies on Agriculture as principle source of income. Research and Extension systems play major role in generation and dissemination of Agricultural technologies aiming at enhancing the income of farmers. The extension system adopts series of extension methods such as Training, demonstration, exposure visit to transfer the technologies from lab to land. Majority of these extension efforts mainly focus on location and crop specific technologies, and mostly on solution to problem basis. However, there is a need for equipping the farmers with basic knowledge of Agriculture in order to create a better knowledge platform at farmer level for taking appropriate farm management decisions and to absorb modern technologies.

In view of this, Save the Children through the support from the European Union seeks to develop agriculture and livestock training guidelines/curriculum for Yobe State with capacity strengthening and development in the State Agriculture.

This manual is a practical guide for farmers in Yobe State. It contains simple, easy to follow tools on the commonly used farming methods and an outline of how farming may be planned and implemented. It provides basic knowledge on Good Agricultural Practices (GAP), enhancing the awareness of farmers on critical factors in selection of crops and cropping patterns, judicious use of natural resources such as soil and water and emphasizing the importance of mechanization and modern technology in the field of Agriculture.

Secretary to the State Government
Yobe State, Nigeria

Preface

Dramatic changes are taking place in agriculture in the Drylands of Nigeria due to changing demography, environmental degradation, poor farming practices and climate change. These changes are affecting the livelihood support systems at local levels and translating to food insecurity issues at national level. To address this, there is need to improve the technical know-how of extension workers who often interface with local farmers to transfer innovative farming and livelihood skills. The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano is an African Centre of Excellence that supports capacity building and research innovations in the drylands of West and Central Africa. The Centre is in partnership with Save the Children International (SCI), a non-governmental organization focusing on vulnerable children, to build the resilience of farmers through training of extension workers on crops and livestock technologies. The learning process is designed to enable farmers to learn continuously and to improve their knowledge, change their attitudes and enhance their skills to develop their farming practices in the context of environmental and climatic changes.

This manual is developed for SCI, Yobe State Office by the CDA in collaboration with the Departments of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Agronomy, Animal Science, Crop Protection, Environmental Management, Forestry & Wildlife, Geography and Soil Science of Bayero University, Kano. The manual is need-based, intended to be used in building the capacity of stakeholders in Yobe State with the hope of improving the productivity and livelihoods of farmers. The manual can be adopted by relevant stakeholders in other places.

The manual is presented in six sections: Livestock Production Practices, Best Agronomic Practices of Some Crops, Post-Harvest Activities of Selected Crops, Crop Protection, Value Addition to Agricultural Commodities and Natural Resource and Environmental Management. Each section is further broken down to sub sections in modular arrangement capturing objectives, activities, and practical exercises. The contribution of staff of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture and the staff in the Faculty of Agriculture and Earth and Environmental Sciences in the development of this manual is duly acknowledged.

Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin
Director

Table of Content

List of contributors	2
Forward.....	4
Preface	5
Table of Content	6
SECTION I: LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION PRACTICES.....	17
MODULE 1: IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL CHICKENS	17
• 1.1. Introduction	17
• 1.2 Housing/ Shelter and Facilities.....	21
• 1.3 Feeding, Water and Health Care.....	23
• 1.4 Processing and Use.....	25
• 1.5 Record Keeping.....	26
• 1.6 Monitoring and Evaluation	27
• 1.7 Key Messages.....	27
MODULE 2: IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL GOATS	28
• 2.1 Introduction	28
• 2.2 Site Selection and Housing.....	29
• 2.3 Nutrition.....	30
• 2.4 Daily Routine Husbandry Practices	32
2.4.3 Identification of Poor Producing Goats	33
• 2.5 Breeding and Gestation	33
• 2.6 Key Messages.....	35
• 2.7 Monitoring and Evaluation.....	35
MODULE 3: FEEDS AND FEEDING IN SMALL RUMINANTS.....	37
• 3.1 Introduction	37
• 3.2 Small ruminants feed resources in Yobe State.....	37
• 3.3 Small ruminants' diseases and management.....	39
SECTION II: BEST PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SOME FOOD CROPS. .	42

MODULE 4: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SORGHUM (<i>SORGHUM BICOLOR L.</i>) AND PEARL MILLET (<i>PENNISETUM GLAUCUM L.</i>).....	42
• 4.1 Introduction	42
• 4.2 Good Agronomic Practices (Gap) for Sorghum and Pearl Millet Production.....	42
• 4.3 Promising Sorghum Cultivars Obtained in North Eastern Nigeria and their Qualities.....	43
• 4.4 Promising Pearl millet cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.	44
• 4.5 Cultural Practices.....	44
MODULE 5: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF MAIZE (<i>ZEA MAYS L.</i>)	49
• 5.1 Introduction	49
• 5.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for maize production.	50
• Seed rate.....	51
MODULE 6: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF RICE (<i>ORYZA SATIVA L.</i>)	53
• 6.1 Introduction	53
• 6.2 Good Agronomic practices (GAPs) of rice production.....	53
MODULE 7: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF COWPEA (<i>VIGNA UNGUICULATA L. WALP.</i>) AND GROUNDNUT (<i>ARACHIS HYPOGAEA L.</i>).....	61
• 7.1 Introduction	61
• 7.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for cowpea and groundnut production.....	62
MODULE 8: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES FOR SESAME	66
• 8.1 Introduction	66
• 8.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for sesame (Benniseed) production.....	66
MODULE 9: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SELECTED FRUIT AND VEGETABLES	69
• 9.1 Introduction	70

• 9.2 Onion (<i>Allium cepa</i> L.)	70
9.2.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for onion production	70
9.2.2 Post planting	72
• 9.3 TOMATOES.....	73
9.3.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for tomato production.....	73
• 9.4 PEPPER (<i>Capsicum</i> spp L.)	76
9.4.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for pepper production	76
SECTION III: POSTHARVEST ACTIVITIES OF CROPS	78
MODULE 10: POST-HARVEST HANDLING AND MANAGEMENT OF CEREAL CROPS.....	78
• 10.1 Objectives.....	78
10.1.1 Activities	78
10.1.2 Time Required.....	79
10.1.3 Learning Exercises	79
10.1.4 Materials	79
10.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation.....	79
• 10.2 What is Post-harvest?	79
• 10.3 Post-harvest losses	80
• 10.4 Threshing Practices	80
10.4.1 Proper use of manual tools available for harvesting in a locality.....	80
10.4.2 Stage and timing of harvesting	80
10.4.3 Indicators of harvesting time.....	81
10.4.4 Precautions during harvesting	81
• 10.5 Drying Practices	81
10.5.1 Important Tips in Drying Grains Practices.....	81
10.5.2 How to measure grains' moisture content	82
10.6.1 How to reduce losses during threshing.....	82
• 10.7 Cleaning/Sorting, winnowing	82
• 10.8 Causes of losses and loss management During Storage	83
10.8.1 Losses caused by insects	83

10.8.2	Method of controlling insects-infecting stored grains.....	83
10.8.3	Storage facilities	84
10.8.4	Storage practices	84
10.8.5	Seed storage	85
MODULE 11: RICE POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT		85
• 11.1	Objectives.....	85
11.1.1	Activities.....	85
11.1.2	Time Required.....	85
11.1.3	Learning Exercises	86
11.1.4	Materials.....	86
11.1.5	Pre and Post Training Evaluation	86
• 11.2	Introduction	86
• 11.3	Some Tips on Rice harvesting Practices.....	86
11.3.1	Problems of Rice Harvesting.....	87
• 11.4	Rice Storage:.....	87
• 11.5	Rice Processing:.....	88
MODULE 12: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF GROUNDNUTS & COWPEA CROPS		89
• 12.1	Objectives.....	89
12.1.1	Activities	89
12.1.2	Time Required.....	89
12.1.3	Learning Exercises	89
12.1.4	Materials	89
12.1.5	Pre and Post Training Evaluation	89
• 12.2	Groundnut Post-harvest management	90
• 12.3	The process of harvesting groundnuts:	90
• 12.4	Stages in post-harvest handling of groundnuts.....	90
• 12.5	Aflatoxin Problem in Groundnut.....	90
12.5.1	What are Aflatoxins?	90
12.5.2	What causes contamination of groundnuts by Aflatoxin?.....	90

12.5.3	What are the effects of aflatoxins contamination?	91
12.5.4	How to minimize the effects of Aflatoxins.....	91
• 12.6	Cowpea Post-harvest management.....	92
12.6.1	The process of harvesting Cowpea	92
12.6.2	Harvesting	92
12.6.3	Stages in post–harvest handling of cowpea	92
MODULE 13: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF TOMATO & ONION CROPS		92
• 13.1	Objectives.....	92
13.1.1	Activities.....	92
13.1.2	Time Required.....	93
13.1.3	Learning Exercises	93
13.1.4	Materials.....	93
13.1.5	Pre and Post Training Evaluation.....	93
• 13.2	Onion Post-harvest management.....	93
• 13.3	Harvesting	93
• 13.4	Tomato Post-harvest management	94
13.4.1	Harvesting.....	94
MODULE 14: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF SESAME		96
• 14.1	Objectives.....	96
14.1.3	Learning Exercises	97
14.1.4	Materials	97
• 14.2	Post Harvest Handling and Management Practices of Sesame	97
• 14.3	Harvesting	97
SECTION IV: CROP PROTECTION.....		104
MODULE 15: PEST AND DISEASES OF CROPS AND THEIR MANAGEMENT		104
• 15.1	INSECT PESTS OF MILLET, SORGHUM AND SESAME.....	104
15.1.1	Objectives:.....	104
15.1.2	INSECT PESTS OF MILLET.....	105

15.1.3 INSECT PESTS OF SORGHUM.....	107
15.1.4 INSECT PESTS OF SESAME	109
• 15.2 INSECT PESTS OF COWPEA AND GROUNDNUT.....	111
15.2.1 INSECT PESTS OF COWPEA	111
15.2.2 INSECT PESTS OF GROUNDNUT	113
• 15.3 Insect Pests of Mango and Pepper.....	114
15.3.1 MANGO	114
15.3.2 INSECT PESTS OF PEPPER	118
• 15.4 Major Insects Pests of Rice, Maize, Tomato and Onion	119
15.4.1 Insect Pests of Tomato	119
15.4.2 Insect Pests of Maize	125
15.4.3 Insect Pest of Onion.....	129
• 15.5 DISEASES OF CEREALS (Rice, Maize, millet, sorghum etc).....	132
15.5.1 Diseases of Maize.....	133
15.5.2 Diseases of millets and sorghum.....	135
15.5.3 VIRAL DISEASES	138
15.5.4 DISEASES OF RICE.....	139
• 15.6 DISEASES OF VEGETABLES	141
15.6.1 Tomato Diseases.....	141
MODULE 16: POSTHARVEST PESTS AND DISEASES OF SOME CROPS	
AND THEIR MANAGEMENT	142
• 16.1 TRAINING OBJECTIVES.....	142
• 16.2 Post-Harvest Diseases: Meaning, Classification, Types and Control	143
16.2.1 Classification of Post-Harvest Diseases.....	143
16.2.2 Types of Post-Harvest Diseases:.....	144
16.2.3 Control of Post-Harvest Diseases:.....	146
• 16.3 Post-Harvest pests of crops	147
16.3.1 Insect pests of stored grains	147
16.3.2 Rodents Damage and their Control (Rats and Mice)	153

16.3.3 BATS.....	157
16.3.4 Agricultural Bird Pests	158
• 16.4 AFLATOXIN CONTAMINATION IN CROPS.....	159
16.4.1 AFLOTOXIN CONTAMINATION.....	159
16.4.2 Aflatoxins: Health and Economic Challenges	160
16.4.3 ENVIRONMENTS THAT ENCOURAGE AFLATOXIN DEVELOPMENT.....	161
16.4.4 KEY STEPS THAT PREVENT AFLATOXIN	161
SECTION V: VALUE ADDITION TO AGRICULTURAL COMMODITIES	162
MODULE 17: VALUE ADDING ACTIVITIES AND CUSTOMER VALUE..	162
• 17.1 Objectives.....	162
17.1.3 Learning Exercises	162
17.1.4 Materials	162
17.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation.....	163
17.2 Adding Value to Agricultural Commodities.....	163
17.2.1 Introduction	163
17. 2. 2 What is Value Addition and how is Value Added?	163
17.2.4 What Add Value to Agricultural Commodities	164
17. 2. 5 Creating a Value-Added Product	165
• 17.3 Agricultural Commodity Value Chain.....	165
17.4 Exercises	167
MODULE 18: MARKETING OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCE.....	169
• 18.1 Objectives.....	169
18.1.1 Activities	169
18.1.3 Learning Exercises.....	169
18.1.4 Materials.....	169
18.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation.....	170
• 18.2 Marketing.....	170
• 18.3. Functions of Marketing in Agribusiness.....	171
18.3.1 Assembling.....	171

18.3.2 Storage	172
18.3.3 Standardizing and grading	172
18. 3.4 Transportation.....	172
18.3.5 Processing.....	172
18.3.6 Packaging.....	173
18.3.7 Retailing.....	173
18.4 Factors Considered in Packaging and Branding Decisions.....	173
• 18.6 Basic Steps in Planning the Marketing Process	174
• 18.7 Market Intelligence	175
• 18.8 Exercises	175
MODULE 19: SAVINGS, SAVINGS MOBILIZATION AND RECORD	
KEEPING.....	176
• 19.1 Objectives.....	176
19.1.1 Activities	176
19.1.3 Learning Exercises	177
19.1.4 Materials	177
19.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation.....	177
• 19.2 Savings and Savings Mobilization.....	177
19.2.11 Guidelines in Obtaining Farm Credit.....	181
• 19.3 Basic Record Keeping	182
19.3.1 Reasons for Keeping Farm Records.....	182
19.4 Types of Farm Records.....	182
19.4.1 Production Records.....	182
19.4.2 Business Records.....	183
• 19.5 Record Keeping System.....	183
• 19.5.1 Criteria for selecting a Record Keeping System	183
• 19.6 Business Record Design	183
19.6.1 Samples of Farm Business Records	184
• 19.7 Exercises	185

SECTION VI: NATURAL RESOURCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT	186
MODULE 20: WATER CONSERVATION	186
• 20.1 Intended Learning Outcome:.....	186
• 20.2 Methods of Water Conservation	186
20.2.1 Micro or Drip Irrigation	187
20.2.2 Zai Pits.....	187
20.2.3. Ripper-Furrow Planting System.....	189
20.2.4. Subsurface Irrigation Systems	190
20.2. 5. Gated Pipe Irrigation.....	191
20.2.6. Harvesting and storage of Rain Water	192
MODULE 21: SOIL MANAGEMENT	193
• 21.1 Intended Learning Outcome.....	193
• 21.2 Soil Management Practices.....	193
21.2.1 Application of Manures	193
MODULE 22: AGROFORESTRY	198
• 22.1 Objectives, duration and methods of training	198
• 22.2 Introduction	199
22.2.1 But why practice agroforestry?	199
• 22.3 System and Practices.....	201
Alley Cropping:.....	203
• 22.4 Benefits.....	205
22.4.1 Economic benefits	205
22.4.3 Environmental benefits.....	206
• 22.5 Establishing and Managing Agroforestry Systems.....	206
22.5.1. Identifying appropriate agroforestry options.....	206
22.5.2 Key elements to be considered in this decision-making process:..	207
22.5.3 Choice of trees.....	208
22.5.4 Factors to be considered in the Design of an Agroforestry System	208

22.5.5 The selection of plant and animal material	209
22.5.6 Planting	210
22.5.7 Marketing	210
• 22.6 Maintaining and Monitoring an Agroforestry System	210
• 22.7 Gender and Agroforestry	211
MODULE 23: TREE PLANTING	211
• 23.1 Training Objectives:.....	212
• 23.2 Module One.....	212
23.2.1 Climatic Conditions of the Planting Site (Northern Yobe)	212
23.2.2 Planting season	212
23.2.3 The choice of the tree species; this should be guided on the following:.....	213
23.2.4 Tree Species for Agroforestry	213
• 23.3 Preparation, Production and Acquisition of the Planting Stock	213
23.3.1 Preparation	213
23.3.2 Production and Acquisition of the Planting Stock.....	214
• 23.4 Plantation Operation.....	214
23.4.1 Plantation Materials	214
23.4.2 Handling of Planting Stock.....	214
23.4.3 Transportation of the Planting Stock	214
23.4.4 Site Preparation	214
• 23.5 Tending Operations	215
MODULE 24: PESTICIDES APPLICATION, HANDLING AND MANAGEMENT	215
• 24.1 Training Objectives.....	215
• 24.2 Pest identification, Recognition and Control	216
• 24.3 PESTICIDE CLASSIFICATION AND APPLICATION	220
• 24.4 PESTICIDE LABELING	226
• 24.5 SAFETY PRECAUTIONS WHEN HANDLING PESTICIDES.....	234

• 24.6 TYPES OF SPRAYING EQUIPMENT AND SPRAYER CALIBRATION	236
• 24.6 APPLYING PESTICIDES DURING STORAGE	245
• 24.7 HERBICIDE APPLICATION.....	248
• 24.8 PESTICIDES POISONING AND FIRST AID	252
• 24.9 PRACTICALS	257
MODULE 25: ENVIRONMENTAL/SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS	261
• 25.1 Overview	261
• 25.2 Introduction:	262
• 25.3 Identification of Local Actors	262
• 25.4: Creating Awareness	262
• 25.5 Identification of Environmental Factors and Implications	263
• 25.6 Identification of Social Factors and Implications.....	263
• 25.7 Mitigating Measures	264
• 25.8 Follow-up.....	264
• 25.9 EIA ON ENERGY EFFICIENT STOVES (EES)	264
25.9.1 Introduction.....	265

SECTION I: LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION PRACTICES

MODULE I: IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL CHICKENS

- **I.1. Introduction**

Indigenous chickens are widely distributed in the rural areas of tropical and sub-tropical countries where they are kept by the majority of the rural poor. The chickens are hardy, adaptive to rural environments, survive on little or no inputs and adjust to fluctuations in feed availability. There is a need to pay proper attention to the development of local chickens, bearing in mind their potentials for rural poverty alleviation and animal protein food security. It is a system that is not only viable but sustainable. They are most often managed by the women who provide them with an independent source of income. It is known that a broody hen that produces 60 eggs and 2-3 slaughter birds per year can provide 4kg meat per head which is significantly higher than the annual protein consumption in the rural areas. The Nigerian poultry industry will ultimately get improved performance when the Fulani chickens are crossbred with exotic dual-purpose breeds e.g. Plymouth Rock.

I.1.1 Learning Objectives

Beneficiaries should be able to:

- Maintain a high level of sanitation in the poultry house.
- Clean feeders and drinkers daily.
- Provide a balanced and adequate diet with clean water always.
- Formulate rations (mix) using locally available feedstuffs.
- Use poultry droppings as manure for the home garden.
- Keep a record on the stock number, health management, expenditures and income

I.1.2 Advantages of keeping local chickens

The popularity of village chicken is because of the following merits:

- Local fowls are adapted to local climate and harsh ecological conditions.
- Their products (meat and eggs) are sources of high-quality animal protein for households.
- The meat is portable, easily prepared and low in fat.
- They are more suitable for extensive (free range) system of production as they make better use of garbage than hybrid chickens.

- Imported production inputs are not required.
- Local chickens suffer less poultry diseases than the more fragile hybrids.
- In many cities, the village chicken's meat is preferred to that of commercial broilers because it has better texture and stronger flavour. This is reflected in the price of the village chicken which is twice that of the industrial broiler.
- The birds are conveniently sized and can easily be transported.

1.1.3 Nutritional Importance of Egg

Eggs contain almost every nutrient. They provide 77 calories, 6 grams of protein, 2 grams carbohydrates and 5 grams of healthy fats. Eggs are rich sources of lecithin, vitamins (A, D, E, K, B2, B6, B9, and B12) and minerals such as selenium, phosphorus, zinc, iron, and copper.

1.1.4 Indigenous Poultry Breeds

The most commonly kept Indigenous breed of chicken in Nigeria is not an official breed and does not have a breed standard; the Fulani chicken and the Yoruba chicken. The only real difference between them is that the Fulani's types are a little larger, some of the indigenous breeds have either "frizzle" or "necked neck" genes.

1.1.5 Existing Peasant Production System

The usual practice in most villages is to raise local chickens extensively, allowing them to scavenge the village and surrounding area. Local Chickens live on seeds, insects, worms, leaves, green grassed and kitchen scraps. The village hen lays a dozen eggs, takes 3 weeks to hatch out a brood of chicks, stays with the chicks six weeks or more, and only then starts laying again. The scavenger hen can begin to lay at about 6 months of age.

Fig. 1: Local chickens

1.1.6 Choice of Foundation Stock

In judging chickens for use as foundation stocks, the conformation, body size and the correct colour of the variety are the most important factors to be taken into consideration. The foundation birds must be free of defects and diseases. The qualities to look for in a good layer hen are:

- Red, large and waxy combs
- Large and soft wattles and ear lobes
- Pliable and wide apart pelvic bones
- Large, oblong and wet cloaca

1.1.7 Selection of a Good Cock for Upgrading

Since one cock is usually mated to about eight hens, a cock's prolific ability is more valuable in the improvement of next generation. The choice is based on:

- Good conformation/body size
- Strong legs, sharp eyes
- Freedom from defects and diseases
- Alertness, attractiveness and high sex drive
- The combs/wattles also have to be bright red and soft.

Note: The Plymouth Rock cock is a recommended breed that can be obtained from Sovet International, Kano State.

Fig. 1: Plymouth Rock cock

1.1.8 The Reproductive Cycle of Local Hen

1. The laying phase (10 days)
2. Incubation phase (21 days)
3. The brooding phase (about 56 days)

Egg production is usually in two to three clutches per hen per year with about ten eggs per clutch. Hatchability is good (80%) and compares favorably with the performance of improved birds.

Chick mortality is highest during the dry season because of reduced availability of water hence there should be adequate provision of water.

The level of fertile egg production is in the range of 20 - 30 eggs per annum (i.e. a mean clutch size of 8-9 eggs and 2.5 clutches per year).

Separation of chicks from the hen at four weeks of age can reduce the interval between the broody periods and increase the number of clutches. The reproductive cycle of hens can be shortened by reducing stress, improving the quality and quantity of feed, protecting birds from predators and rodents, timely vaccinations, control of both internal and external parasites as well as getting rid of aggressive and unproductive birds.

1.1.9 Identification of Poor Producing Birds

Non-laying or low producing hens should be identified and removed from the laying flock. Removal of undesirable animals from the herd can be for the following reasons:

- Uneconomic- poor production,
- Very poor reproductive ability, with sterility problems and breeding, irregularities,
- Very poor conditions, stunted growth,
- Suffering from an incurable illness, or birds with infectious diseases.

Characteristics of these hens include pullets that are a few months later in starting to lay than the average of the flock, possession of dull colour and shrivelled combs, long, narrow serrations on the comb, shrunken, hard to the touch, and covered with whitish scales; deep eyes; Small, weak, deformed, inactive hens with long beaks and heads, absence of yellow pigment in vent, eye ring, beak, skin, and shank, round, dry and wrinkled cloaca

- **1.2 Housing/ Shelter and Facilities**

Most local chicken keepers in Nigeria provide some form of shelter for their birds at night. This varies from the use of spare rooms which are usually kitchens, stores, wire/wooden cages to the building of a "Companion house". The companion house is a small mud structure of about one-meter-high attached to the main building.

1.2.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn about facilities necessary for providing adequate chicken houses
2. Be knowledgeable about preparing different laying nests
3. Learn about the need for the provision of perches for local chickens

Fig. 2: Different types of chicken shelters

1.2.3 The Chicken House

Build local chickens houses using easily available and cheap materials such as bamboo, raffia sticks/wood, thatch, mud etc.

Local Chicken House Facilities

- Drinker - a bowl of water with the protector

- Feeder (feeding trough) - bamboo feeder, wooden feeder, and local clay pot. A narrow feeder such that will not allow the mother entrance and scatter feeds is advised.

1.2.4 Laying Nest

Chickens need individual nests for egg-laying. They can be made of wood or other locally available materials such as bamboo and orchard type of grasses. They need to be stocked with a thick layer of litter to prevent eggs from breaking.

Fig. 3: Different laying nests for hens

1.2.5 Perches

Chickens like to spend the night on perches in high places. Perches are usually made of wood. Trees can also be used as perches.

Fig. 4 Different Perches for hens

- **1.3 Feeding, Water and Health Care**

Local chickens require carbohydrates, proteins, minerals and vitamins in their diet if they are to produce maximally. The birds are usually left to scavenge in the surrounding. It is important to feed the birds with a complete and balanced diet. It is important therefore, that the chickens get extra, especially animal protein such as worms, insects, snails etc. Otherwise, they must be given extra plant protein-rich ingredients.

In dry periods, a vitamin deficiency condition can quickly develop. Feed supplement containing wood ash, dried greens, crayfish dust, and fruits could be added to their diets to supply some of the minerals and vitamins they need.

For maximum productivity under the free-range system, green food should be introduced as early as 10 days of life, additional green food such as chopped lettuce, spinach or onions can be introduced gradually until they attain the age of 5 weeks. There should be an unlimited supply of water.

1.3.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Quantity of ration to feed chickens
2. Learn about supplementary diet formulations for different classes of local chickens

3. Health care, parasite and disease control

1.3.2 Quantity of Ration to Feed

An adult chicken will need 100-150 gm. of feed a day, depending on the body size and production level accompanied by adequate water. Birds on range particularly during the rainy/cropping season may pick between 65-70gm of their daily feed needs and the balance should be provided from formulated feeds.

Table 1: Supplementary diet formulations for different classes of local chickens

Ingredients (Kg)*	Chicks (0-5wks)	Growers (5-25wks)	Adults/layers (25wks)
Maize, Guinea corn, sweet potato peels etc.	45.0	42.0	35.0
Offals of Maize/Guinea corn	34.0	43.0	45.0
Full fat soybean/groundnut cake	15.0	10.0	10.0
Bone ash	2.5	2.5	3.5
Limestone	0.0	0.0	4.5
Common salt	0.25	0.25	0.25
Wood ash/Greens	0.75	0.75	0.75
<i>Moringa</i> seed	1.5	1.5	1.0
Total	100	100	100

**Locally available equivalent measure to be used for quantifying ingredients*

Practical Session:

Demonstrate how to formulate a ration for local chickens using the above locally available ingredients.

1.3.3 Health Care

A. External Parasites

Hens should be regularly dusted with Selvin Asuntol or Katzimet etc. to keep them free of external parasites such as lice, mites, and ticks.

B. Internal Parasites

These parasites are roundworms, tapeworms, threadworms etc.

C. Control

If parasites are discovered in the faecal droppings of the birds, recommended deworming drugs should be bought from the local veterinary store for administration. Also, protect birds from contaminated water and feeds.

D. Diseases

Newcastle disease is of considerable economic importance because of the severity and the nature of its attack. Signs from such affected birds usually include diarrhoea, twisting of the neck ruffled feather and redness of the eye. A high percentage of affected birds die of the disease within one week. Other diseases to watch out for in free-range chicken production are coccidiosis, fowl pox and fowl cholera.

E. Control

Prevention by vaccination (NDV Vaccine) is highly recommended. Vaccinate at day old, 4 weeks (*Lasota*) and 16 – 18 weeks (*Kamarov*) administered in drinking water. In general, to be on the safe side, farmers should ensure that all feeders and drinkers are kept clean. Ensure a high level of sanitation in the poultry house and provide an adequate diet with clean water.

- **It is vital to vaccinate birds against prevalent diseases**

Vaccination	Age
NDV (<i>Lasota</i>)	4 weeks
Fowl Fox	6 - 7 weeks
Fowl Typhoid	6 - 7 weeks
Fowl Cholera	6 - 7 weeks
NDV (<i>Kamarov</i>)	16 -18 weeks

F. Poisons

Poisonings can occur when mouldy feed containing toxins are eaten or accidental feeding on insecticides, herbicides and grain preservatives.

- **1.4 Processing and Use**

1.4.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn the ways slaughtering birds
2. Learn about record keeping
3. Monitoring and evaluation indicators to watch out for

1.4.2 Slaughtering

Birds that are earmarked for slaughter should be deprived of feeds for 8-10 hours to ensure empty guts for easy cleaning. Adequate water should be made available.

- **1.5 Record Keeping**

Record keeping in local chicken production should not be too elaborate nor complicated. It should, however, ensure improved management practices and profitability assessment. An example of such simple record keeping is as shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Record keeping in poultry rearing

S/N	Bird Records	Number
A.	Production Records	
1.	Total number of on-farm birds ----- Number of cocks ----- Number of hens----- Number of Chicks-----	
2.	Total number of eggs laid-----	
B.	Health Record	
1.	Number of eggs per clutch----- Number of clutches per annum----- Incubation date. ----- Hatching date----- Number of chicks hatched ----- Mortality ----- Vaccination ----- Deworming date ----- Dusting date Medication date ----- type-----	
C.	Expenditure Record	
1.	Cost of foundation stock purchase ----- Shelter ----- Equipment ----- Feed ----- Vaccination/medication ----- Labour ----- Total -----	
D.	Income Records	
1.	Sales of live chickens ----- Sales of eggs -----	

• **1.6 Monitoring and Evaluation**

Chickens

1. How many chickens are available
2. Has any of the chickens died
3. How many eggs were laid
4. How many of the eggs were used for home consumption
5. How many of the eggs were hatched
6. How many of the chicks died
7. Has any of the chicken been sold
8. Do the chickens receive supplementary feeding in addition to free-range feeding
9. Do the chickens have a house and a perching place
10. Is the chicken house clean
11. Do the chickens have feeding and drinking containers
12. Are the feeding and drinking containers clean
13. Has any of the chickens had health problems
14. If yes, what health problem was observed a. New Castle disease (NDV)
b. Wet Droppings c. Coccidiosis d. Fowl Pox e. Others
(Specify).....
15. Which animal specialist was contacted for treatment of the disease a.
Community animal care b. Extension Agent c. Veterinarian d. Others
(Specify)
16. What feed is given to the chickens on a daily basis? a. Grains b. maize or
a combination of brans c. Formulated feed d. Others
(Specify).....
17. Is there proper record kept for the chickens (Please observe)

• **1.7 Key Messages**

- Ensure a high level of sanitation in the poultry house.
- Farmers should ensure that all feeders and drinkers are cleaned daily.
- Provide an adequate diet with clean water.
- Simple feed ration can be formulated using locally available foodstuff.
- Use poultry droppings as manure for the home garden.
- Record on stock number, health management, expenditures and income should be kept.

1.8 Bibliography

National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS) 2000:
Improving the performance of local chickens. Extension bulletin, NO
92. Poultry series NO. 6.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plymouth_Rock_chicken

<https://www.backyardchickencoops.com.au/blogs/learning-centre/8-reasons-why-your-laying-hens-have-stopped-producing-eggs>
<https://backyardpoultry.iamcountryside.com/chickens-101/how-to-raise-free-range-chickens/>

Video Links:

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/making-business-home-raised-chicks>
<https://www.accessagriculture.org/taking-care-local-chickens>
<https://www.accessagriculture.org/preparing-low-cost-concentrate-feed>

MODULE 2: IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL GOATS

• 2.1 Introduction

Goats have been traditionally raised for meat and milk. Their small size and low cost of maintenance has made them popular among small scale farmers. The benefits of local goat production include:

- Better digestion of its fat and protein content than cow milk and beef,
- High Vitamin A and calcium content.
- Beneficial for people who have cow milk allergy or stomach ulcer.
- Droppings from these animals also improve soil fertility of farms.

2.1.1 Learning Objectives

Beneficiaries should be able to:

- Maintain good hygiene in the goat house
- Kids receive colostrum soon after birth.
- Introduce kids to roughage (chopped grasses and maize stover) by the second week and supplements (0.25kg of vitamins and minerals) by the fourth week.
- Wean kids by 3 months.
- Increase the plane of nutrition before mating and after birth.
- Vaccinate and deworm goats timely.
- Keep record of total expenditure and income of production.

2.1.2 Available Breed of Goat in Yobe State

A. Borno Sahel goats

The Borno Sahel goats are among the few breeds in Nigeria. They are characterized by their fine short coat with colours ranging from white, black,

red or a combination of all these colours. They have a medium to large body size with long legs which are well adapted to trekking. Males weigh an average of 25 to 30kg while females weigh an average of 20 to 25kg. The breed is predominant in Borno/Yobe States, Nigeria.

Quarantine - It is ideal to quarantine goats after being purchased especially from open markets for at least two weeks and any observed disease/infection treated appropriately. Meanwhile, some first aid materials and drugs should be provided such as Vitalyte, Glucose and some antibiotics as well as wound dressing materials.

Fig. 4: Borno Sahel goats

2.1.3. Nutritional Importance of Goat Milk and Meat

Goat milk consists of 4.5% fat, 3.6% protein, 4.3% lactose, and 0.8% minerals, indicating that it has slightly more total solid, fat, total protein, casein, minerals, and less lactose than cow and human milk. It contains less Alpha-S1-Casein protein and lactose hence it can be consumed by individuals that can't tolerate cow milk. Goats milk is a good source of protein, contains less sugar (lactose), 13% more calcium, 25% more vitamin B6, 47% more vitamin A, and 134% more potassium than regular cow's milk.

Goat meat is lower in calories, saturated fats, and cholesterol than beef, pork, lamb and chicken. It also contains a higher amount of protein and more iron than beef.

- **2.2 Site Selection and Housing**

Sites should be dry, suitable for keeping the feed in good condition, waste

storage and other facilities. Goat houses should be located about 165 feet away from wells and other water sources.

2.2.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn appropriate roofing materials for goats
2. Learn systems of management
3. Learn about necessary equipment needed for a successful goat production

2.2.2 Roof materials

The house can be built with either block or mud with thatched or zinc roof respectively.

Fig. 5: Sample of goat shades

2.2.3 Floors

Low-level floor beds are the most favourable type of flooring in goat housing. Examples of bedding materials include wood shavings, sawdust, tree leaves etc. The floors can be made of rammed earth clay or rough concrete that can be easily cleaned.

2.2.4 System of Management

A semi-intensive system of management should be practiced. The goats should be allowed to move around within the house for easy monitoring and supplementary feeding.

2.2.5 Equipment

Feeders made from metal (cut drums) and plastic drinkers located properly to avoid feed and water contamination with animal wastes.

• 2.3 Nutrition

2.3.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn about feeding of kids
2. Knowledgeable about feeding of adult goats

2.3.2 Feeding kids

- Kids should receive colostrum (first mother's milk) soon after birth to provide necessary nutrients and antibodies to protect them from diseases.
- If this cannot be obtained from the mother, other sources available (e.g. other mothers within the herd, cow colostrum, etc.) could be used.
- Provide one litre (four medium cups) of milk per day depending on the kid-size.
- Introduce kids to roughage (chopped grasses and maize leaves and stalks) by the second week and supplements (0.25kg of vitamins and minerals) by the fourth week.
- Wean kids by 3 months.
- Provide artificial/locally prepared (as alternative) colostrum for orphaned kids: (an egg, half litre of fresh warm water, half litre whole milk, one teaspoonful of castor oil and similar amount of cod liver oil and a pill of a broad-spectrum antibiotic then mix thoroughly).

2.3.4 Feeding Adult Goats

Adequate and fresh food and water is essential for good meat and milk production. Energy and protein are the most important elements to consider in the diet.

- Examples of energy sources are molasses and cereals (maize bran ('Dusa'), rice bran, wheat bran, yam, sweet potato, and cocoyam peels while protein sources are (fish meal, cottonseed cake and groundnut cake).
- The energy and protein sources could be mixed together with some mineral supplements (limestone and bone meal or local potash i.e 'Kanwa').
- Fresh grasses, hay, silage or pasture plants should be cut or chopped and given to them. Examples include Napier, *Desmodium*, *Leucaena*, and groundnut haulms ('Harawa').
- Increase the quality and quantity of feed before mating and after birth.

• 2.4 Daily Routine Husbandry Practices

Along with providing good housing, the goats need some special care and management. Thus, they can be managed by members of a group for feeding, watering, observation, and medication. A routine schedule can be made by the group for the roles and responsibilities of group members for the goats' care.

2.4.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn about good feeding practices
2. Learn about identification of poor producing goats

2.4.2 Good Feeding Practices

For continuous optimum and profitable income:

- Always feed them fresh, high quality, and nutritious feed; try to avoid used or contaminated feed.
- Always serve goats sufficient fresh and clean water.
- Always provide veterinary services and vaccinate your goats timely (as recommended by NVRI).
- Never include urea in the feed because it is toxic to goats.
- It is important to routinely monitor the growth of the goats.
- When there are too many males, castrate some of them to reduce unnecessary fight. Castration also prevents the development of typical odour.
- Keep a record of total expenditure and income of your production.

Fig. 6 Water Trough for goats

2.4.3 Identification of Poor Producing Goats

Removal of undesirable animals from the herd, for reasons of low production, or very poor reproductive ability, with sterility problems and breeding irregularities, very poor conditions, stunted growth and suffering from an incurable illness. Animals to be removed from the flock include disabled animals due to injury or loss of organs, blind animals, extremely lame goats, unhealed fractured animals, females with an excess number of teats etc. come under the animal proposed for removal from the flock.

• 2.5 Breeding and Gestation

1. Males of about 1 year of age should be used for breeding, while females should be between 8-12 months of age. Breeding stock should be obtained from a very good source.
2. Identify a good breeding male goat (buck) that has no deformities, strong legs, and feet with two well-developed testicles. Select breeding females (doe) that have good body condition, high twinning ability, strong legs, soft udder (breast), and two functional teats.
3. The mating ratio is one male to 15 females.
4. Provision of good quality feed at the time of breeding and during pregnancy especially during the last two months is important.
5. Pregnancy lasts for five months and can be detected by progressive enlargement of the abdomen and udder.

2.5.1 Learning Objectives

At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

1. Learn about the mating and gestation period of goats
2. Know about how to prepare for kidding
3. Learn about herd health and biosecurity
4. Learn about sanitation and waste management.

2.5.2 Kidding

Two weeks to kidding prepare the kidding pen. The pen should be clean, dry, well ventilated and provided with fresh bedding. A bottle of iodine (for treating the navel of the newly born kid) and a soft cloth should also be provided. On the day of birth, the goat becomes restless and will alternate between standing and lying down. She will no longer eat or drink, the udder is long and stretched out and she will isolate herself. A long thread of slime

hangs out of the vagina. The goat should not be sent out for grazing at this stage rather should be monitored closely.

2.5.3 Herd Health and Biosecurity

The following health care practices should be observed:

- Good hygiene should be maintained in the goat house.
- Ensure that feeding and milking utensils are kept clean at all times.
- Provide good quality concentrate and roughages.
- Quarterly de-worm the goats against internal parasites such as roundworm, tapeworm and flukes using deworming medication (antihelminth e.g. Albendazole).
- Eliminate external parasites such as ticks by spraying substances that kill ticks and mites (Acaricides).
- Routine vaccination should be carried out.
- Ensure proper identification of goats using an ear-tag or tattoo (this will help in isolating infected animals).
- Provision of sanitary conditions, good milking procedures, well-ventilated housing, and dry bedding are the best defences against the disease called Mastitis.
- Foot rot's treatments involve cutting away the under-run hoof to expose the diseased tissues to the air, which improves healing.
- Cutting knives and shears should be disinfected with 10% solution of zinc sulphate, 5% formalin and 5% copper Sulphate or sprayed with antibiotic aerosol).

Vaccination Schedule for Goats

S/N	Name of Disease	Primary Vaccination (Age-Months)	Regular Vaccination
1	Anthrax	6	Once Annually (In affected area)
2	Haemorrhagic Septicaemia (H.S.)	6	Once Annually
3	Enterotoxaemia	4	
4	Black Quarter (B.Q.)	6	Once Annually
5	PPR	3	Once in 3 years
6	FMD	4	Twice (Sept. & March)
7	Goat Fox	3	Once (December) in one year
8	CCPP	3	Once Annually

Note: Parasites, both internal and external, are the most important health concern for goat health and productivity. Good nutrition, good

sanitation, rotating pastures and feeding hay and other forage in racks pay off as are good internal parasite control practices. Pour-on medication can minimize the menace of the external parasite. Report any sudden death to nearest veterinary clinic for post-mortem examination of carcass/proper diagnosis.

2.5.4 Sanitation and Waste Management

Waste from dairy goats could be managed by collection, storage, and utilization in an environmentally sustainable manner. The following should be taken into consideration:

- Ensure that goat houses are kept clean all the time.
- Goat droppings should be packed from the house regularly into sacs to prevent a build-up of ammonia.
- Goat manure is a rich source of nitrogen for crops, hence can be used to improve the fertility of farmlands.

• 2.6 Key Messages

- A semi-intensive management system should be practiced
- Good hygiene should be maintained in the goat house
- Kids should receive colostrum soon after birth to provide the necessary nutrients and antibodies to protect them from the disease.
- Introduce kids to roughage (chopped grasses and maize stover) by the second week and supplements (0.25kg of vitamins and minerals) by the fourth week.
- Wean kids by 3 months.
- Increase the plane of nutrition before mating and after parturition.
- Vaccinate and deworm your goats timely.
- Keep a record of total expenditure and income of your production.

• 2.7 Monitoring and Evaluation

Goats

1. How many goats are available
2. Has any of the goats given birth
3. Has any of the goats died
4. Has any of your goats been sold
5. Has any of the goats been slaughtered for household consumption
6. Do they receive supplementary feeding addition to free-range grazing
7. Do the goats have a pen

8. Is the goat pen clean
9. Do the goats have feeding and drinking containers
10. Are the feeding and drinking containers clean
11. Has any of the goats had health problems
12. If yes, what health problem was observed a. Diarrhoea b. Mastitis c. Respiratory problem d. Others (Specify).....
13. Which animal specialist was contacted for treatment of the disease a. Community animal care b. Extension Agent c. Veterinarian d. Others (Specify)
14. What feed is given to the goats on a daily basis? a. Forage b. maize or a combination of brans c. Formulated feed d. Others (Specify).....
15. Is there proper record kept for the goats (Please observe)

2.5.7 Bibliography

N-Power (AGRO) Training Manual for Extension Advisors (2000).
 Produced by NAERLS and Sasakawa African Association/SG2000.
 Edited by M.K. Othman, A.O. Lawal and A.O. Iyiola-Tunji.
 Sheep and Goat Production. National Agricultural Extension Research
 Liaison Services (NAERLS). Extension Bulletin No 46. Livestock
 Series No 8.

<http://agritech.tnau.ac.in/animalhusbandary/animhus>

www.alamy.com

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809762-5.00035-8>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sahelian_goat

<https://www.agriculturenigeria.com/research/common-indigenous-goat-breed-in-nigeria/>

Video links:

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/making-raised-platform-sheep-and-goats>

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/dairy-goat-feeding>

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/herbal-treatment-diarrhoea>

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/deworming-goats-and-sheep-herbal-medicines>

<https://www.accessagriculture.org/slm11-farmers-pastoralists>

https://www.kya_chevre_rousse_october_2015_en.pdf

MODULE 3: FEEDS AND FEEDING IN SMALL RUMINANTS

• 3.1 Introduction

Yobe State have livelihood zones, among them is livestock production. Ruminants are the major livestock reared in the State. Small ruminants are second only to crops in providing livelihoods to rural and peri-urban dwellers in form of food (both meat and milk), income, nutrients to the soil, employment, insurance, and raw materials to agro-allied industries. Most of the ruminants in Yobe State are managed under range-livestock production system and crop-based livestock production system. Small ruminants require feeds for maintenance, growth, reproduction and production. In Yobe State, climate is characterized by dry and rainy seasons. During rainy season there is abundance of herbage however, in the dry season sometimes forage availability is zero, rangelands are degrading due to high stocking rate and management which leads to over grazing. The acute feed shortage results low growth development, increases diseases susceptibility, lower reproductive performance and general decline in productivity of small ruminants in the State.

Learning objectives: At the end of this training the participants are expected to:

- i. Identify common feedstuffs and their limitation(s) in dryland area
- ii. Identify available non-conventional feedstuff(s) in dryland area
- iii. Able to conserve forage
- iv. Understand feeding strategy during dry season

Nutrients

For profitable small ruminants' production nutrients requirements have to be met. Nutrients requirement changes with body weight and the requirement is much higher during gestation and lactation. Feeds are made of up nutrients. These nutrients are water, energy, proteins, vitamins and minerals. They are released during digestion and absorbed in the digestion tract. Nutrients have three metabolic functions and are:

- i. It provides raw materials for the synthesis of body tissues and products
- ii. It regulates metabolism of other nutrients, and
- iii. Provide energy to the body

• 3.2 Small ruminants feed resources in Yobe State

Rangelands/Pastures: Except in private farms pasture is not usually produced in the State. Therefore, rangeland is one of the major feed resources found in Yobe State. Sheep and goats raised under these conditions graze on

degraded rangelands and or supplemented with low quality feedstuffs such as crop residues. Nutrient contents of these feed resources are so low and unbalanced that the provision of complements is necessary for livestock maintenance and production. Concentrate feeds such as wheat bran, groundnut cake (GNC), cotton seed cake (CSC) etc. are commonly used to achieve the said objective.

Crop residues: Crop residues are major feed resources for small ruminant in the State. The major residues of cereal crops include millet, sorghum, rice and maize while for legumes the major residues are haulms of cowpea and groundnut. The cereals crop residues are characterised with low crude protein, high amount of fibrous material and low dry matter digestibility. While those of legumes have higher crude protein compared with cereals residues with higher digestibility. Other residues include maize cob, sugarcane tops and bagasse, soy bean residue. If their limitation is improved, optimum utilisation of the resources will reduce feed shortage during its scarcity.

Agro-industrial by-products (AGIBPs): Recycling, reprocessing and utilization of any AGIBPs offer the possibility of alleviating the current limited feed resources and to reduce feeding cost. AGIBPs refer to the by-products obtained from the industry due to processing of the main products. Compared with crop residues, agro-industrial by-products are less fibrous and more concentrated, and often have a high nutrient content. Some of these by-products can be classified as concentrates for both the energy and proteins. The by-products available within the State are: brans of wheat and rice, wheat offal, rice offal, GNC, CSC, brewers dried grain (BDG), molasses, multi-nutrients block etc., the major source of worry with by-products is the small-holder farmers cannot afford them as they are relatively expensive.

Forage conservation

Excess forage harvested in the growing season and stored for feeding in dry season is the basis for feeding in most ruminant production systems. The forage can either be stored dry, as hay, or as silage. The method of conservation will be influenced by climate, what the conserved forage is to be used for, the tools and machinery available and the feeding system (Payne, 1990).

Forage that is conserved with high amount of moisture is considered silage, while that with low moisture content is known as hay.

Hay is harvested when the plant reaches the flowering stage and there are good drying conditions, such as low humidity and air movement, these are more important than still sunny weather. There is need to turn the crop in

order to allow the air to penetrate the swath, or placing on racks or tripods. When dry it should be stored under cover, but air must be able to circulate in the stack to minimize the risk of mould formation.

Silage is the storing of forages or fodder under anaerobic conditions, created by compaction of the material and exclusion of air, to allow the conversion of plant sugars to lactic acid, of green forage, as cut or after wilting, especially necessary for succulent crops. Crops low in fermentable carbohydrates may need an additive, e.g. molasses, maize meal or a purchased product, to ensure this. The stage at which the crop is cut will depend on whether it is needed as high energy/high protein feed, when it will be cut at an early stage, or as a bulk feed, when nutritive value will be lower but the quantity harvested will be greater (Payne, 1990).

Practical session: Demonstration of silage making.

References

Herrero M, Thornton PK, Gerber P, Reid RS (2009) Livestock, livelihoods and the environment: understanding the trade-offs. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 1 (2):111-120.

Payne, W.J.A. (1990). An Introduction to Animal Husbandry in the Tropics, fifth edition. Longman Ltd., London, UK, 881 pp.

- **3.3 Small ruminants' diseases and management**

3.3.1 Introduction

Health can be defined as the state of being that allows sustainable, optimum productivity. While disease can be defined as the state of being that prevents optimal productivity. Diseases and parasitic infections are problems limiting small ruminant production worldwide. Economic losses include decrease in production, cost of prevention, cost of treatment, and possible death of infected animals. The effect of diseases and parasitic infection are influenced by host, management practice and disease or parasitic factors. There are essential and sufficient causes of diseases. In essence, the cause of diseases is impossible to replace such as causative organisms or nutritional deficiency where as in sufficient cause is about contributory factors that make diseases to occur such as transmitter or management practices.

Learning objectives

- Address basic health issues that are associated with small ruminant production
- Identify signs and symptoms of the diseases and parasites

Identification of Sick Animals

Diseases is one of the major problems that decrease livestock productivity and, in many instances, results in serious economic losses in farm animals. It saves a lot of money and unpleasantness if sheep and goats are and remain healthy because of good care. A sick sheep and goat will be noticed as it differs from the rest of the herd. Especially for acute (quickly developing) diseases, the symptoms/signs are often obvious. The condition of the animal suddenly changes. Rapid intervention is necessary because acute can also mean fast declining; in that case you may lose your animal. With chronic (long-lasting) diseases, the signs are not as obvious. Sometimes you will only notice that a sheep or goat is getting thin and produces less. Such diseases are therefore difficult to detect. By comparing with other goats within the herd and of neighbouring herds, you should be able to see whether or not you are dealing with a chronic disease or not.

3.3.2 Important infectious diseases

The most common infectious diseases i.e. disease transmissible from one animal to the other, are:

i) *Pestis des petits ruminans* (PPR)

Goats are more susceptible to PPR than sheep. Adolescent goats (6 months) suffer most. The disease has seasonal occurrence with outbreaks seen mainly during the cold dusty months of harmattan and during the early rainy season. More than half or all animals in the herd may be infected, death may also take similar pattern. The incidence of this disease can be reduced by raising the level of immunity in adult animals before lambing/kidding. The process protects offspring of such animals for upwards of 3 months.

ii) Contagious *caprine* pleuro-pneumonia (CCPP)

This disease is caused by a bacterium, *Mycoplasma mycoides var capri*, is spread by drop infection (nasal mucus), when kept permanently stalled, the entire herd can be infected. Death rate can rise to 100%. Signs include rapid breathing, with coughing, the animal groans when breathing out and usually, secretes much nasal fluid.

iii) Mastitis: Mastitis or udder infection is a disease found all over the world. Both acute and chronic forms are found. Bacteria of the type staphylococcus and streptococcus are usually the cause. In particular poor hygienic conditions in the stall and unhygienic milking promote

the disease, production decreases strongly among affected animals and the milk is not suitable for human consumption.

- Other infectious diseases of sheep and goats include Brucellosis, Ecthyma, Anthrax, Foot-and-mouth disease, pasteurellosis etc.

Disease Due to Feeding Mistakes

A sudden transmission from one kind of feed to another can easily cause digestive problems in sheep and goats. Two frequently occurring problems are Bloat (tympanitis) and Diarrhoea.

Mineral Deficiencies

Minerals such as salt, calcium, phosphorus, iron, copper, and iodine are important for the proper functioning of life processes of sheep and goats. A shortage is only noticed after the animal has used up its reserves, the deficiencies have then existed for quite some time. Signs of mineral deficiencies include, decreasing appetite, declining fertility, a dull coat and poor growth. The animal licks at all kinds of objects and even eats them, in an attempt to satisfy its mineral needs. Always provide mineral salt lick to sheep and goat in the form of **salt lick**.

Parasites

Stomach and intestinal worms, lice, mites, and ticks, are a very serious health problem of sheep and goats. Parasites rob important nutrients from your animals. Prevention and treatment of parasites is important to the productivity of your herd. Good nutrition, good sanitation, rotating pastures and feeding hay and other forage racks placed off from the ground are good internal parasite prevention practices. Ticks are a serious problem particularly in the tropics. They are not ingested but attach themselves to the animal spreading disease through the blood and taking nutrition from your animal. A good management program must be in place to prevent fatal diseases. Pour-on medication can minimize the menace of the external parasite.

Bibliography

Kusiluka, L. and Kambarage, D. (1996). Diseases of small ruminants in sub-Saharan Africa: a handbook

Miller, J. E; Olcott, B. and Bath, G. F. (2010). Health management, diseases and parasites. In: Goat science and production (Ed) Solaiman, S. G. Blackwell publishing

Sheep and Goat Production. National Agricultural Extension Research Liaison Services (NAERLS). Extension Bulletin No 46. Livestock Series No 8

SECTION II: BEST PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SOME FOOD CROPS.

MODULE 4: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SORGHUM (SORGHUM BICOLOR L.) AND PEARL MILLET (PENNISETUM GLAUCUM L.)

• 4.1 Introduction

Sorghum belongs to the grass family *Poaceae*, together with maize, wheat, barley, pearl millet and finger millet. It is essential that farmers know the crop they are cultivating to adopt the most effective production practices. Sorghum has an extensive root system which aids efficient moisture extraction and a smaller leaf area which reduces water loss through evapo-transpiration; the leaves have a waxy cuticle that retards drying. Drought conditions stop growth before flower initiation and plant remains vegetative, only resuming leaf production and flowering when conditions become more favorable. These features assist to make sorghum and pearl millet drought tolerant.

• 4.2 Good Agronomic Practices (Gap) for Sorghum and Pearl Millet Production

I. Ecological Requirements:

- The best time to plant is when there is sufficient water in the soil and the soil temperature is 15 °C or higher at a depth of 10 cm.
- Temperature plays an important role in growth and development after germination. A temperature of 27-30°C is required for optimum growth and development.

- Sorghum and pearl millet is grown mostly in areas with an annual rainfall range of 300-750 mm/annum. It is grown in areas which are too dry for maize as crop is drought tolerant.
- Sorghum and pearl millet can be grown on many different soils but best yields are obtained on deep, fertile, well-drained loamy soils. However, it is quite tolerant of shallow soil and droughty conditions.
- Sorghum and pearl millet grows poorly on sandy soils, except where heavy textured subsoil is present.
- The crop is more tolerant of alkaline salts than other grain crops and can therefore be cultivated successfully on soils with a pH between 5.5 - 8.5.
- Sorghum and millet can better tolerate short periods of waterlogging compared to maize. Soils with a clay percentage of between 10 and 30 % are optimal for sorghum production.

2. Variety Selection

While selecting the sorghum and millet variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a particular area. Seeds of the sorghum variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety should be suitable for the soil condition in the selected field. Hence the factors to consider are summarized below:

- The growing period (days to maturity: Early maturing),
- Yield potential, (High yielding)
- Susceptibility to bird damage/losses,
- Pest and disease resistance. (striga, stem borers, anthracnose, smuts)
- Good domestic and industrial utilization.

• 4.3 Promising Sorghum Cultivars Obtained in North Eastern Nigeria and their Qualities

1. SAMSORG 45 (12NICSV188)

Drought tolerant and matures earlier (80-100 days), flowers in 67 days, high iron content and with yield potential of 2.5-3 t/ha.

2. SAMSORG 46 (KNICSV-22)

Dwarf, high iron content, required spacing 110-120 cm between rows and 30 cm between stands; matures in 90-110 days and it is drought tolerant; yield potential 2-3 t/ha; suitable for Sudano-Sahelian region.

3. ICSV400

Medium height, white seed, early maturing (90-100 days), suitable to all parts of North Eastern zone and with yield potential of 1.8-3 t/ha.

- **4.4 Promising Pearl millet cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.**

1. **SAMMIL-I (EX-Borno)**

Grows in all parts of North Eastern states, early maturing (70-90 days); resistant to major diseases of millet and yield potential 2-3 t/ha.

2. **SOSSAT-C88**

Medium height, tolerant to high moisture stress, early maturing (85-95 days); resistant to Downey mildew (<5% incidence); moderately resistant to stem borer, yield potential 1.5-2.5 t/ha.

3. **SUPER SOSSAT**

Early maturing, cultivated in all parts of North eastern states; tolerant drought tolerant and early maturing (80-90 days); moderately resistant to stem borer, head worms, smut, sorghum midge and qulea birds with yield potential of 2-3 t/ha;

- **4.5 Cultural Practices**

1. **Land Preparation**

Tillage Systems

Sorghum grain is small seeded, and so it should be grown on a well-prepared seedbed. The seedbed preparation should begin soon after the previous crop is harvested to allow enough time for weed control, decay of crop residue, storage of soil moisture and soil firming. Farmers have an option to prepare land using conventional or conservation tillage.

- For best results, the seedbed should be well prepared. The best seedbeds are freshly prepared ridges constructed 75 cm apart (**approximately one normal walking pace**) in shallow row openings.
- Under conventional tillage, farmers plough their fields using the animal drawn single mould board plough. On average, depth of ploughing can reach 30cm. Ploughing results in the soil structure being disturbed. These results in soil becoming loose and prone to soil erosion. Over time, a plough pan (compacted layer of soil) will develop, which makes it difficult for roots or water to penetrate.

Zero Tillage

- Zero-tillage involves sowing the crop directly into an untilled soil. Planting stations are made with hoes, or the seed is sown with a specially made machine planter (hand seeder, jab planter). The great benefits of zero-tillage are that it does not require draught power, while soil and water are conserved, and yields may be stabilized or enhanced.

Benefits of Minimum or conservation tillage

- ZT reduces soil erosion by as much as 60-90% depending on the conservation tillage method.
- Pieces of crop residue shield soil particles from rain and wind until new plants produce a protective canopy over the soil.
- Organic matter added as crop residue decomposes creates an open soil structure that lets water in more easily, reducing runoff.

Sowing date

- Planting should be done soon after the rains are well established and immediately after a good rainfall. Hence, the planting date will vary, depending on the location. Assuming the rains arrive on time, the planting dates written against some of the recommended varieties should be observed for good results.
- Early planting has also been shown to benefit from the early release of mineral nitrogen, and this usually occurs at the onset of the rains. Too early or too late planting will both produce a poor crop because of the inadequacy of moisture throughout the growing season, as well as attacks by pests and diseases, etc. Too early sowing of short-duration varieties may lead to grain maturing during the rains, thus resulting in moldy or black heads.
- However, farmers are advised to be guided by weather forecasts, given the climate change prevalence.

2. Sowing/ sowing methods

Before sowing

There are some activities necessary to carry out just before planting to prevent wastage of seeds and ensure establishment of good plant population of the cereals in question. These include:

- Germination test
- Seed treatment
- In some cases, raising seedlings in a nursery for transplanting as in sorghum.

Germination test: this will serve as a guide to how many seeds to be sown in a hole. The test gives an idea of how many 'normal' seedlings can be expected from a given number of seeds. Normal means the shoot and root parts are not deformed and look healthy not diseased. It can be done by sowing directly into a prepared seed bed or sowing on moist blotted paper, tissue paper etc.

Seed treatment: Seed dressing helps to ensure the prevention of decay before germination and smut disease after germination. Thus, it ensures even stands at the recommended population density, and a higher yield of cereal grains.

- i. Sorghum and millet can be sown manually directly on prepared seedbed either on ridges or on flat land using 10-13kg and 4-5kg per hectare seeds for sorghum and pearl millet respectively, depending upon the spacing adopted and nature of the seeds.
- ii. Sorghum can also be transplanted into the field when the rain fall regime has become fully established (preferable in the month of August).

3. Seed rate

The amount of seed required per unit area depends on:

- Optimum plant stand required per unit area,
- Plant type i.e. tall or short plants,
- Weight of the seed,
- Quality of seed in terms of germination.

Seed rate should be determined based on the optimum number of plants required in unit area (hectare or acre or sq ft or sq m) for good yield.

The recommended plant stand for pearl millet under normal condition is

53,333 [One plant per stand/hill at 75cm x 25cm];

53,333 [Two plants per stand/hill at 75cm x 50cm]; or

53 plants per m² [for 1&2 plant per stand/hill] or **17,828**.

Example

1 hectare = 10,000 m² (100 m x 100 m; approx. 43, 560² feet)

Recommended spacing = 75cm x 25cm

Since hectare is measured in meter square there is need to convert the spacing to meters too = 0.75m x 0.25m = 0.1875 m².

Therefore, 10,000m²/0.1875m² = 53,333plants/ha [one plant stand⁻¹]

10,000m²/0.375 (75cm x 50 cm) = 53,333 plants/ha [2 plant/stand stand⁻¹]

']

Since 1 acre = 3342.8 m² (60% of 1 ha or 36,000² feet)

3342.8 m²/0.1875 (75 cm x 25 cm) = 17,828 [One plant stand⁻¹]

3342.8m²/0.375 (75 cm x 50 cm) = 17, 828 [Two plants stand⁻¹]

Estimation of seed quantity per hectare:

Given: pearl millet seed with 75% germination, 1000 seed weight of 12g and the required plant population is 53, 333 (Two plant per stand at 75 cm x 25cm).

Step 1: How many seedlings required per ha at 5 seeds per hill? = 53,333 x 5 = 266,666

Therefore, total number of seeds to be used per hectare = **266,666**

Step 2: To determine the weight of 266, 666 seeds = 266,666 x 12,000g = 3.2kg

Step 3: To determine total seed needed at 75% germination = 3.2kg/0.75 = 4.3 kg

Step 4: To determine the seed weight needed to plant 1 ha. of land at 75% seedling survival = 4.3/0.75 = 5kg.

Hence, 6-8kg of millet seed is needed per hectare depending upon the variety.

Sorghum will require 10-13 kg per hectare depending upon the variety.

4. Spacing: The recommended spacing between ridges or rows is 75 cm, approximately one normal walking pace. The stands on the rows should be spaced at 25cm. About 5–7 seeds should be planted in each stand, at about 2.5 cm deep, covered with soil, and made firm. About 2 weeks after germination, seedlings should be thinned to 2 plants stand⁻¹.

5. Fertilizer application: Results of research have confirmed that sorghum (particularly the improved varieties) responds to nutrient application. Nitrogen is mostly lacking for optimum sorghum and pearl millet production. Nitrogen recommendations will vary with expected yield, soil texture and cropping sequence.

- The following are the nutrient recommendations for sorghum: 64 kg/ha of N and 32 kg/ha of phosphorus (P₂O₅). For very sandy soil (light soils), especially in the Sahel savannah that are known to be deficient in potassium, 30 kg K₂O/ha are recommended in addition to nitrogen and phosphorus. On heavy soils, approximately 80 kg of N and 40kg

P_2O_5 /hectare is recommended. A combination of compound fertilizer 15-15-15 and urea could be used to meet these requirements. Apply 6 g of NPK15:15:15 per hill (equivalent to 2 cover of coke bottle).

- However, **8–10 t/ha of farm yard manure (FYM)**, compost could also be applied where the chemical fertilizer is not available.

6. Weed management: Why and when should weed management be done?

Inefficient weed control is one of the main causes of low yields in sorghum.

- Some weeds serve as alternative hosts of pests and diseases pathogens. They reduce profits by lowering the quality, quantity, yields and value of sorghum/millet.
- Some weeds are parasitic and poisonous to sorghum/millet.
- It is important to control weeds throughout, but especially in the early stages of crop growth.
- This can be done through use of cultural/physical methods (hand pulling, hand picking, hoe weeding), mechanically by inter-cultivation and chemically by used of herbicide.
- As a general recommendation, first weeding at 4-5 leaf stage (3-4 weeks), just before top dressing. The second weeding is done after 6-7 weeks after sowing.

Types of Weeds

- Weeds can be classified as annual (complete their life cycle within one season) and perennial weeds (complete their life cycle in more than one year). *Rotteboelia cochinchinensis* and *Striga hermonthica* (witch weed) are examples of annual weeds, while *Imperata cylindrica* is an example of a perennial weed.
- Perennial weeds multiply through roots and stems. Mechanical weeding only cuts off the tops but the bottom continue consuming the nutrients and water meant for crops. These should be controlled early before the beginning of the season as later attempt of control them will damage the crop.
- The main biotic impediment to sorghum production in the Sahelian region and Sub-Saharan Africa at large is highly connected to *Striga* infestation where 100% yield loss can be obtained were susceptible cultivars of sorghum are been cultivated.
- There are several methods available for *Striga hermonthica* weed management which includes: cultural methods- intercropping,

transplanting, use of N-fertilizer, hoe weeding/hand pulling before it flowers, use of trap and catch crop, crop rotation and use of resistant varieties; chemical methods- use of both pre-emergent (imazapry, imazaquione) and post emergent (2,4-D, MCPA) herbicides. However, the best result is obtained using an integrated approach (IWM).

Similarly, when adopting chemical method of weed control, it is important to adhere to the following:

1. Application should be based on correct weed identification.
2. The choice of herbicide, however, depends on the predominant weed species and the availability of the herbicide.
3. Herbicides are available for pre-emergence or post emergence weed control depending on time of application. If herbicide is applied at planting, one weeding may be required at 5-6 weeks after planting depending on weed abundance.

7. Herbicide Application

Types of herbicides

- Pre-plant: incorporate into the soil before planting e.g granulated herbicides.
- Pre-emergence: applied after planting before emergence of both the crop and weeds, e.g. Lasso, Atrazine, cinosulforun, prosulforun, pendamethalin, imazapry, imazaquione etc.
- Post emergence: applied after emergence of both crop and weeds, e.g 2,4-D, Atrazine, Bentazone etc.
- It is essential to keep strictly to their recommended rates to avoid injury to the sorghum crop.

MODULE 5: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF MAIZE (ZEA MAYS L.)

• 5.1 Introduction

- Maize is grown worldwide and is a major traditional food cereal in the tropics. In Nigeria, maize production is increasingly becoming popular owing to its increased use as food for humans and livestock. In addition, maize has a relative yield advantage over traditional crops, such as millet and sorghum. Maize is plagued by a lot of production constraints.

- Most notable among these are *Striga*, streak virus infestation, and insect pests, as well as environmental problems such as drought and low soil fertility.
- Poor quality seeds are another important limiting factor in maize production. Often, farmers utilized seeds from the previous season's harvest or purchase seeds directly in the open market without regards to genetic purity.
- A key activity in raising crop yields and agricultural output is increasing the availability of quality seeds and adherence to the production practices designed for the crop.
- This manual considered both the open pollinated varieties (OPV) as well as the hybrid varieties.

• 5.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for maize production.

1. Site selection

- Soil for growing maize should be fertile and well drained, with sufficient and reliable rainfall evenly distributed over the growing season.
- Waterlogged conditions should be avoided.
- Recommended maize varieties for the area should be obtained from a reliable seed source and planted.
- Depending on the history of the site, seed treatment with fungicides or insecticides may be necessary before planting.

2. Land preparation

- Land should be prepared in the form of ridges, 75 to 90 cm apart, manually, by ox-drawn ridger, or by tractors. Animal traction is also commonly used on lighter soils. Large-scale commercial farmers use tractors to plough, harrow, and ridge their farms.

3. Seed selection

- Pure seeds should be obtained from the breeder or the research institution responsible for developing the variety, or from registered growers in your area.

Promising maize cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

1. SAMMAZ 23

Open pollinated / composite varieties early maturing (90 days) suitable for short rainy season areas, resistant to streak virus, tolerates low soil nitrogen.

2. **SAMMAZ 25**

Early maturing (90-100 days), highly tolerant to drought, resistant to streak virus, resistant to low soil nitrogen, adapted for drought prone areas of Sudano-sahelian savannah regions; high yielding (5-6 t/ha).

3. **SAMMAZ 31**

Early maturing (80-95 days) with yield potential of 4-5 t/ha.

4. **Sowing/ sowing methods**

Before sowing:

There are some activities necessary to carry out just before planting to prevent wastage of seeds and ensure establishment of good plant population of the legumes in question. These include:

- **Germination test:** this will serve as a guide to how many seeds to be sown in a hole. The test gives an idea of how many 'normal' seedlings can be expected from a given number of seeds. Normal means the shoot and root parts are not deformed and look healthy not diseased. It can be done by sowing directly into a prepared seed bed or sowing on moist blotted paper, tissue paper etc.
- **Seed treatment:** Seed dressing helps to ensure the prevention of decay before germination and smut disease after germination. Thus, it ensures even stands at the recommended population density, and a higher yield of both maize seed.

- **Seed rate**

The amount of seed required per unit area depends on:

- Optimum plant stand required per unit area (spacing)
- Plant type i.e. tall or short plants
- Weight of the seed
- Quality of seed in terms of germination.

Seed rate should be determined based on the optimum number of plants required in unit area (hectare or acre or sq ft or sq m) for good yield.

- 25 kg/ha for open pollinated varieties
- 15 kg/ha for hybrids

- 15 kg for popcorn.

5. Spacing/plant population

- Open-Pollinated/Popcorn varieties: Hand planted, 90 cm x 40 cm, 2 plants/stand to give 55,555 plants/ha.
- Hybrids: Hand planted, 90 cm x 40 cm, 2 plants/stand to give 55,555 plants/ha.
- Mechanical Planting: (Any Variety)
75 cm x 25 cm, 1 plant/stand to give 53,333 plants/ha or
75cm x 50 cm, 2 plant/stand to give 53,333 plants/ha of
90 cm x 20 cm, 1 plant/stand giving 55,555 plants/ha.

There should be no thinning or supplying except in very bad cases.

6. Fertilizer rate and time of application

Open-pollinated varieties

- In the savanna zone, apply 400 kg (8 bags) of 25:10:10, 100 kg (2 bags) of Single Super-phosphate and 3 to 5 kg of Zinc Sulphate per/ha at planting as band or broadcast application, to give 100kg N, 58 kg P₂O₅; 40 kg K₂O, 14 kg S and 1-2 kg Zn per/ha.
- Alternatively apply 500 kg (10 bags) of 20-10-10-2S-1Zn per/ha at planting.

Hybrids

- For every high yields, apply 600 kg (12 bags) of 25:10:10 per hectare in two splits at planting (200 kg) and 5 to 6 weeks after planting (400 kg), to give 150 kg N, 60 kg P₂O₅ and 60 kg K₂O per hectare.
- In the savanna zone, add 200 kg (4 bags) of Single Super-phosphate and 5kg of Zinc Sulphate to give a total of 150 kg N, 78 kg P₂O₅, 60 kg K₂O, 14 kg S and 2kg Zn.
- Alternatively, apply 500 kg (10 bags) of 20:10:10-2S-1Zn/ha at planting and a second dose of 100 kg (2 bags) of Urea per hectare. (5-6 WAS).

7. Weed Control:

- ✓ It is important to keep the field for crop production free of weeds from planting to harvesting. All available and effective weed control methods should be used according to growing or field conditions.
- ✓ Mechanical weeding, physical (hand pulling; hoe-weeding first at 3-4 WAS second at 7-8 WAS),

- ✓ Chemically through use of pre-emergence (Atrazine at 3kg/ha and Metolachlor at 3-4kg/ha) and post-emergence (2,4-D and Bentazone @ 1-2kg/ha) herbicides can also be adopted to keep the fields weed-free.

8. Pest and diseases management

All the available control methods should be used to reduce pest and disease incidence. Treatment of seeds with chemicals is recommended for maize against army worm

9. Harvesting

Harvest of maize should be done as soon as it is ripe for the purpose desired, undue delay in harvesting increases damage due to diseases and pests.

MODULE 6: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF RICE (ORYZA SATIVA L.)

• 6.1 Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important crops that provide food for about half of the world population, particularly in Asia, Africa and Latin America where the demand for rice is a top priority. In Nigeria, rice constitutes a major part of the diet across each region of the country. Rice is cultivated on 1.8 million hectare with average grain yield of 3.0 t/ha for lowland and 1.5 t/ha for upland. Its cultivation cut across major agro-ecological zones, which ranges from the mangrove ecology of Niger Delta in the coastal areas to the dry zones of the Sahel in the north. Rice has consistently increased in demand and has assumed strategic importance in Nigeria's food security agenda. The increase in demand for rice in Nigeria is attributed to high population growth rate, rapid urbanization and rising incomes. Increase in national rice demand has triggered an increase in domestic production in the last decade. However, demand still exceeds production and large quantities of rice are imported to meet demand at a huge cost in foreign currency. Productivity in rice production must be increased to attain rice self-sufficiency and future demands resulting from population growth.

• 6.2 Good Agronomic practices (GAPs) of rice production

I. Ecological requirements

Rice is growing under varying conditions that is difficult to define the climate that is more suitable for its development. This is mainly due to the great diversity of its cultivars. Rice required a high growing temperature of about 30-32°C, the minimum temperature for germination is 18°C for tropical varieties and 10-12°C for subtropical. Rice does not tolerate frost at any stage of growth, long period of sunshine is essential for high yield, however, modern cultivars are mostly day neutral or have only a slight reaction to the photoperiod. The optimum rainfall requirement for upland or dry land rice is 250-1500mm evenly distributed during the growing period. Rice requires a heavy soil that holds water with a pH range of 4.5-8.

2. Site/Land Selection:

During rice production, certain guidelines should be followed during land selection: There are two major physical criteria to be considered which are as follows;

- i. **Source of water:** water is vital for plant growth, and can be used to control weed especially in upland rice. Therefore, farmers should avoid highly drought prone areas, as well as very deep ditches (to get rid of too much water). Farmers should choose gentle slopping land for easy drainage, and a fairly flat land for ease of water distribution.
- ii. **Soil type:** Rice can be grown on different types of soil- from sandy loam to heavy clay. However, sandy soils should be avoided. Select a naturally fertile land, with moderate organic matter. Avoid highly iron-toxic soils if lowland and avoid iron deficient and acid soils if upland.

3. Variety Selection

While selecting the rice variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a particular area. Healthy and uniform sized seeds from a reliable source should be selected. Seeds of the rice variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety should be suitable for the soil condition in the selected field.

Improved proven rice varieties that can adaptable to the Sudano-sahelian region

1. FARO-40,
2. FARO-44
3. FARO-45,
4. FARO-46,
5. FARO-54
6. FARO-55
7. FARO-56

8. FARO-58

9. FARO-59

They are all good water use efficiency, pest/disease resistant, early maturing (90-110 days) varieties, tolerant to drought, high yielding and with good cooking qualities.

4. Land Preparation

The field should be ploughed thoroughly without any lumps. Green manure crops can be raised in the field in order to enhance the nutrient content of the soil if soil is known to be deficient in fertilizer. Organic manures like farm yard manure, compost and vermin-compost can be used to enhance the soil fertility. Field should be irrigated well within three days of sowing to avoid hardness of the soil.

- a. **For direct seeded rice:** Plough and harrow twice a week or two, until when the rains are stable. Remove stubbles and burry vegetation very well. Level the field properly before seeding.
- b. **For transplanted rice:** Plough the field with early rains. Puddle when there is sufficient water in the field and raise nursery at the same time now remove stubbles that did not rot and level properly for transplanting when the seedlings are less or 21 days old. If necessary create bunds across gradients dividing the field into section.

Advantages of proper land preparation

- Levelling = improved water coverage in lowland and reduced erosion in upland
- Bounding increases water distribution and retention
- Increased reliability of direct seeding (reduces labour by 30 person per days)
- Reduces weeds up to 40%
- Eliminate volunteer crop, first stage of seed mixture

5. Seed preparation (cleaning before sowing):

Salt solution can be used to remove the chaffy seeds from good seeds through the following steps;

- Take some water in a vessel and drop an egg in it.
- Keep adding salt to it slowly until the egg reaches the surface of the water.
- When the seeds are dropped in this water, the good quality seeds will sink into the water.
- Remove the unviable seeds that float on the surface of the water.

- Wash the selected seeds in good water for 2-3 times to remove the salt deposits.
- If this is not done, the germination capacity of the seeds will be affected.
- By this method, the unviable seeds can be removed completely.
- This method should be followed when there is more of chaff.

6. Sowing:

Planting the crop on time will help produce a fast-growing, uniform crop that will have higher yields and will be better able to compete with weeds and pests. The best time to plant depends on the locality, variety, water availability, and the best harvest time. Rice can either be transplanted from a nursery or direct-seeded in the field. Transplanted crops will normally take less time in the production field but 10-15 days longer for the total crop duration. In both cases, a well prepared seedbed is needed. There are two ways of establishing rice crop viz; direct seeding and nursery.

- I. **Direct seeding:** Rice seeds are directly sown in the field when there is assurance of seed viability (80-95%). There are two types of direct seeding depending on the ecology and moisture content of the soil (i.e. wet and dry direct seeding).
 - **Wet direct seeding:** in this method, farmers are advised to follow the following steps while sowing the crop;
 - ✓ Pre-germination of seed- soak the seed for 24 hours and then drain for 24 hours in the shade before broadcasting evenly over the water-covered soil surface.
 - ✓ Broadcast pre-germinated seed at 100 kg ha^{-1}
 - ✓ Allow surface water to drain or percolate naturally into soil
 - ✓ Keep soil surface moist by adding water
 - ✓ Add permanent water at 10-15 days after establishment or at 2-3leaf stage.
 - ✓ Apply basal fertilizer after permanent water is added.
 - **Dry direct seeding:** the following steps should be adopted in dry direct seeding;
 - ✓ Hand broadcast dry seed at 100 kg ha^{-1} or machine drill seed at 80 kg ha^{-1} and 20mm depth
 - ✓ Apply basal fertilizer through the seed drill
 - ✓ Cover broadcast seed and fertilizer with a light harrowing
 - ✓ Flash flood until 15 days after emergence or 2-leaf stage then adds permanent water.

II. Nursery bed operations for transplanted rice: For transplanting, seedlings are raised in either a dry or wet nursery. In dry nursery the land is well-cultivated and fertilized with well-rotted farmyard manure. Nursery beds are made 1-1.5m wide and of appropriate length. The beds are slightly raised. For planting one hectare of field, seedlings are raised in nurseries of about 350-500m² in area. Adequate fertilizer should be applied before sowing. Pre-soaked seeds are broadcast or drilled (10cm apart) in the prepared nurseries at the rate of 1-2kg per 20-35m². The seed is covered with 2-3cm soil.

A wet nursery is the more common method. The land is flooded and puddled and fertilized (farmyard manure). Nursery beds are made as for dry nursery. They are also slightly raised. Pre-soaked, sometimes pre-germinated seeds are broadcast on mud at the rate of 25 kg per 350-500m² of nursery beds and water is allowed to stand continuously on the beds after the seedlings are about 15 cm high. Seedlings grow quickly and are ready for transplanting in 25-30 days, when they are 15-30 cm tall and have developed 5-7 leaves (depending on the variety). Sometimes the seeds are germinated on strips of polythene or other materials (impermeable layer such as banana leaves, plastic sheet) which keep the root system on the surface. Such seedlings are easier to raise and are ready for transplanting in 10-14 days. This system is referred to as the Dapog method. A 20-25m² seed bed is enough for 1 hectare. For either of the systems it is important to sow thinly as this will encourage sturdy and healthy growth of the seedlings and savings in seeds. The sown seeds are to be covered with grass mulch and removed on the 7th day after the seedlings must have emerged.

III. Transplanting:

It is advisable to site nursery beds near the cultivation area as the weight of the seedlings is quite cumbersome. Transplanting is done mostly by hand but it can also be done mechanically. Usually 2-3 seedlings are transplanted at each position at 20-25cm x 20-25cm inter and intra row spacing, respectively. Older seedlings grow more slowly than younger ones and they may result in prolonged maturity, reduced tillering capacity with consequent reduction in yield. A day or two before transplanting, the soil is heavily watered to make uprooting of the seedlings easy. Seedlings should be pulled out carefully, the root washed, tied into bundles before transplanting to the field. About 3 days before transplanting a rotavator is used to break the soil into very fine particles. The soil should be drained to improve aeration.

7. Plant population

Establishing the correct number of plants per unit area is essential in terms of reducing competition for the available growth resources such as water, nutrient, space and sunlight. However, the seed rate and plant population per unit area depends on certain factors: rice ecosystem, planting method adopted, planting depth, seed quality as well as the variety.

Plant population of 300-400 panicles per m² can be maintained during rainy season and can be increased to 500-600 panicles per m² during dry season.

Low plant population may lead to:

- Increased number of tillers, which also influences number of panicles during harvest
- Increases the population of weeds. And
- Decreases the yield potential of the variety

High plant population on the other hand may decrease yield and quality of paddy through:

- Competition for the available growth resources
- Mutual shading
- Reduction in grain size

Hence, the use of adequate seed rate will reduce the cost of production and reduces competition for growth resources.

How to determine seed rate

What is the area to be cultivated? = 1ha (100 m × 100 m = 10,000 m²)

How many hills/ha at 20cm × 20cm spacing? $10,000\text{m}^2 / (0.2\text{m} \times 0.2\text{m}) = 250,000$

How many seedlings per hectare at 4 seeds per hill? $250,000 \times 4 = 1,000,000$

Therefore, total number of seed per hectare = 1,000,000 seeds

Weight of 1,000,000 seeds = 20-30 g; Av = 25g

Weight of 1,000,000 seeds = $1,000,000 \times 25,000 \text{ g} = 25\text{kg}$

% germination for rice = 50-90%; Av= 70%

Seed needed at 70% germination = $25\text{kg} / 0.7 = 36\text{kg}$

% seedling that survive = 50-90, Av=70%

Final seed weight needed to plant one hectare of land = $36\text{kg} / 0.7 = 50\text{kg}$

8. Fertilizer application:

Most soils provide only limited amount of nutrients to the crop, therefore fertilizers need to be applied to increase grain yield. In some cases, fertilizers are also added to improve the soil's physical condition. The amount and type of fertilizer applied are determined on the assumption that 1ton of grain will remove 15 kg nitrogen (N), 2–3 kg phosphorus (P), and 15–20 kg potassium (K). These base rates need to be modified according to the soil type, the season, the crop condition, prevailing weather conditions, and efficiency of

application. In Nigeria, the recommended fertilizer rate for rice is 70-120kgN, 30-40kg P₂O₅ and 30-40 kg K₂O per hectare depending on the fertility status of the soil and the ecology. For efficient fertilizer use:

- ✓ Use organic fertilizer (manure, compost, straw, husk, plant leaves) whenever possible, especially in nurseries.
- ✓ Apply fertilizer according to soil type and expected yield. As a guide, a 2 t/ha yield on clay loam soil will require 20 kg N and 5 kg P. Sandy soils may require another 10-15 kg K. Double these recommendations for a 3 t/ha expected yield.
- ✓ Apply all P, K, and 10% N evenly and incorporate just before seeding or transplanting.
- ✓ For direct seeded broadcast crops, it is okay to apply 10-14 days after establishment when there is water in the field.
- ✓ Apply remaining N (Urea) in 2 equal splits at 30 days and 50–60 days (panicle initiation) after emergence.
- ✓ In established crops, apply chemical fertilizer only in standing water and evenly across the whole field.
- ✓ Do not apply high rates of fertilizer for traditional varieties as they may have limited response and cause lodging.
- ✓ Do not use chemical fertilizer if you need more than 5 kg paddy to pay for 1 kg of fertilizer.
- ✓ Inorganic fertilizers must be stored in a dry and cool place that is out of children's reach.

Examples of fertilizers are: NPK 15:15:15 (15% N; 15% P₂O₅; 15% K₂O),
NPK 20:10:10 (20% N; 10% P₂O₅; 10% K₂O),
NPK 30:10:10 (30% N; 10% P₂O₅; 10% K₂O)

Fertilizer recommendation for Sahelian region

Rain-fed: 60-80kg N; 30-60kg P₂O₅ and 30 kg K₂O

Irrigation: 100-120kg N, 60kg P₂O₅, 60kg K₂O

Time of fertilizer application

Nitrogenous fertilizer should be applied in greater quantity and in splits. The lighter the soil, the greater the number of splits. It is usually applied in two splits doses- 40% N at sowing, 30% top dress at 4 WAS or at tillering and last split at 7 WAS during flowering (panicle initiation stage). However, full dosage of P and K are to be applied during land preparation or at 2 WAS.

9. Water Management:

Water availability largely determines the potential crop yield. For a crop to continue to grow, the water supply needs to be similar or a little above

evaporation. In an efficient system, each 1 kg of grain produced will require a minimum of 2,000 liters or 2 m³ of water. Good water control increases crop yields and grain quality as well as improving the efficiency of other inputs such as fertilizer, herbicide, and pesticides. To maximize water-use efficiency:

- ✓ Maintain the bunds;
- ✓ Level the fields;
- ✓ Puddle the fields where possible;
- ✓ Use direct-seeding techniques;
- ✓ Use short-duration crops; and
- ✓ Harvest on time.

Water quality

Good-quality water is necessary to maximize crop growth. The rice plant is susceptible to salinity especially at the seedling stage and during the panicle development stage from panicle initiation to booting. Symptoms of salt toxicity include “firing” of leaves and reduced dry matter production. The effects of high salinity during panicle development are less obvious as there is little leaf effect, but florets and grain numbers per panicle are reduced greatly reducing yield.

10. Weed Management in Rice

Weeds compete directly with the rice plants and reduce rice yield. Each 1 kg dry matter of weeds is equivalent to 1 kg grain loss. Weeds cause most yield loss within the first 20–50 days after crop establishment. Weeding after panicle initiation may also be important to prevent weeds shedding seeds in future crops. Two hoe or hand weeding at 2-3 weeks and 5-6 WAS or WAT will be adequate. Herbicide can also be used to control weed in rice, some common Herbicides include: Butachlor at 1.5kg a.i/ha PE, Butachlor + Propanil at (1.5 + 3.0) kg a.i/ha POE at 15 DAP, Propanil + Oxadiazon at 2.5 kg a.i/ha POE at 15 DAP, Propanil + Bentazon at 3.0 kg a.i/ha POE at 15 DAS.

For Effective weed management in rice, the following steps should be practice:

- ✓ Ploughing and harrowing in fallow should be undertaken at least 10–14 days apart or after rain.
- ✓ Good land levelling reduces weed growth because most weeds have trouble germinating under water.
- ✓ Select varieties which have early vigour.
- ✓ Use clean rice seed which is free of weed seeds.
- ✓ Apply permanent water early- weeds cannot germinate under water.
- ✓ First weeding begins within 2–3 weeks after establishment and the second in another 2–3 weeks. Weed before fertilizer application.

- ✓ Using herbicides. Identify the weed correctly and use the appropriate herbicide as recommended on the label.
- ✓ Spray when the weeds are tender.
- ✓ Apply pre-emergence herbicides after sowing prior to establishment.
- ✓ Apply post-emergence herbicides after emergence being careful of crop damage.
- ✓ Herbicides are poisonous; if they are not used properly they can cause health and environment problems. Label them clearly and keep them out of children's reach.
- ✓ Always use protective clothing when spraying.
- ✓ Do not wear raincoats when spraying as this increases sweating.

Also, good weed management helps reduce weed competition, which not only increases yields but also improves grain quality by reducing dockage levels and reducing moisture differentials between weed seeds and grain.

Good management practices for weed control in rice

1. Ensure good land preparation
2. Ensure good water management
3. Cultural/ (crop rotation, reduced spacing, good fertilization)
4. physical methods (hand pulling, hoe-weeding,)
5. Chemical methods- this can be achieved by the use of herbicide.
6. Integrated weed management (IWM)-

There is no single approach that can give satisfactory degree of weed control. Hence, the best approach is to combine two-three of the above mention methods in a compatible manner. Example, good land preparation + pre-emergence herbicide application + reduced spacing + hand pulling/hoe weeding.

MODULE 7: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF COWPEA (*VIGNA UNGUICULATA* L. WALP.) AND GROUNDNUT (*ARACHIS HYPOGAEA* L.)

• 7.1 Introduction

The success of any good crop production after site selection is the availability of good quality seeds of high yielding varieties, adapted to the growing area, and preferred by the farmers. The quality of seeds alone is known to account for an increase in productivity of at least 10–15%. To achieve this high quality,

all the factors in production that will affect viability and genetic purity should be taken into account. The production techniques should be mastered and the environmental conditions (soil fertility and climate) known.

Cowpea and groundnut are both self-pollinated crops having the same phenology. Therefore, have similar production activities.

- **7.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for cowpea and groundnut production**

1. Field selection: The choice of field is an important component of good crop production.

- Cowpea is less demanding than groundnut and can be grown in soils of diverse types, ranging from predominantly clay to predominantly sand, and from acidic to basic.
- For both cowpea and groundnut, the best soil is a well-drained, sandy loam to clay loam soil with pH 6 and 7.
- To manage disease, insects, and weeds, the history and crop rotation of the field should be known.

2. Land preparation: Land should be prepared as early in the season as possible.

- The land should be cleared of old crop residues that could be burned.
- For cowpea that is planted later in the season, herbicide can be used before planting.
- Generally, deep ploughing and harrowing once or twice will provide good root growth that enables plants to get moisture from the soil.
- The recommendation for groundnut production in drier areas is a flat seedbed running across the slope.

3. Seed selection: It is important to use genetically pure seeds of a given variety from a reliable source (registered seeds).

- Pure seeds should be obtained from the breeder or the research institution responsible for developing the variety, or from registered growers in your area.
- Good quality seeds should meet the following characteristics:
 - ✓ Genetic purity and uniformity conform to the standards of the particular cultivar.
 - ✓ Seeds are disease-free, viable, and free from admixtures of seeds of other crops and weeds, and inert material.
 - ✓ Seeds are uniform in size, shape, and color.

Promising cowpea cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

1. IT97K-499-35

Recommended for all North eastern states of Nigeria, early maturing (50-60 days) required a spacing 75 cm between rows and 30 cm between plants, semi-erect and with yield potential of 1-1.6 t/ha. Palatable with cooking time of 10-45 minutes, resistant to many pest and diseases including striga gesnoroides, with high fodder yield.

2. IT90KD-277-2

Adapted to all North eastern states of the region, potential yield of 1.2-1.6 t/ha with good palatability, medium maturity period 90-100 days, it is a semi-upright in growth habit, has some level of resistance to striga, aphids, thrips, bruchids, viruses and several diseases;

3. IT99K-573-1-1

Grows in all states of North East, Medium maturing (90-100 days), potential yield 1.5-2 t/ha, large white seeds, semi upright, good palatability, gives good fodder and can resist insects/pests and striga infestation.

Promising groundnut cultivars suitable for North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

i. SAMNUT-24

- Early-maturing (80-90days), good haulm yield (2.5-3t/ha), vigorous plant growth, good yield (2-2.5t/ha) and high oil content (53%).

ii. SAMNUT-25

- Early-maturing (80-90 days), good yield potential (2.5-3t/ha), highly resistant to rosette and moderately resistant to ELS and LLS disease, with high oil content (51.5%).

iii. SAMNUT-26

- Early-maturing (80-90 days), highly resistant to rosette and moderately resistant to ELS and LLS disease, good yield potential (2-2.5t/ha) and good oil content (50.9%).

iv. SAMNUT 14 (Ex -Dakar)

- Suitable for all states of the region; similar to SAMNUT 23 in pod shape, size and pod distribution, seed coat color, and seed size; early maturing 90-100 days, erect growth habit, susceptible to rosette and leaf spot diseases, drought tolerant variety with oil content of 50-52% and yield 2-2.8 t/ha.

4. Sowing/ sowing methods

Before sowing:

There are some activities necessary to carry out just before planting to prevent wastage of seeds and ensure establishment of good plant population of the legumes in question. These include:

- **Germination test:** this will serve as a guide to how many seeds to be sown in a hole. The test gives an idea of how many 'normal' seedlings can be expected from a given number of seeds. Normal means the shoot and root parts are not deformed and look healthy not diseased. It can be sown directly into a prepared seed bed or on a moist blotted paper, tissue paper etc.
- **Seed treatment:** Seed dressing helps to ensure the prevention of decay before germination and smut disease after germination. Thus, it ensures even stands at the recommended population density, and a higher yield of both cowpea and groundnut seed.

5. Seed rate

The amount of seed required per unit area depends on:

- Optimum plant stand required per unit area (spacing)
- Plant type i.e. erect or spreading type
- Weight of the seed
- Quality of seed in terms of germination.

Seed rate should be determined based on the optimum number of plants required in unit area (hectare or acre or sq ft or sq m) for good yield.

6. Method of sowing and spacing:

Both cowpea and groundnut can be grown in flat beds or on ridges, depending on the field conditions. Three (3) seeds/hill should be sown by dibbling at the depth of 3-5cm and later thinned to 2 plants/stand at 2 weeks after sowing (WAS).

- For sole cowpea, a spacing of 75 cm between the rows and 20 cm between plants within the rows is used for the medium maturing varieties;
- Spacing of 50 cm between the rows and 20 cm between the plants within the row is used for early maturing varieties.
- Where cowpea is to be intercropped or relayed with other crops, such as maize, sorghum, millet etc, the spacing should be 75 cm × 50 cm.
- Also the cowpea should be sown at about 4–6 weeks after planting the first crop, maize, sorghum, or millet.
- For strip intercropping, adopt 2 rows of cereal to 4 rows of cowpea to improve the productivity of erect and shade-sensitive cowpea varieties. The cereal and cowpea should be planted at the recommended spacing and depth.

- The recommended spacing for sole groundnut is 75 cm x 20 cm.

Seed rate

A. For cowpea

- Spreading type 10-15kg/ha
- Erect 25-30kg/ha

B. For groundnut

- Depending upon the varieties 40-55kg/ha

7. Planting date:

- For groundnut, planting should be done as soon as possible after the onset of the rains. Early planting is recommended to avoid rosette attack.
- For cowpea, planting is done when there is sufficient moisture in the soil to allow germination and when there will be enough time for the varieties to mature after the end of the rainy period.
- In general, the ideal time for planting medium maturing varieties of cowpea is about 60-75 days before the rains are expected to end and for 45-50 days for extra-early varieties..

8. Fertilization:

- For good cowpea or groundnut production, phosphorus and potash fertilization are required, notably in the poor soils of the Sudan savanna and Sahelian regions of West Africa.
- Fertilizer applied at the rate of 200 kg/ha of 0.5-15 or a combination of 30–40 kg/ha P_2O_5 and 25–30 kg/ha K_2O is sufficient to ensure good growth of the cowpea crop.
- The fertilizers should be incorporated in the soil before planting. Top dressing is not advised.
- For groundnut, the application of 54 kg/ha P_2O_5 and 25 kg/ha K_2O is required to get good crop performance. Fertilizer can be applied before or immediately after planting.
- If available, organic manure at the rate of 3 t/ha should be applied.

9. Weed control:

- ✓ It is important to keep the field for crop production free of weeds from planting to harvesting. All available and effective weed control methods should be used according to growing or field conditions.

- ✓ Mechanical weeding, physical (hand pulling; hoe-weeding at 3 and 6 WAS), pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicides can be adopted to keep the fields weed-free.

10. Pest and diseases control:

All the available control methods should be used to reduce pest and disease incidence. Treatment of seeds with chemicals is recommended for both groundnut and cowpea.

11. Harvesting

Harvesting should be timely when most pods are dry as in cowpea.

- For cowpea, multiple picking may be necessary depending on the type of variety planted
- For groundnut, it should be done when pods have turned brown to early dark in colour .

MODULE 8: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES FOR SESAME

• 8.1 Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) or benniseed is one of the highly sought cash crop in Nigeria. It's second to cocoa in terms of export value. Despite the increasing demand and price of sesame in the world market, its productivity is declining due to some factors ranging from poor agronomic practices to poor harvest and post-harvest handling of the commodity. This text therefore, will try address this issues considering the demand of the commodity for both domestic and industrial uses (export) which in turn boost the farmers' income and improve his livelihood options.

• 8.2 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for sesame (Benniseed) production

I. Field selection: The choice of field is an important component of good crop production.

- Sesame is adaptable to many types of soil but it does best on well-drained soil with a pH of 5.5-6.7,
- The crop is usually produced on upland plains while depressions and valleys areas with poorer drained soils are generally unsuitable,
- It does reasonably well on poor soils; sandy loams are preferred. Once established, it can tolerate short periods of drought, but is very intolerant of water logging. It has poor ability to compete with weeds in the early stages,
- Sesame can be grown in rotation following sorghum, maize, groundnuts, cotton, millet, or cowpea,
- It can also be grown as a mixed crop with sorghum, millet, and other cereals.

2. Land preparation: Land should be prepared as early in the season as possible.

- The land should be cleared of old crop residues that could be burned.
- Plough and harrow the soil to a depth which will physically support the plant and allow the use of sufficient moisture and nutrients; sufficient enough to control weeds; and must leave the soil surface level.
- Ploughing can be done using the hoe, animal drawn plough and tractor drawn plough.
- Ploughing should be carried out after the first set of rains to ensure that the land is soft enough for penetration by implements and harrow after a week or two before sowing the seeds.
- A level field improves water use efficiency, helps control in crop weeds and allows the rapid removal of excess water.

3. Seed selection/sources of seed: It is important to use genetically pure seeds of a given variety from a reliable source (registered seeds).

- Pure seeds should be obtained from the breeder or the research institution responsible for developing the variety, or from registered growers in your area.
- There are many varieties of sesame available from which farmers can select.
- The major varieties found in Nigeria with their qualities are itemized below.
- However, they can either be for industrial uses such bakery, biscuits and other confectionaries or just for oil extraction which probably distinguished based on the seed colouration.

Promising sesame cultivars that can adapt to north eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

- i. NCRIBEN-01M (530-6-10)**
Yield potential of 1000kg/ha, oil content of 45%, medium maturing (102-115 days), white seed coloration
- ii. NCRIBEN-02M**
Yield potential of 750 kg/ha, oil content 45%, medium maturing (102-115 days), light brown in color.
- iii. E8**
Yield potential of 1000 kg/ha, oil content 50%, early maturing (90 days) with light brown color.
- iv. YANDEV 55**
Yield potential of 600 kg/ha, oil content 45%, medium maturing (125 days) with light brown color.

4. Sowing/ sowing methods

Before sowing:

There are some activities necessary to carry out just before planting to prevent wastage of seeds and ensure establishment of good plant population of the legumes in question. These include:

- i. Germination test:** this will serve as a guide to how many seeds to be sown in a hole. The test gives an idea of how many 'normal' seedlings can be expected from a given number of seeds. Normal means the shoot and root parts are not deformed and look healthy not diseased. It can sow directly into a prepared seed bed or on moist blotted paper, tissue paper etc.
- ii. Seed treatment:** Seed dressing helps to ensure the prevention of decay before germination and smut disease after germination. Thus, it ensures even stands at the recommended population density, and a higher yield of both cowpea and groundnut seed.

5. Seed rate

The quantity of seed required per unit area depends on:

- Optimum plant stand required per unit area (spacing)
- Plant type i.e. erect or spreading type
- Weight of the seed
- Quality of seed in terms of germination.
- Method of sowing to be used.

Seed rate should be determined based on the optimum number of plants required in unit area (hectare or acre or sq ft or sq m) for good yield.

- ✓ **3-5 kg/ha** in furrow sowing, and
- ✓ **8kg/ha** in broadcasting

6. Method of sowing and spacing:

- ✓ Three (3) sowing methods are usually practiced by sesame farmers across the producing areas which are:
 - Broadcasting (no spacing),
 - Drilling (60 inter row spacing only)
 - Dibbling (75cm x 15 cm, 60cm x 10cm)

7. Planting date:

- As soon as the rain becomes fully established (Mid June-early July)

8. Fertilization:

- Sesame performs well under application of 60kg N, 30kg P₂O₅ and 30kg K₂O, which can be supplied using NPK 15:15:15 at planting or at 2 weeks after sowing (WAS) while the remaining 30% of N will be top dressed at 5-6 WAS using Urea.

9. Weed control:

- ✓ It is important to keep the field for crop production free of weeds from planting to harvesting. All available and effective weed control methods should be used according to growing or field conditions.
- ✓ Mechanical weeding, physical (hand pulling; hoe-weeding) application of pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicides can be adopted to keep the fields weed-free.

10. Pest and diseases control:

All the available control methods should be used to reduce incidence of pest and disease.

MODULE 9: BASIC PRODUCTION PRACTICES OF SELECTED FRUIT AND VEGETABLES

- **9.1 Introduction**

OBJECTIVES: To improve the farmers production practices through good agronomic practices.

- **9.2 Onion (*Allium cepa* L.)**

Onion belongs to the family *Alliaceae*, it is a naturally packed vegetables consisting of fleshy connective scales which are enclosed in paper like wrapping leaves.

It is one of the most commonly consumed vegetable in Nigeria. More than 2 million tonnes of onions are produced annually in Nigeria, and 98% of the production is from the northern parts of the country.

9.2.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for onion production

1. Site selection

- Needs a fertile and well drained sandy-loamy soil with a pH of 5-7.
- The temperature requirement of the crop is between 15-25°C.
- Low atmospheric humidity and clear bright days are also necessary to ensure insect activities for pollination.
- Organic matter can be added prior to planting to improve the soil properties.
- The land can be prepared by Ploughing 3-5 times to ensure fine soil tilt and organic material incorporated during the final plough.

2. Variety Selection

While selecting the onion variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a particular area. Seeds of the onion variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety

Promising onion cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

i. Gindin Tasa (Kano Red)

Dark brown to pink large bulbs. Light bolt and post-harvest rot. Good for dry and wet season, matures in 120-130 days.

ii. Wuyan Bijimi

Light to red or brown, medium sized bulbs of oval shape; high bolting tendency, matures in 110- 120 days. Good for dry season but could be grown under rain fed.

iii. Ex-Gayanawa (Samon - I)

Medium to large, brown ovate (flattened from top with round base) bulbs. Good storage, low bolting tendency, matures in 110-120 days and Suitable for dry season.

iv. Yar Damasak/Geidam

3. Nursery preparation

- For good germination in the nursery, a well-tilled seedbed with a fine loose surface is necessary. The seedbed with moist poultry droppings and compost should be worked into the seedbed before sowing.
- After preparing the seedbed, mark it out in rows, which should be about 10-15cm apart in a 120cm wide seedbed. Then a groove of about 12m depth is made along each row.
- The seeds can now be sown in either of the two ways. The first method is to mix the seeds with an equal amount of fine sand and then spread the mixture evenly in the furrow. The second method is to first spread the sand into the furrow and the seeds are then spread evenly over the sand in the furrow.
- After sowing the seeds, the furrow is slightly covered with soil. The seedbed should be cover with light mulch and water once or twice a week. After germination, the mulch is removed. Hand weeding and watering should continue until the seedlings are 6-8 weeks old when they should be ready for transplanting.

4. Planting/Transplanting

- Planting of onions can be done by seeds or setts.
- Dry season onions cultivation commenced in November to December and it takes 3-4 months to reach maturity depending on the variety.
- Rain fed onions is planted between April to August.
- Seeds should be raised in the nursery and when it reaches 40-45 days can be transplanted in to the field
- Planting is done on ridges; and furrows should be created to ensure ease when carrying out post planting operations.
- Spacing of 10 cm x 10 cm can be adopted for transplanting.
- When transplanting, spread the roots carefully in the natural position before pressing the soil around the plant.

5. Irrigation

- Generally, irrigation should be done weekly for at least 2 months after planting or 3 weeks before the plant attains full maturity.
- Irrigation is very essential during the bulb forming stage, however if the watering doesn't stop at the right time, it may delay maturation.
- Excessive irrigation or watering should be avoided because it may affect the growth of the crop.
- Type of irrigation system to be adopted is of critical importance, as irrigation system like overhead can promote fungal growth. Ideally, the best irrigation system for onion farming is drip irrigation.

9.2.2 Post planting

These include activities such as:

- i. **Weed control:** weeds have the capacity to decrease onions yield of onions, hence it is important to take care of them.
 - ✓ Good land preparation is the first step to weed management in all cropping system.
 - ✓ Hoe weeding 2-3 times (3,6 & 9 WAS) is recommended for onions throughout the growing season.
 - ✓ Application of post- emergence herbicide is important in reducing the menace of weeds in onions e.g
 - ✓ Mulching with organic materials such as grasses, rice straw and husk can also reduce the density of weed species.
- ii. **Pest and diseases control**
- iii. **Fertilization:** Onion requires good fertilizer application. Generally, any fertilizer application should be based on soil test. The amount of nutrient requires varies from location to location depending on the inherent soil fertility. For general purposes however, a fertilizer rate of 65kg N/ha, 40kg P₂O₅/ha and 45kg K₂O/ha is recommended, and can be applied four weeks after transplanting.
- iv. **Harvesting**
 - It takes the bulb onions about 3-4 months to reach maturity. The ideal time for harvest is the dry season.
 - They can be harvested when 50% of the neck falls.

- Another indicator is the formation of a shiny membranous cover around the bulbs or when the foliage of the plant begins to wither.
- Harvesting is done by pulling the bulbs of onion plants then cutting off the leaves.

• 9.3 TOMATOES

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is a fleshy vegetable fruit that can be grown as a garden fruit or in large commercial quantities. Tomato is a constant ingredient for the preparation of multiple meals in Nigeria. Tomato can be cultivated in the green houses and also in the field.

9.3.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for tomato production

1. Site selection

- Needs a fertile and well drained sandy-loamy soil with a pH of 5-7.
- The temperature requirement of the crop is between 20-27°C.
- Low atmospheric humidity and clear bright days are also necessary to ensure insect activities for pollination.
- Organic matter (compost, poultry droppings) can be added prior to planting to improve the buffer capacity of the soil.
- The land can be prepared by Ploughing 3-5 times to ensure fine soil tilt and organic material incorporated during the final plough.

2. Varietal Selection

While selecting the onion variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a particular area. Seeds of the onion variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety

Promising tomatoes cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

i. Enterpriser (Samtom-11)

A fresh market type with large oblate fruits, good for both rain-fed and dry season production.

ii. Ronita (Samtom 12)

Medium sized, firm pear-shaped fruits, more compact than Roma VF, resistant to nematodes and suitable for dry season.

iii. Roma VF (Samtom -71)

Medium sized, pear shaped, fruits, suitable for dry season production and resistant to nematodes and fusarium wilt, red fruit with good keeping quality;

3. Nursery preparation

- For good germination in the nursery, a well-tilled seedbed with a fine loose surface is necessary. The seedbed with moist poultry droppings and compost should be worked into the seedbed before sowing.
- After preparing the seedbed, mark it out in rows, which should be about 10-15cm apart in a 120cm wide seedbed. Then a groove of about 12m depth is made along each row.
- Sow in nursery bags made up of polythene sachet water bags. Cut each bag into two equal parts and perforate the sealed bottom of each half to allow for water drainage. Fill each half bag with a dark soil (humus) mixed with poultry droppings or compost 4:1 or light sandy loam soil. Sow two seeds in each half bag. Water carefully every evening using Knapsack of seed to avoid displacement of seed from position, germination will take place after 4 to 5 days. In order to avoid insect and rodent attack on seedlings, a nursery tent made of mosquito net can be used as protection.

4. Land preparation

- Where possible land should be ploughed and harrowed and pre-emergent herbicide selective for tomatoes used.
- In cases of zero tillage, land should be cleared and as much as possible should be weed free at the time of transplanting.
- Where there are weeds, the land should be sprayed with systemic herbicide e.g. glyphosate prior to transplanting in seven days.

5. Transplanting

- ✓ Seedlings are transplanted after spending between 3 and 4 weeks in the nursery.
- ✓ Plant density varies dependent on the growth vigor of the tomato variety.
- ✓ Hybrid varieties grow more vigorously and hence planting density should be reduced.
- ✓ Some recommended planting spatial distribution of hybrid tomato seedlings are shown below:-
 - (a) 45cm x 90cm within and between rows respectively:

Planting density per hectare Area per square meter occupied by each seedling = $0.45\text{m} \times 0.90\text{m} = 0.405\text{m}^2$

No. of stands or seedlings / hectare = $10,000/0.405 = 24,691$

stands

(b) $60\text{cm} \times 90\text{cm} = 0.6\text{m} \times 0.9\text{m} = 0.54\text{m}^2$

No. of stands or seedlings /hectare = $10,000/0.54 = 18,518$ stands.

- ✓ Two weeks before transplanting seedlings to the field, till soil to about 1 foot and mix in aged manure or compost.
- ✓ Plant seedlings 45cm or 60cm apart. Pinch off a few of the lower branches on transplants, and plant the root ball deep enough so that the remaining lowest leaves are just above the surface of the soil.
- ✓ Water well to reduce shock to the roots.

6. Fertilization

- Tomato thrives better with organic more than inorganic fertilizer.
- The use of poultry droppings to fertilize tomato is now gaining popularity.
- The amount to be used depends on the nutrient status of the soils.
- It is better to apply two weeks after transplanting and thereafter every month.

7. Care/staking

- Stake tomatoes by supporting the growing branches on a standing peg of more than 1m height to obtain higher yields.
- Fertilize two weeks prior to first picking and again two weeks after first picking.
- If using stakes, prune plants by pinching off suckers so that only a couple of stems are growing per stake.

8. Irrigation/watering

- Water generously for the first few days.
- Water well throughout the growing season.
- Mulch five weeks after transplanting to retain moisture.
- Use pesticides for pest control and herbicide for most pre-emergence herbicides. Fertilize with organic or inorganic manure at list three times before maturity.

9. Pest and diseases control

Tomatoes are susceptible to insect pests and diseases; as such adequate control measures should be administered,

10. Harvest/storage

Harvest tomatoes when they are matured and slightly ripe for long distance markets and when they are matured and fully ripe for fresh market. Store tomatoes in a cool dry place.

- **9.4 PEPPER (*Capsicum* spp L.)**

Pepper (*Capsicum* spp) is belonging to the family *Solanaceae* and genus *Capsicum* include *Capsicum annuum* (sweet or bell pepper) and *Capsicum Frutescens* (aroma pepper and chillies or hot pepper).

9.4.1 Good Agronomic Practices (GAP) for pepper production

1. Site selection/Ecological requirements

- Needs a fertile and well drained sandy-loamy soil with a pH of 5-7.
- The temperature requirement of the crop is between 18-30°C.
- Pepper is a day neutral crop and can tolerate shade (grow well under shade).
- Pepper can grow best on areas with 600mm of rainfall and it does not withstand flooding and drought.
- Organic matter (compost, poultry droppings) can be added prior to planting to improve the buffer capacity of the soil.

2. Variety Selection

While selecting the pepper variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a given locality. Seeds of the pepper variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety

Promising pepper cultivars obtained in North eastern Nigeria and their qualities.

i. FL-2289 (Sampep-I)

Compact growth, medium maturing (140 days), vivid red in colour, medium length (4 cm) fruit with pointed ends. Fruit held independently and highly pungent.

ii. P. Sakarho (Sampep-3)

Compact growth, early maturing (130 days); red-orange in colour, medium sized fruit with pointed ends; fruits held pendent and moderately pungent.

iii. U-KIMBA (Sampep-4)

Compact growth but tend to shed leaves at maturity, medium maturity 140 days; fruit medium to long 4-5 cm, slender with pointed ends, pink colored, held upright and highly pungent.

3. Propagation

Pepper is propagated by seed

a. Nursery Activities

- ✓ The soil should be well-prepared, loose and in good tilth.
- ✓ Plough the soil if the hardpan is present and the bed is prepared and constructed with 1-1.2m width by any suitable length.
- ✓ The seed is then broadcast or drill with an intra-row spacing of 20cm.
- ✓ The bed is usually mulched to conserve moisture and reduce heat.
- ✓ A starter dose of fertilizer is needed at two weeks after planting and the seedling are ready for transplanting when they have 8-12 leaves usually 20-40 days after sowing.

4. Land preparation

- Where possible land should be ploughed and harrowed and pre-emergent herbicide selective for pepper used.
- In cases of zero tillage, land should be cleared and as much as possible should be weed free at the time of transplanting.
- Where there are weeds, the land should be sprayed with systemic herbicide e.g. glyphosate prior to transplanting in seven days.

5. Transplanting

- 10-20t of farm yard manure can be applied at land preparation, and the seedlings can be transplanted on ridges or basin during dry season.
- Transplanting should be early in the morning or late evening and irrigation is done immediately.
- If moisture is adequate the spacing is 50 -80cm x 20-40cm inter and intra row spacing, respectively.

6. Fertilization

- The fertilizer should be applied at the rate of 130kg N/ha. 80kg P/ha and 110kg K/ha depending on the fertility of the soil, and the N is applied in split dose at 2-3 weeks after transplanting and 4 weeks after first application.

7. Weed control

- The critical weed competition is 6-9 WAT in pepper it can be control by weeding manually using hoe or by using post-emergent herbicide e.g. Alachlor, Linuron and Dipheramid at the rate of 1.0, 0.5 and 1.0 kg a.i /ha respectively at first and third days after transplanting.

8. Pest and Diseases control

Pepper is been attacked by many pest and diseases, therefore there need to be apply control measures accordingly.

9. Harvesting

Pepper is ready for harvest at 2-3 month after transplanting and 3-6 weeks after flowering by handpicking when it is matured and ripe (change in colour).

10. Storage

Freshly harvested pepper must be stored between 7-10°C under 95% humidity, and it has a shelf life of only 3-5 weeks, but when dried it can be stored for several months.

SECTION III: POSTHARVEST ACTIVITIES OF CROPS

MODULE 10: POST-HARVEST HANDLING AND MANAGEMENT OF CEREAL CROPS

• 10.1 Objectives

10.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration

- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

10.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

10.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

10.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

10.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **10.2 What is Post-harvest?**

This is the stage immediately following the harvest. It determines the final quality of product. Postharvest management includes the following activities. The activities immediately following harvest are post-harvest activities and these include

- i. Harvesting
- ii. Drying
- iii. Threshing/Shelling
- iv. Cleaning/Winnowing
- v. Storage
- vi. Processing
- vii. Transportation
- viii. Marketing

• 10.3 Post-harvest losses

Post-harvest losses refer to quantitative and qualitative losses that occur to agricultural products/commodities (e.g. grains) after harvesting due to a series of operations the products under goes through:

- Inappropriate pre-harvest practices,
- inadequate farming equipment,
- poor grain handling (quality losses)
- poor grain drying systems
- poor grain storage systems

Post-harvest losses cause financial losses and food safety issues, moisture related problems (rotting, moulds etc.), grain losses from pest infestations and so on. These losses impact greatly on household food vulnerability and cash income (livelihood). In general, post-harvest losses can be minimized by adopting or use of Good Agricultural Practices during post-harvest activities from harvesting to marketing i.e. use of proper post-harvest management practices. Post-harvest losses can be managed through:

- i. Tools used for harvesting
- ii. Stage and timing of harvesting
- iii. Indicators of harvesting time
- iv. Process of harvesting in your community.

• 10.4 Threshing Practices

10.4.1 Proper use of manual tools available for harvesting in a locality

- Sickle
- Knife/cutlass, etc.

10.4.2 Stage and timing of harvesting

- Time of harvest influences yield, quality and storage life of crop.
- Prematurely harvested cereal crop has high moisture content and it is of low quality. In addition, it is susceptible to mould, loss of viability, increase drying cost, loss in weight/quality and so on.
- Delayed harvesting leads to excess shattering and grains are pre-disposed to pests e.g birds attack, rodents, germination and increased field losses (Heads of sorghum that fall to the ground come into contact with fungi in the soil.

10.4.3 Indicators of harvesting time

- Harvest at the right time and moisture content. Learn from experienced producers in the production cluster.
- The purpose of the crop or use for which the crop was intended; e.g. sorghum for silage/fodder/feed harvested before flowering and for production harvested after grains matures.
- Market demand; e.g. maize harvested at green (fresh maize) or dry (dry maize grains) stage depending on market demand.
- Weather conditions – most crops are harvested during dry conditions,
- Prevailing market price and profit margins – harvesting can be delayed in order to obtain better prices at a later date.
- sometimes farmers are forced to harvest their crops early to avoid floods (especially in low lands) and to prevent destruction by livestock released before harvests.

10.4.4 Precautions during harvesting

- During harvesting, care should be taken to make sure that produce is not affected in quality or quantity.
- The crop should be harvested at the right stage depending on the intended use,
- The timing should also be correct and weather conditions should be dry because wet weather enhances rotting of produce,
- Delayed harvesting is not encouraged as many crops can get spoiled, thus reducing the quality and quantity available for consumption and sale.

• 10.5 Drying Practices

10.5.1 Important Tips in Drying Grains Practices

- Grains are usually dried until the correct moisture content (10 to 12 %) for optimum storage is attained. The reasons for drying to reach a moisture content level of 10 to 13% include:
 - Prevention of mould growth and aflatoxin contamination of the grains,
 - Reduction of the likelihood of insect attack,
 - Prevention of grain germination.
- Field drying is mostly practiced where the panicles are stack into bundles in the field and allowed to dry in the sun. But they should be kept off the ground whilst being dried so as to avoid mixing with stones and other debris.

10.5.2 How to measure grains' moisture content

i). Smelling a sample of grain for mouldy smell

- ✓ Take a representative sample of the produce under consideration in a convenient container,
- ✓ Move the container with sample close to your nose,
- ✓ Smell the sample: The smell of the produce should be typical. Other smells e.g. of chemicals, mouldiness, rot etc. should not be detectable.

ii). Biting grain method

- ✓ The biting test is even simpler to perform and can help determine suitability of grains for storage: A dried grain is tested by biting. If suitable for storage it will be brittle, hard and break easily into many parts.

10.6 Threshing practices

- Beating with sticks on the ground or in sacks, or using a mortar and pestle,
- Grinding on stones and motor,
- Use of threshing machines.

10.6.1 How to reduce losses during threshing

- Reduce losses during threshing by doing it on mats, cement blocks or smeared ground,
- Thresh early to reduce crop exposure to birds, rats, and other pests in the field,
- Dry thoroughly to reduce the moisture content of the grain before storage; (moisture content should be at 10-12%),
- Sorting is very important, especially when maintaining some crops as seeds, or improving the quality for marketing,
- The grain may be stored as un-threshed panicles (in the case of sorghum) or threshed before storage,

- **10.7 Cleaning/Sorting, winnowing**

Grain cleaning is achieved by winnowing to remove the low-density materials such as chaffs, leaf, stalk and empty seeds.

Sorting: It is done to remove the heavy material (stones, soil) which cannot be removed by winnowing.

- **10.8 Causes of losses and loss management During Storage**

The principal causes of quality/quantity losses and/or deterioration in stored grains are:

- Insects
- Moulds (High moisture content)
- Rodents
- Birds

10.8.1 Losses caused by insects

The losses caused by insects include:

- Weight loss,
- Loss in quality/market value,
- Introduce diseases,
- Reduced germination in seed material,
- Reduced nutritional value.

10.8.2 Method of controlling insects-infesting stored grains

i). Non-chemical methods of insect control (recommended)

- Timely harvest of crops: harvesting should be done when crop reaches physiological maturity. This reduces damage and losses due to birds, insect pests, rodents and termites, and reduces chances of transporting pests from field to the store.
- Adequate drying of harvested crops: Grains should be well dried in the sun before storage. This prevents germination, growth of fungi and attack by insects. Drying can be done the traditional way, by spreading the crop on clean bare ground for one to three weeks depending on the weather. Drying grains can also be done for one day by spreading on tarpaulin sheet. Note that if grains have been attacked by weevils, drying the grains in the sun for just one day will kill weevils, including larvae.
- Sterilization of food grains: This is done by spreading food grains on concrete floor, tarpaulin or a black plastic sheeting and covering tightly with clear plastic sheet under direct sunlight for 30-60 minutes. This destroys pests which have attacked the grain.
- Use of plant extract:
 - Mixture of ash and chili peppers mixed with grain: Dry the chilies and pound them into fine powder. Sieve cold wood ash from the fire place. Mix 2kg of wood ash with one table spoon of chili powder. Make sure they are thoroughly mixed with approximately 3kg of grain and the mix is ready for storage (This is mainly for seeds).

- Use of neem products. Mature neem leaves, if dried under shade, is used to control weevils. Mix 4kg of neem powder with 100kg of grain.
- Use of hot pepper (borkwano/sheta): Use four table spoons of well-ground pepper mixed thoroughly with 20 kg of grain.
- Storage of grain in air tight containers: All insects, including weevils, need air to breathe. So, storing grains in such tight containers such as PICS bags (Triple Bags), gourds, pots, GP tanks (Plastic water tanks) or jerricans can keep away weevils.
- Smoking: Farmers can build a wood fire to place under granaries so that smoke enters the cobs or pods of grains and shells of beans or nuts.
- Storing new grains in a clean environment: Clean and clear all old grains from the store in good time before harvest, and burn all trash. Also, farmers are advised not to mix old grains with new ones.
- Proper threshing and cleaning of grains: Cleaning and sorting of grains to remove broken, infested and dirty grains is important.
- Regular inspection of stored grains: This gives farmers an opportunity to take action before weevils start damaging grains, either by sun drying of the grain/beans/nuts, or through the application of organic chemicals.
- Area surrounding the store to be kept clean and tall grass cut regularly. Old fence can act as a hideout for rats.

ii) Chemical method: should only be used as the last resort, when other methods are not effective.

10.8.3 Storage facilities

Some of the common traditional storage facilities are:

- ✓ Granaries
- ✓ Clay pots
- ✓ Gourds
- ✓ Jute bags
- ✓ Metal drums and bins
- ✓ Baskets
- ✓ Underground pits
- ✓ Bins of stone or mud plaster

10.8.4 Storage practices

The Four pillars of good Storage practice include:

- Ensuring that the crop going into the store is in good condition,
- Keeping the store in good condition,
- Practicing good storage hygiene,

- Maintaining the condition of crops and stores throughout the storage season

10.8.5 Seed storage

- Grain may be stored in sealed pots or gourds, or in tins or bottles.
- Plastic water containers with screw-on lids make ideal seed stores.
- Larger quantities of maize seed are stored by suspending entire cobs from the roofs or overhang of the house; they may also be suspended from trees.

10.9 Transportation

- Transportation is an important operation of the grain value chain, as commodities need to be moved from one step to another, such as field to processing facilities, field to storage facilities, and processing facilities to market. The lack of adequate transportation infrastructure results in damage of food products through bruising and losses due to spillage.
- Transportation losses are relatively very high due to poor road infrastructure along with these improper and poorly maintained modes of transportation results in large spillage and high contamination. Also, poor handling and packaging contributes to losses.
- Overloading of trucks is another major reason for high transportation losses.

MODULE II: RICE POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT

• 11.1 Objectives

Explain Rice Post-Harvest Practices and its associated components

11.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

11.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

11.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

11.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

11.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **11.2 Introduction**

Post-harvest management of rice covers the following activities:

- i. Harvesting,
- ii. Threshing,
- iii. Winnowing/Cleaning,
- iv. Drying,
- v. Storage
- vi. Processing
 - Parboiling
 - Milling the paddy rice.

- **11.3 Some Tips on Rice harvesting Practices**

Harvesting and threshing methods of rice vary widely from farmer to farmer and also from country to country. The levels of mechanization, from country to country also differ widely.

- The methods for rice harvesting may either be manual, animal or mechanically operated.
- Rice harvesting is mainly carried out in Sub-Saharan Africa manually. The process involves cutting of the rice plants at maturity stage, pre-drying, threshing, winnowing, drying and bulking. Several of these post production activities have direct bearing on the quality of paddy available

for processing. The steps involved with rice post-harvest activities are considered below:

- The optimal stage to harvest a rice crop is when the grain moisture content is between 20 - 25% or when 80 - 85% of the grains are straw coloured and the grains in the lower parts of the panicle are in the hard doe stage. This is about 30 days after flowering.
- If the crop is harvested too late, many grains are lost through shattering or drying out and are cracked during threshing. Cracked grains do not germinate and they also break during milling.
- If rice is harvested too early, there will also be many immature seed grains and this will reduce quality.
- Immature rice kernels are very slender and chalky and this results in excessive amounts of bran and broken grains during milling.

11.3.1 Problems of Rice Harvesting

Late harvesting

- i) Lodging,
- ii) Over drying of grain,
- iii) Shattering,
- iv) Rodent/bird attack,
- v) Contamination when panicles touch the ground.

Early harvesting

- Many of immature grains,
- Discoloured grains,

Timely harvesting will ensure high paddy yield, a quality product for parboiling or milling and high milling recovery with low kernel breakage.

• 11.4 Rice Storage:

Rice is best stored as paddy because the husk provides some protection against insects and helps prevent grain quality deterioration. A safe storage system will prevent the grain from getting wet after drying and also give protection from insects, rodents, and birds.

Rice can be stored for longer periods if:

- Moisture content is maintained at less than 14% for grain and 12% for seed;
- Grain is protected from insects, rodents, and birds; and
- Grain is protected from re-wetting by rain or from the surrounding air.

A rule of thumb for seed is that the life of the seed will be halved for every 1% increase in moisture content or a 5°C increase in storage temperature above recommended levels.

• 11.5 Rice Processing:

Milling:

- Milling rice paddy removes the husk and bran layer to produce white rice. Rice is best milled at 13–14% moisture content.
- Best results are attained when the process is completed in a number of stages. Grain temperatures should not exceed 45°C during the process.
- An efficient mill removes the husk (20%), the bran or meal (8–10%), and leaves 70% as white rice.
- Rice grown in irrigated systems should attain 60% white rice as head rice (unbroken, white kernels) and rain fed systems 40–50% as head rice. Rice is milled in several ways.
 - Hand pounding using a mortar with a pestle results in very high numbers of broken rice and leaves brown rice (meal layer still attached). Cleaning of the husk is done by winnowing.
 - A one-step milling process where the husk and the bran are removed in one pass and white rice is produced directly from the paddy. The single-pass rice mill is an adaptation of the Engle berg coffee huller. This process results in many broken kernels, low white rice recovery (50–55%), and head rice yields less than 30%. The fine broken are often mixed in with the bran and the ground rice husk.
 - A two-step milling process where the husk and the bran are removed separately. These mills are often called compact rice mills and, in many countries, have superseded the Engle berg mill. The two-stage mill has separate hulling and polishing processes. Rubber rollers remove the husk and the brown rice is polished with a steel friction whitener. These mills have a capacity of 0.5–1 t/hour paddy input and are often used for custom milling in rural areas. The milling performance of the compact rice mill is superior to the Single-pass huller with milling recoveries normally above 60%.
 - A multi-stage milling process where rice passes through a number of different operations. The milling process in larger commercial mills combines a number of operations and produces higher quality and higher yields of white rice from paddy rice.

The process involves:

- Pre-cleaning the paddy prior to milling;
- Removing the husk or outer layer from the paddy;
- Polishing the brown rice to remove the bran layer;
- Separating the broken grains from the whole kernels;
- Bagging the milled rice; and

- Managing the by-products.

MODULE 12: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF GROUNDNUTS & COWPEA CROPS

• 12.1 Objectives

Explain Groundnut and Cowpea Post-Harvest Practices and associated components

12.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

12.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

12.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

12.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

12.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **12.2 Groundnut Post-harvest management**

Postharvest management of groundnut covers the following activities:

- i. Harvesting (Digging)
- ii. Drying
- iii. Decortication/Threshing/Shelling
- iv. Cleaning/Winning
- v. Storage
- vi. What happens after farm

- **12.3 The process of harvesting groundnuts:**

- Preparation before harvesting and tools used for harvesting,
- Timing of harvesting,
- Indicators of harvesting time,
- Precautions during harvesting,
- Process of harvesting in your community.

- **12.4 Stages in post-harvest handling of groundnuts**

- Cleaning
- Drying and methods of drying
- Curing
- Storage (in bags; Hermetic storage - PICs bag)
- Shelling (manual or mechanical)

- **12.5 Aflatoxin Problem in Groundnut**

12.5.1 What are Aflatoxins?

- ✓ They are poisonous substances produced by certain fungi. Small quantities of aflatoxin can cause fatal liver cancer in both animals and humans and eventually death.
- ✓ Aflatoxin contamination is serious quality problem in groundnuts.

12.5.2 What causes contamination of groundnuts by Aflatoxin?

The causes of contamination of groundnuts by Aflatoxin can be grouped into:

I. Pre-harvest factors

- End of season moisture stress to the crop for more than 20 days,
- Growth cracks and mechanical injury to the pod,
- Damage to pods by termites or pod borers,
- Death caused by diseases (stem, root, and pod rots) at pod maturity stage,

- Nematodes damage to the pod.

2. At post-harvest

- Harvesting over mature crop,
- Mechanical damage to the pod at the time of harvest,
- Stacking the harvest when pod moisture is more than 10% or under humidity conditions,
- Storing haulms with immature pods,
- Pod rotting due to roof leakage or high moisture levels,
- Insect damage during storage.

12.5.3 What are the effects of aflatoxins contamination?

- Aflatoxin causes marked deterioration in pod and kernel quality because of fungal growth.
- Contaminated kernels are unfit for consumption. If eaten in sufficient quantities aflatoxin can cause sickness, hepatitis and/or liver cancer. It is, therefore, extremely important to ensure good management of ground nut crops and suspected seed should be destroyed rather than used for human or animal consumption,
- Reduced market price of the produce,
- Causes decay in both seeds and non-emerged seedlings,
- Severely affects the export of groundnut and its bi-products.

12.5.4 How to minimize the effects of Aflatoxins

The effects of aflatoxin can be minimized by the following methods:

- Harvesting the crops as soon as it is mature, any delay will encourage the development of fungus,
- Avoid damaging of pods during cropping,
- Removing soil from the pods before leaving to dry,
- Ensuring that the correct drying procedures are used and that damaged, shriveled, or rotten pods are removed before storage,
- Store the pods under dry, well-ventilated conditions to ensure the moisture content remains low, thus discouraging fungal growth,
- Avoid damaging the seed during shelling and destroy any discolored, shriveled or mould seed,
- Avoid pod damage by insects as this can leave the pods /seeds susceptible to fungal infection,
- Pre-harvest contamination is severe during drought and extra care should be taken to clean the seed, especially the smaller seed.

- **12.6 Cowpea Post-harvest management**

- **12.6.1 The process of harvesting Cowpea**

- Preparation before harvesting and tools used for harvesting,
- Timing of harvesting,
- Indicators of harvesting time,
- Precautions during harvesting,
- Process of harvesting in the community.

- **12.6.2 Harvesting**

- Cowpea harvesting is done when the pods are fully mature and dry.
- In early-maturing and erect varieties, one picking may be sufficient.
- For indeterminate and prostrate varieties, the dried pods can be picked two or three times. The pods do not mature at the same time because of the staggered flowering period.

- **12.6.3 Stages in post-harvest handling of cowpea**

- Drying and methods of drying (10% moisture content)
- Threshing/Shelling
- Winnowing
- Sorting/Grading (seed size, seed colour)
- Storage (air tight containers, bags; Hermetic storage - PICs bag), use of organic materials e.g ash, pepper, oils from plant products etc
- Storage of cowpea with fumigants has been useful too (phostoxin)

MODULE 13: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF TOMATO & ONION CROPS

- **13.1 Objectives**

Explain Tomato and Onion Post-Harvest Practices and associated components

- **13.1.1 Activities**

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

13.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

13.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

13.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

13.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **13.2 Onion Post-harvest management**

Postharvest management of onions includes the following activities:

- i. Harvesting
- ii. Curing
- iii. Topping of bulbs
- iv. Cleaning/Grading
- v. Storage (on floor, off-floor methods, specialized storage facilities)
- vi. Packaging (jute bags,)

- **13.3 Harvesting**

The genesis of post-harvest losses in onions begins with the process and techniques of harvesting used or adopted by the farmer. Therefore, adherence to some indices that govern good harvesting is necessary.

13.3.1 Maturity indices for harvesting

- 75-80% of plants have their leaves fallen over
- Plant does not put on new leaves
- Leaves start drying (e.g external leaf)
- Resistance to pull-out of the ground

- Counting from date of sowing (bulbs mature within 100 to 140 days, depending on the variety)

13.3.2 Tips on good harvest of onion bulbs

- Stop irrigation at maturity- at 1 (soils with low water retention) or 2 weeks (soils with high water retention) before harvest to prevent bulbs from being waterlogged.
- Harvest bulbs during the cooler part of the day (early morning & late evening).
- Manual harvesting-levering the bulbs with a fork to loosen them and pulling the tops by hand,
- Avoid damaging the bulbs.

1. Curing:

- ✓ Drying of the outer scales to a rustling dry stage to prevent moisture loss and decay by storage pathogens,
- ✓ Can be done through windrowing of field dry method, or in a room, shed or green house.

2. Topping of bulbs
3. Cleaning and grading
4. Storage
5. Packaging

• 13.4 Tomato Post-harvest management

Tomato postharvest management includes the following activities:

- i. Harvesting
- ii. Field packing
- iii. Transportation to the collection center/primary market
- iv. Sorting
- v. Grading
- vi. Packaging
- vii. Transportation to wholesale markets,
- viii. Marketing to retailers and the final consumer
- ix. Storage

13.4.1 Harvesting

The genesis of post-harvest losses in onions begins with the process and techniques of harvesting used or adopted by the farmer. Therefore, adherence to some indices that govern good harvesting is necessary.

- ✓ Tomatoes are harvested when the fruits are turning breaker to light red (long term distribution).
- ✓ Tomatoes are harvested in stage 4 because of the consumer's demand.

13.4.2 Harvest indices for tomatoes

- Tomatoes should be harvested when they reach the maturation stage.
- There are three maturation stages for tomatoes: matured green, partially ripened and ripened stages.
- Harvesting should be done when the fruit is at the breaker stage and at the onset of the partially ripened stage.
- However, table tomatoes can be harvested at the ripened stage.

13.4.3 Tips on good harvesting of tomatoes

- ✓ Harvest tomatoes when temperature is cool, either early in the morning or late afternoon.
- ✓ Tomatoes are usually hand-harvested, graded, and packed in the field.
- ✓ Careful handling of tomatoes during harvesting is important to minimize physical injury.
- ✓ Always wear gloves and clean hands during harvest in order not to damage from your finger nails.
- ✓ Harvesting is done 3-4 times a month.
- ✓ Tomatoes are hand-picked, and directly placed in a clean bag, plastic buckets, and other plastic containers.
- ✓ Harvested tomatoes are kept under the shade while waiting to be transported to the packing house.

i. **Sorting/Grading**

- Tomatoes are to be sorted under the shade in a cool temperature and clean place.
- Sorting by ripeness, size, color variety, and free from damaged.
- Workers who will do the sorting should be trained in advance before working.
- Mechanically damaged, rotten, insect attacked and physiological disorder tomatoes are taken out of the container.
- After grading, tomatoes are to be placed in a plastic crates, wooden baskets, or bamboo, baskets, carton box and any kind of packaging.
- Containers should only contain a good tomato and free from damage.
- Use clean smooth crates and baskets to reduce the physiological injuries on tomatoes

ii. **Transportation**

- Tomatoes are highly perishable fruit, don't exposed to direct sunlight during transportation.
- Trucks can be used for transporting tomatoes from the field to market.
- Wooden crate, bamboo basket, plastic crates are used for long distance transport. As a result, tomatoes are injured through vibration and unsmoothed space inside the packaging.
- Over-filling and the shape inside wooded crate or bamboo basket can also cause damage.

iii. **Post-harvest drying of tomato**

- Tomato can be dried and stored. Dried tomato can also be used to produce powdered tomato which can also be stored for future use.
- Wholesale marketers and tomato farmers usually slice and dry their excess tomatoes to prevent spoilage and losses.
- However, it is best to use tomato of red cultivar to produce dried tomato.
- The tomatoes should be adequately washed with clean water and should be free from pest, disease and molds damage.
- Tomatoes should be cut uniformly into thin slices.
- The seeds should be removed.
- Sliced tomatoes should be sun dried using clean plastic bags, mats or trays on raised platforms to prevent contamination.
- Cover the drying platforms with a clean net to shield the tomatoes from flies.
- Mechanical and solar dryers can also be used for drying.
- Don't dry sliced tomatoes on open floor.
- To produce tomato powder, mill the dried tomatoes.

MODULE 14: POST-HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF SESAME

• **14.1 Objectives**

Explain Sesame Post-Harvest Practices and associated components

14.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration

- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

14.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

14.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

14.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

14.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **14.2 Post Harvest Handling and Management Practices of Sesame**

The post-harvest handling and management practices of sesame include the following:

- i. Harvesting
- ii. Drying
- iii. Threshing/Shelling
- iv. Cleaning/De-hulling
- v. Storage
- vi. Transportation

- **14.3 Harvesting**

The plants are cut with a cutlass or sickle and immediately bundled, tied upright and left in the sun for one week or until they are sufficiently dry for threshing.

14.3.1 Stage and timing of harvesting

- Time of harvest influences yield, quality and storage life of crop,
- Prematurely harvested sesame crop has high moisture content and of low quality,
- Delayed harvesting leads to excess shattering, are pre disposed to pests, germination and increased field losses (capsules of sesame splits and seeds fall to the ground come into contact with fungi in the soil),
- Time of harvesting depends on the variety,
- Harvest at the right time and moisture content,
- The harvesting starts when 75% of the fruit capsules are ripened e.g. have turned brown,
- Stems tend to change from green to yellow to red in color and the leaves has begun to fall off.

14.3.2 Drying

- The primary objective of drying is to achieve rapid and steady drying of the pods, in order to avoid aflatoxin contamination.
- Excessive moisture of seeds can quickly heat up and become rancid.
- Make bundles and stalked upright for drying.
- One week after harvesting, thrash and winnow the seeds.
- More importantly, during oil processing, moist seed leads to low yields and clogs the screw or cage, a part of the press.

14.3.3 Threshing

In order to avoid contamination and reduce losses, thresh on a tarpaulin or on clean concrete floor

This is extremely important as some buyers will reject sesame that has been contaminated with fungal infestation that causes food poisoning, e.g. aflatoxin contamination.

14.3.4 Cleaning/de-hulling

i. Manual Cleaning process

ii. Mechanical Cleaning

14.3.5 Storage

- ✓ Sesame seed is best stored unshelled, in dry conditions, protected from rain and vermin (particularly rats and mice). The seeds for storage must have 10 % moisture content,

- ✓ Bagged seeds (whether shelled or unshelled) should not be placed directly on a concrete floor due to the risk of dampness that may cause mould development,
- ✓ Before bagging, dust the pods with Actellic Super to protect them from storage pests.
 - For short term storage of less than six months, store grains in a clean and roofed store.
 - Lock up the store for safety.
 - Sesame can be stored – if kept in a cool place - for approximately 5 years without loss of viability

14.3.6 Transportation

- ❖ Bulking and Delivery
 - ✓ Bulk grains and bag immediately after threshing. Drying for about 2-3 more days under direct sunlight is necessary to prevent spoilage.
 - ✓ Stack bags on pallets to improve aeration.
 - ✓ Tag bags and transport bags to designated collection centers.
 - ✓ Weigh bags in designated collection centers and record weight in ledgers.
 - ✓ Transport weighed grains to larger collection centers.

14.3.7 Other post-harvest activities

a. Sesame Seed Quality Control

For consumer safety reasons, the Quality Assurance standards should reflect a meticulous and thorough testing process that adheres to stringent guidelines at every step of the sample handling processes from

i. Quality Assurance:

Raw Material Evaluation/Testing:

- To help ensure that only fresh, potent, and pure ingredients are used - yielding premium supplements that are unsurpassed in quality.
- Quality assurance measures are required from the sesame production stage, all throughout sample processing stages, during sample storage, and within post-harvest handling facilities.

ii. **Quality Control (QC):**

- ✓ Post-harvesting operations include series of measurements of elements such as moisture, oil contents and facility environments that are constantly monitored to ensure comprehensive quality storage, manufacturing and post-harvest handling compliance.
- ✓ In addition, ensuring proper packaging of sesame seeds to ensure product integrity, purity and label claim accuracy is more and more priced. .
- ✓ The main quality control tests performed *in situ* include:
 - ❖ Measurement of % moisture content
 - ❖ Measurement of % oil content
 - ❖ Visual assessment of seeds:
 - a) To eliminate foreign matters
 - b) To discard moldy seeds,
- ✓ The microbial purity tests essentially meant for the evaluation of:
 - ❖ fungal infestation (for Aflatoxin contents), and
 - ❖ the bacterial burdens, are performed extemporary.

iii. **Further in-depth control:**

- ✓ The Products should undergo stringent testing before, during and post-harvest handling steps, using recognized techniques including analysis by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Ultraviolet/ Spectrophotometry, etc.
- ✓ Quality Assurance team of the processing plant and Quality Control State Departments should work in concert, providing checks and balances that ensure attention to a supplement's finest details, from raw material testing to final product analysis.
- ✓ Owing to continuous improvement purposes, at every stage in the field, and sesame post-harvest handling and during manufacturing process, samples control procedures, and standards must be reviewed and approved by QA professionals.

iv. **Fungal infestation of sesame/aflatoxin contamination**

- Aflatoxin (*Aspergillus flavus*), a fungi of the *Aspergillus* group, can invade sesame, producing toxic compounds known as aflatoxins (B1 B2 and G1 G2).
- Contaminated produce can be poisonous to people and livestock, and cannot be exported.
- Aflatoxin contamination and the related root disease also affect sesame seed, leading to low germination percentage and poor seedling establishment.
- Aflatoxin contamination can occur in the field, before harvest, during harvesting and post-harvest handling processes, e.g. field sun-drying, storage, and transportation of product.
- Pre-harvest contamination is influenced by soil moisture and temperature, and is likely to be most serious under drought conditions.
- Postharvest aflatoxin contamination occurs if the seeds becomes moist and/or damaged, and can occur at harvest or later.

Note: The soil in the field is known to be an excellent storage reservoir for aflatoxin-producing fungi, e.g. *Aspergillus* species

v. Methods reducing/managing aflatoxin contamination in sesame:

- i. Avoiding mechanical damage to pods or seeds during weeding, harvesting and storage;
- ii. Harvesting sesame seeds as soon as they are mature;
- iii. Proper drying (until moisture content is reduced to about 10 %; this will help avoid *Aspergillus* infestation and consequent aflatoxin contamination. Normally this can be achieved by sun-drying of pods, and avoiding seeds exposure to rains;
- iv. Storing dry seeds under moisture-free conditions. Moist sesame seeds are prone to fungal diseases, as mould spores are present in all crops.

SECTION IV: CROP PROTECTION

MODULE 15: PEST AND DISEASES OF CROPS AND THEIR MANAGEMENT

- **15.1 INSECT PESTS OF MILLET, SORGHUM AND SESAME**

15.1.1 Objectives:

- To identify the major insect pests of millet, their damage symptoms, prevention and control (False wire worm, shoot fly, shoot bug etc).
- To identify the major insect pests of sorghum, their damage symptoms, prevention and control (Sorghum shoot fly, southern corn root worm, pink borer, bollworm etc).
- To identify the major insect pests of sesame, their damage symptoms, prevention and control (Sesame gall midge, Sesame webworm etc).

15.1.2 INSECT PESTS OF MILLET

Millets are one of the most important cereal crops in the semi-arid tropics of the world, and form the staple diet of millions of people in Asia and Africa. Millets are reputed to be relatively free of insect pests when compared with other cereals such as sorghum, rice, and maize. However, this is not true in many areas in Africa, where the millets are attacked by a wide range of pests which may damage the crop at all stages of development.

FALSE WIREWORM (Darkling Beetle)

IDENTIFICATION:

- Young larvae are creamy white but change to a shiny yellow as they grow older.
- Fully grown larvae reach a length of about 25 mm
- The pupa is fragile white
- The adult is brown to nearly black beetle, 7-13 mm long

False wireworm (a) adult, (b) larvae

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- larvae live in the soil and feed upon the plant soon after the seed are planted,
- they hollow out the grain kernels which prevent germination
- Damage symptoms in the fields are bare areas of different sizes and general thinning of the crop stand
- Severe infestation may result in loss of the entire crop

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Adjustment of planting data
- Seed treatment with insecticides

SHOOT FLY (*Atherigona approximata*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The adult is small grey-coloured fly
- Matured larvae are yellow and about 6 mm long

Shoot fly adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Larvae move to the growing point and cut the central leaf, resulting in the production of a dead heart.
- Sometimes the larvae feed on the tender leaf blades and the damaged margins become deep brown in colour.
- Larvae of this fly also damage the earheads severely

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Adjustment of sowing date
- High seeding rate
- Use of higher yielding shoot fly resistant cultivar
- Use of systemic insecticides

SHOOT BUG (*Peregrinusra aidis*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The female is yellowish brown and the male dark brown
- Wings of adults of both sexes may be longer or shorter than the abdomen
- Long winged forms have transparent wings
- Short winged forms extend only to the sixth abdominal segment
- The nymphs and adults' lives in groups on the leaves

Shoot bug adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- The insect imbibes sap from leaves confining itself in the leaf whorls or on the inner side of leaf sheaths.
- The sucking of sap leads to leaf chlorosis and stunted growth,
- Sometimes death of the whole plant occurs
- Reduced plant population or shrivelled and chaffy grains

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Use of effective insecticides

15.1.3 INSECT PESTS OF SORGHUM

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) is an important cereal crop world-wide that is widely cultivated for food, fiber, forage, ethanol, and sugar production. At least 150 insect species have been reported as pests of sorghum worldwide, and more than 100 of them occurred in Africa. Sorghum shoot fly (*Atherigona soccata*), corn rootworm (*Diabrotica sp*), and corn borers are important sorghum pests in Asia, Africa, and Europe. Sorghum aphid (*Melanaphis sacchari*) and sorghum midge significantly impact sorghum production in Australia and some tropical countries.

SOUTHERNCORN ROOTWORM (*Diabrotica undecimpuncta*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The larvae are slender, white or pale yellow, and grow to a length of 12 mm
- The last segment of the larval abdomen has a nearly circular margin and is brown
- The pupa is white and fragile
- The adult is 6 mm long and yellowish-green with 11 black spots on the fore wing
- The adult has black head and antennae that are one-half to two-third of the length of the body

Southern corn rootworm adult and larvae

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- The rootworm bores into the root of sorghum or enters the stalk just above the roots.
- Here it eats out the crown of young plants and kills the growing point
- Symptoms of damage are stunting and dead hearts

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Keeping field free of grassy weeds
- Ploughing and disking 30 days before planting
- Rotation for at least 2 years with a non-grass crop
- Early planting and planting at a higher than normal seed rate
- In-furrow application of effective insecticides

PINK STEM BORER (*Sesamia calamistis*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The adult moth is light beige, more or less striped with brown
- There are considerable geographical differences in colour and markings
- Mature larvae are 30 mm long and 3.5 mm wide, with a brown head and a buff body that has pale pink dorsal markings

Pink stem borer (a) eggs, (b) larvae, (c) pupa, (d) adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Early larval instars feed on leaves, especially the leaf sheaths
- Later instars tunnel into stems through internodes, which causes stem breaking and chaffy panicles
- Panicles also can be attacked
- Other symptoms are shot-holes in whorl leaves and dead hearth in young plants

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Careful weeding and clean cropping
- Removal of food sources near the sorghum crop
- Use of effective insecticides

BOLLWORM (*Heliothis armigera*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The moth is large and brown or grey with specks that form a V-shaped mark on the fore wings.
- The hind wings are dull-coloured, with a black border
- The young larvae are whitish-green
- Fully grown larvae vary from almost black, brown or green to pale yellow or pink with light or dark stripes

- Fully grown larvae are about 40 mm long

Bollworm larvae and adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Larvae infest the sorghum head and feeds on the developing grain
- It also feeds on the tender whorl leaves

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Ploughing the field to expose pupa to heat or predators
- Crop rotation
- Planting of open-type sorghum panicles that expose larvae to predacious insects and birds
- Application of effective insecticides

15.1.4 INSECT PESTS OF SESAME

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is one of the oilseed crops and it is of Indian origin. It is a short duration crop (90-100 days), and with two distinct types of seeds viz., white and black and both yield edible oil. Sesame is attacked by many insect pests such as shoot and capsule borer, sesame gall fly, leaf hoppers, hawk moth, aphids, thrips, pod bugs etc. In addition, leaf hopper (*Orosius albicinctus*) transmits mycoplasma disease which causes phyllody disease. Being an economically important crop and with changing scenario of pests in recent days

SESAME GALL MIDGE (*Asphondylia sesami*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The adult is 5 mm in length
- Red and delicate in appearance
- The larva is apodous, white in colour and 6-7 mm in length

Sesame gall midge adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Larvae feed in flower buds, which stimulates the formation of galls in which the larvae develop
- Larval feeding interferes with development of the seed capsule or cause the fruit to drop
- Larvae also feed within developed capsules which become stunted and twisted

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Application of suitable insecticide to the crop at the start of flowering

SIMSIM WEBWORM (*Antigastra catalaunalis*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- Adult moths are nocturnal and have a wing span of around 15-20 mm.
- The forewings are orange-brown in colour with dark indistinct wavy lines
- The hindwings are pale yellow.
- Larvae are at first white in colour, but become pale green with black spots as they mature. They can grow to 14 mm in length
- Head capsule of the larvae is dark brown.

Simsim webworm adult

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Young larvae mine the leaves and shoot tip.
- Older larvae roll up young leaves at the tip of the shoot and tie them together with silk threads, and feed within the shelter formed.
- Larvae also feed on flowers and bore into pods.

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Observation of closed season
- Sesame grown in shade is attack less
- Foliar spray of effective insecticide at three-week intervals

• 15.2 INSECT PESTS OF COWPEA AND GROUNDNUT

15.2.1 INSECT PESTS OF COWPEA

African continent is the second most important bean producing region of the tropics. Insect pests are among the principal agronomic constraints to the production of the crop in the region.

CUTWORMS (*Agrotis sp*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The adult moth has grey-brown forewings with a dark brown or black kidney-shaped marking
- The hindwings are almost white
- Later instars vary from grey, greenish grey, greenish brown to brown or black
- Mature larva is 3-4 cm long
- The pupa is smooth and shiny brown with two spines at the tip of the abdomen
- The pupa is about 2 cm long

Cutworms larvae

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Larvae girdle and cut off plant at soil level

- Damage may also occur below ground, leaving cavities that cause plants to wilt and die
- In severe cases an emerging crop may be completely destroyed

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Use of baits (often grain or animal protein) treated with insecticides

FLOWER THRIPS (*Megalurothrips sjostedti*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- Adult is tiny, shiny-black, and about 2 mm long
- With a yellowish band across the pronotum
- The nymphs are cream to orange in colour and usually found within the flower

Flower thrips

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Both adults and nymphs feed at the base of petals and stigma
- Severe injury is characterised by flower malformation, distortion, and discolouration
- In some cases, flower buds do not open and abort prematurely
- Damage may be more serious in dry areas

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Mulching combined with irrigation, may help reduce adult emergence from pupation in the soil
- Application of effective insecticides

SPINYBROWN BUG (*Clavigralla tomentosicollis*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The adults are stout, about 10 mm long, furry and brown
- Adults feed singly or in mating pairs and drop off the plant when disturbed
- Nymphs are sluggish and form colonies on pods and peduncles

Spiny brown bug

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- Symptoms of damage on beans are tiny depressions (dimpling) on the pod wall and seed coat
- The seeds rot or shrivel and lose viability
- The whole pod may also be shrivelled.

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Use your hands to take any Squash Bugs or eggs off of your plants and squish them
- Try planting Pollen & Nectar Producing Plants to attract good predators that will eat Spiny brow Bugs
- Application of effective insecticides

15.2.2 INSECT PESTS OF GROUNDNUT

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.), is grown globally for its food and edible oil in about 30 million ha. In Africa, Nigeria cultivate about (2.6m ha). Groundnut is attacked by many insects at different stages of plant growth, but only a few of the over 100 insects associated with this crop are economically important.

WHITE GRUBS (*Schyzonycha africana*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- The young grubs are translucent, white, and 5 mm long when they hatch.
- Fully grown grubs are larger than a human thumb,

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- The larvae initially feed on soil organic matter for a few weeks and then eat roots.
- They also damage pods
- Severely infested fields have large patches of dead plants and the surviving plants are often stunted and show signs of wilting.

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Ploughing exposes many larvae, pupae, or even adults to the sun and to predators, e.g. birds.
- Crop rotation is an effective control method
- Ensuring proper drainage in the field since grubs prefer moist soil, especially with decaying organic matter - female beetles prefer to lay eggs on moist-decaying organic matter.
- Reducing or pruning trees that attract adults bordering the crop.
- Heavy application of nitrogen fertilizer which can kill first instar larvae .
- Shaking down trees that harbour adult scarab beetles. The fallen beetles can be collected and destroyed (e.g. by putting them in bags which can be burned)

• 15.3 Insect Pests of Mango and Pepper

15.3.1 MANGO

MANGO HOPPER

IDENTIFICATION:

- The nymphs are greenish with black or brown markings, cannot fly and move rapidly on the plant
- Adult are golden-brown or dark brown, wedge-shaped insects about 4-5 mm in length which look rather like a small cicada.
- When disturbed, the adults jump off the plant with a clicking sound, fly a short distance and then quickly resettle on the plant

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS:

- The wedge shaped nymphs and adult insects puncture and suck sap of tender parts, reducing vigour of plants and particularly destroying the inflorescence and causing fruit drop.
- Heavy puncturing and continuous draining of sap causes curling and drying of infested tissue.
- They also damage the crop by excreting a sweet sticky substance facilitates the development of sooty mould

NATURAL ENEMIES OF MANGO HOPPER

- **Parasitoids:** *Polynema* spp., *Gonatocerus* sp, *Tetrastichus* sp
- **Predators:** *Mallada boninensis*, *Plexippus paykullii*

FRUIT FLY

IDENTIFICATION:

- The eggs are white, elongate, and elliptical in shape.
- The white maggot is legless, and resembles an elongated cone.
- Their mouth is at the pointed end of the body.
- Pupae (puparium) is yellowish-brown and seed-like.
- Adults abdomen has two horizontal black stripes and a longitudinal median stripe extending from the base of the third segment to the apex of the abdomen.
- These markings may form a "T" shaped pattern, but the pattern varies considerably.

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS

- The female punctures outer wall of mature fruits with the help of its pointed ovipositor and insert eggs in small clusters inside mesocarp of mature fruits.
- On hatching, the maggots feed on fruit pulp and the infested fruits start rotting due to further secondary infection

Natural enemies of fruit fly

- **Parasitoids:** *Fopius arisanus*, *Diachasmi morphakraussi*

MANGO NUT WEEVIL

IDENTIFICATION:

- Eggs are elliptical, about 0.8 mm long and 0.3 mm wide and are creamy-white in colour when freshly laid.
- Larvae are white grubs with a curved body, brown heads and legless.
- Newly hatched larvae are extremely slender and elongated and about 1 mm long.
- Mature larvae are about 17 mm long.
- Pupae are whitish when newly formed, but change to a very pale red colour just before the adult emerges.
- Adults are weevils with a compact body, about 8 mm long.
- They pretend to be dead when touched or disturbed.

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS

- Grub makes zigzag tunnels in pulp
- Eats unripe tissue and bore into cotyledons
- Fruit dropping at marble stage
- Oviposition injuries on marble sized fruits.
- Adult weevils feed on mango leaves, tender shoots or flower buds

Natural enemies of Mango nut weevil

- **Predators:** *Rhizoglyphus* sp, *Camponatus spoecophylla*, *Smaragdina* sp.

STEM BORER

IDENTIFICATION:

- The eggs are brownish-white, cylindrical, and 6 x 2 mm, with narrowly rounded ends.
- Newly-hatched, first-instar larvae are about 10 mm long.
- Fully grown larvae may reach 100 mm long, elongate

DAMAGE SYMPTOM

- The larvae tunnel the axis of inflorescence and destroy it completely.
- Damage by stem borer (*E. indica*) causes bending and drying of the inflorescences.
- At fruit setting as young maggots bore into these tender fruits which slowly turn yellow and finally drop.
- The inflorescence shows stunted growth and its axis bends, at the entrance point of larva

Natural enemies of Inflorescence midge

- Parasitoids: *Tetrastichus* sp., *Platygaster* sp., *Systasis dasyneurae*, *Aprostocetus* spp.

BARK EATING CATERPILLAR

IDENTIFICATION

- Full grown caterpillar is dirty brown in colour and is about 35-45 mm in length.
- Pupae is about 10 mm long,
- Adults Male head and thorax are rufous (reddish to brown).
- Forewing is pale-rufous with numerous dark-rufous bands of strigae; there is a spot at the end of the cell.

- The abdomen and hindwings are fuscous.
- Female head, thorax and abdomen are ochreous-white.
- Forewings are ochreous-white with markings as in the male.
- Hindwings are pale, slightly suffused with fuscous, with numerous obsolescent brown striga.

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS

- Caterpillars bore into the trunk or junction of branches
- Caterpillars remain hidden in the tunnel during day time and come out at night, feed on the bark.
- Larvae construct galleries and move in it.
- Affected plant show dried galleries on the stem and shoots.
- Webbing consists of wooden frass and faecal pellets of larvae hanging outside the tunnel.
- Heavy infestations retard the growth of tree and affect the fruits yield.

15.3.2 INSECT PESTS OF PEPPER

PEPPER WEEVIL (*Anthonomus eugenii*)

IDENTIFICATION:

- Adult have a long, stout beak and strongly arched body with thorax and elytra covered with scales.
- They are generally 2 - 3.5 mm long and 1.5 - 1.8 mm wide,
- Beetles are light brown immediately following eclosion, darkening to a greyish black color
- Eggs are laid singly and measure approximately 0.53 mm in length and 0.39 mm wide.
- They are pearly white in color when first laid, darkening to yellow over time.
- Eggs are an oblong-oval shape usually, but may take on the shape of the cavity in which they are laid.

- Larva measured approximately 1 mm long at the smallest and maturing to a final length of about 6 mm.
- The body is white but may appear grey with accumulation of matter in the digestive tract,
- The head being yellowish-brown with brown margins

DAMAGE SYMPTOMS

- Stems of infested pods will begin to yellow and wither at their attachment to the plant, and the pods themselves may prematurely take on a yellow/red color and fall from the plant.
- Significant fruit drop is perhaps the most easily observed indicator of pepper weevil infestation.

PREVENTIVE MEASURES/CONTROL:

- Disc or plow under pepper plants and cull piles of fruit following harvest, eliminating a potential reservoir for infestation between crop plantings.
- It is also important to eliminate nightshade weeds that can act as an alternate host;
- If an infestation occurs, it is critical that fallen or culled fruit be removed from the site or destroyed.
- Create enabling environment for hymenopterous parasitoids (pteromalid *Catolaccus* hunter and the braconids *Triaspis eugenii* and *Urosigalphus* sp) that attack pepper weevils
- Use of effective Insecticides (permethrin, oxamyl, esfenvalerate, and cryolite

• 15.4 Major Insects Pests of Rice, Maize, Tomato and Onion

15.4.1 Insect Pests of Tomato

APHIDS (Peach aphid, Potato aphid) *Myzus persicae*

Identification:

- ✓ Two species of aphids are common on tomatoes, the potato (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*) and green peach (*Myzus persicae*) aphids.
- ✓ Aphids have soft pear-shaped bodies with long legs and antennae and may be green, yellow, brown, red, or black depending on the species and the plants they feed on.

- ✓ Most species have a pair of tube-like structures called cornicles projecting backward out of the hind end of their body. The presence of cornicles distinguishes aphids from all other insects.
- ✓ Generally adult aphids are wingless, but most species also occur in winged forms, especially when populations are high or during spring and fall.
- ✓ The ability to produce winged individuals provides the pest with a way to disperse to other plants when the quality of the food source deteriorates.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ Small soft bodied insects on underside of leaves and/or stems of plant; usually green or yellow in color, but may be pink, brown, red or black depending on species and host plant.
- ✓ Aphids remove sap from the plant with their piercing-sucking mouthparts.
- ✓ Tomato plants can tolerate large numbers of aphids without suffering yield loss.
- ✓ However, severe infestations can cause leaves to curl and may stunt plants.
- ✓ If aphid infestation is heavy it may cause leaves to yellow and/or be distorted, necrotic spots on leaves and/or stunted shoots.
- ✓ Aphids secrete a sticky, sugary substance called honeydew which encourages the growth of sooty mold on the plants.
- ✓ Aphids may transmit viruses from plant to plant on certain vegetable and ornamental plants

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ If aphid population is limited to just a few leaves or shoots then the infestation can be pruned out to provide control
- ✓ Check transplants for aphids before planting; use tolerant varieties if available;
- ✓ Reflective mulches such as silver colored plastic can deter aphids from feeding on plants;
- ✓ Sturdy plants can be sprayed with a strong jet of water to knock aphids

- ✓ from leaves
- ✓ Insecticides are generally only required to treat aphids if the infestation is very high - plants generally tolerate low and medium level infestation;
- ✓ Insecticidal soaps or oils such as neem or canola oil are usually the best method of control; always check the labels of the products for specific usage guidelines prior to use.
- ✓ Many predators also feed on aphids. The most well-known are lady beetle adults and larvae, lacewing larvae, soldier beetles, and syrphid fly larvae.
- ✓ Naturally occurring predators work best, especially in garden and landscape situations.

Tomato fruit worm – *Helicoverpa armigera*

Identification:

- ✓ The adult is a nocturnal moth of medium size with a wingspan of 28-37 mm and is very variable in intensity and shade of colour.
- ✓ The forewings are pale yellowish-brown. There are several darker reddish-brown lines across the wing, with a dark spot slightly in front of the mid-point.
- ✓ The hind wing is paler, with a broad blackish band extending over the outer half, and the wing has a pale terminal fringe.
- ✓ It can be found feeding at flowers during the day. The female can lay up to 2000 eggs on the host plant.
- ✓ Fully grown caterpillars are about 30–40 mm long

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ The caterpillar is omnivorous but feeds predominantly on herbaceous and low shrubby plants. They pupate underground.
- ✓ Plants of the families Solanaceae and Leguminosae are favored hosts. It will eat virtually all parts of the host plant but concentrates principally on the flowers and fruits.

- ✓ They will also feed on the soft parts of the young needles of pine trees, just at the tip of the fascicle sheaths.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ The use of synthetic insecticides was found to be effective these including Carbaryl, Karate, Cypermethrin, Dimethoate and Monocrotophos have been documented to effectively protect tomato fruits.
- ✓ The neem extract, especially the neem seed extract was found to be as effective in reducing the number of holed fruits and damaged fruit.
- ✓ Neem product have found to act as deterrents of oviposition for *H. armigera*
- ✓ Cultural manipulation is one of the elementary procedures which create hygienic condition in field that is unfavorable for pest development.
- ✓ Hand picking is a traditional practice for removing large size larvae and infested fruits.
- ✓ Three times weeding, three times handpicking and chemical application is most effective for management of *Helicoverpa* larva but hand picking is best from economic point of view.
- ✓ Deep ploughing during summer reduces number of pupa whereas fall ploughing reduces the number of overwintering populations of *Helicoverpa*
- ✓ Early sowing, balance dose of fertilizer application, better intercultural operation and irrigation practice reduce number of *Helicoverpa* in tomato field.
- ✓ Strip cropping or Inter cropping with marigold, wheat, sunflower, sesame, soybean, cowpea and mungbean reduce *Helicoverpa* infestation in tomato.
- ✓ Pheromone trap is effective *Helicoverpa* monitoring tools among various monitoring techniques.
- ✓ Resistant genotypes are best for insect pest management
- ✓ Entomopathogenic fungus have been used in management of *Helicoverpa*

WHITE FLIES - *Bemisia tabaci*

Identification:

- ✓ Whiteflies, also known as aleyrodidae, are soft-bodied, winged insects closely related to aphids and mealybugs.
- ✓ They can be as small as 1/12 of an inch, somewhat triangular in shape, and are often found in clusters on the undersides of leaves.

- ✓ They are active during the daytime, so they are easier to spot than some other nocturnal pests.
- ✓ Whiteflies are capable of overwintering and reproducing throughout the year in warmer climates.
- ✓ Eggs are laid on the undersides of leaves. When the eggs hatch, the larvae will look like teeny white ovals without legs. They don't move but they immediately start sucking the plant juice. This is why gardeners miss the whiteflies until it's too late.
- ✓ Adult females can produce up to 400 eggs, which can hatch in between one week and a month. They are usually laid in a circular pattern.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ Whiteflies suck plant juices and, in turn, produce a sticky substance known as honeydew. Honeydew left on its own can cause fungal diseases to form on leaves.
- ✓ They can be found in most any region, but they are so tiny that they are usually camouflaged.
- ✓ Due to whitefly feeding, plants will quickly become extremely weak and may be unable to carry out photosynthesis.
- ✓ Leaves will wilt, turn pale or yellow, and growth will be stunted.
- ✓ Honeydew is a sign that the whiteflies have been feeding for several days. You might also see ants, which are attracted to the honeydew.
- ✓ Check undersides of leaves around the veins for white insects, even if they aren't visible, and feel leaf surfaces for honeydew.
- ✓ If the whiteflies are feeding, they'll suddenly all fly off the leaves in a swarm, so it's very obvious.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Always start with blasting whiteflies with your watering hose. This will cause them to scatter.
- ✓ Then, spray your leaves with insecticidal soap. Coat them; be sure to spray the undersides of leaves.

- ✓ Only spray plants when temperatures are cooler—such as late in the day, as heat may cause an adverse reaction in your plant. Follow up 2 or 3 times.
- ✓ Homemade mixture should be helpful to control and deter whiteflies: Use a mixture of dishwashing liquid, such as Palmolive with lemon, and water.
- ✓ Ladybugs, spiders, lacewing larvae, and dragonflies are a few of many beneficial insects that can control a whitefly population. Hummingbirds are another natural predator.
- ✓ When it comes to whiteflies, **avoid chemical insecticides**; they're usually resistant and all you end up doing is killing the beneficial insects—their natural predators—and the insects which pollinate the garden for a better harvest.

LEAFMINERS (*Tuta absoluta*)

Identification

- ✓ Mature larvae drop from leaves into soil to pupate; entire lifecycle can take as little as 2 weeks in warm weather; insect may go through 7 to 12 generations per year.
- ✓ The larvae feed on apical buds, tender new leaflets, flowers, and green fruits which make it a serious pest in tomato.
- ✓ Host Range, this insect also attacks other solanaceous crops like potato, eggplant, pepino and tobacco. It is also reported on many solanaceous weeds.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ Thin, white, winding trails on leaves; heavy mining can result in white blotches on leaves and leaves dropping from the plant prematurely
- ✓ Early infestation can cause fruit yield to be reduced; adult leafminer is a small black and yellow moth which lays its eggs in the leaf, larvae hatch and feed on leaf interior.
- ✓ Yield loss: If unchecked, insect will cause 100% yield loss.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Leafminer natural enemies normally keep populations under control;

- ✓ Check transplants for signs of leafminer damage prior to planting; remove plants from soil immediately after harvest if making new plantings in same place or close by;
- ✓ Keep the field free from weeds especially Solanum, Datura, Nicotiana;
- ✓ Use pheromone traps and white sticky traps to monitor and control insect
- ✓ Only use insecticides when leafminer damage has been identified as unnecessary spraying will also reduce populations of their natural enemies.

15.4.2 Insect Pests of Maize

Maize is one of the world's most important cereal crops. Its wide genetic diversity and multiple uses account for its cultivation in a large range of environments. Many factors limit maize production; insects and mites being among the most important. Lepidopterous pests are the most damaging insects of maize worldwide. This group includes stem and ear borers, armyworms, cutworms, and grain moths. Next in importance are the beetles (weevils, grain borers, rootworms and white grubs), followed by the virus vectors (aphids and leafhoppers).

STEM BORERS (*Busseola fusca*)

Identification

- ✓ Eggs are creamy-white when laid but darken just before emergence. They are usually laid in batches of 30-100 under leaf sheaths.
- ✓ The larvae (caterpillars) lack conspicuous hairs or markings and the head capsule is dark brown and the prothorax is yellowish-brown.
- ✓ The adult wing-span is 25-35 mm. Its forewings are light to dark brown with darker markings. The hind wings are white to grey-brown.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ The African maize stalk borer is indigenous to and occurs throughout mainland Sub-Saharan Africa. Maize and sorghum are its main crop hosts.
- ✓ The larval stage (caterpillars) cause damage to maize by feeding on young leaves from where they can enter the stems.
- ✓ This may kill the plant. In older plants their feeding can damage can reduce grain production.

- ✓ First-instar larvae feed in the young terminal leaf whorls producing characteristic patterns of small holes and 'window-panes' (patches of transparent leaf epidermis) where tissues have been eaten away.
- ✓ Later they eat into the growing points, which may be killed so that the dead central leaves form characteristic dry, withered 'dead-hearts'. Older larvae tunnel extensively in stems, eating out long frass-filled galleries which may weaken stems and cause breakages.
- ✓ Larvae also tunnel into maize cobs and into the peduncles of sorghum and millet inflorescences and may seriously affect grain production.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Intercropping maize with non-hosts crops like cassava or legumes like cowpea can reduce African maize stalk borer damage.
- ✓ Alternatively, maize can be intercropped with a repellent plant such as silver leaf desmodium (*Desmodium uncinatum*) and a trap plant, such as Napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*), molasses grass (*Melinis nutiflora*) as a border crop around this intercrop to protect maize from stemborers.
- ✓ The trap plant draws the adult female away from the crop. More eggs are laid on the trap plant than on the crop but the larvae develop poorly or not at all on the trap plant. This practice is known as "push-pull".
- ✓ Good crop hygiene through the destruction of maize residues by burning to get rid of the larvae and pupae within the stems, and removal of volunteer crop plants and/or alternative hosts, prevents carry-over populations. This helps in limiting the initial establishment of stemborers that would infest the next crop.
- ✓ Two of the most abundant natural enemies of the African maize stalk borer are the larval parasitoids *Cotesia sesamiae* and *Bracon sesamiae*.
- ✓ They locate the stemborers while the stemborers are feeding inside the plant stems lay eggs into them.
- ✓ Chemical control can be achieved by applications of granules or dusts to the leaf whorl early in crop growth to kill early larval instars.
- ✓ This method has limited effectiveness once the larvae bore into the stem.
- ✓ Neem products (powder from ground neem seeds) are reportedly effective and may be applied to the leaf whorl in a 1:1 mixture with dry clay or sawdust. Pesticides are poisons so it is essential to follow all safety precautions on labels.

SHOOT FLIES (*Atherigona spp*)

Identification

- ✓ The larva is yellowish brown with a brown head which mines the midrib enter the stem and feeds on the internal tissues.
- ✓ Adult fly is dark grey, like the common house fly, but much smaller in size.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ The maggot feeds on the young growing shoots resulting in “dead hearts”.
- ✓ They feed on the decaying core of the shoots. Subsequently on the death of central shoot, plant gives out tillers and plant get bushy appearance.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Grow resistant cultivars
- ✓ Furrow application of phorate granules 10 G 10 kg/ha (or) lindane 6 G 25 kg per ha
- ✓ Seed treatment with imidachloprid 70 WS 10 g/kg of seeds.

GRASSHOPPERS (*Zonocerus variegatus*)

Identification

- ✓ *Z. variegatus* has seven post-embryonic stages (adult and six larval stages) stages I to 3 larvae are gregarious while stages 4 to 6 and adults are solitary.
- ✓ The length of eggs varied from 5.10 to 7.52 mm
- ✓ Damage is caused mainly by the later instars and the pressure on crops

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ Heavy damage does occur, the plants often being entirely defoliated and the cobs eaten away
- ✓ Nymph and adults will feed on corn in any plant growth stage
- ✓ The outer rows of corn are usually the first attacked, but as the grasshoppers reach the adult stage, they move further into the field eating the leaves, silk and tips
- ✓ When grasshopper populations are high and damage is severe, they may only leave the leaf mid-ribs, pruned ears and barren stalks.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Scaping the field bunds and summer ploughings to destroy eggs, dusting cabaryl 10 D or malathion 5 D at 10 kg/ac or foliar spraying with fenitrothion 2 ml/l found effective in their management.
- ✓ Hand picking of adults if few or if the field is small
- ✓ Sprinkle wood ash on the leaves of the small plants
- ✓ Remove weeds in and around the maize field
- ✓ Burn or destroy all crops residues around the maize planting area
- ✓ Identify egg laying sites and destroy by ploughing or digging before first planting

ARMY WORMS (*Spodoptera exempta*)

Identification

- ✓ The eggs of *Spodoptera exempta* are pale-yellowish, darkening through development until, just before hatching, the black head-capsules of the larvae can be seen through the shells.
- ✓ Eggs are laid in batches of 10-600 which are covered by black scale-hairs from the tip of female abdomen
- ✓ Larvae occur in two forms: the gregarious (gregaria) form characteristic of high-density populations and the solitary (solitaria) form found at low larval densities. Intermediate, 'transiens' forms may also be present.
- ✓ Mahogany-brown, 10-14 mm long, with a smooth, shiny surface. They are difficult to distinguish from pupae of other *Spodoptera* species.

- ✓ Adult *S. exempta* are stout-bodied moths of typical noctuid appearance, 14-18 mm long and with a 29-32 mm wing span.

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ The symptom of *S. exempta* attack is gross feeding damage to foliage, growing points and young stems.
- ✓ Severe infestation results in total defoliation or destruction of the plant to ground level.
- ✓ Infestation of the crop by *S. exempta* is evident from the 'windowing' or skeletonizing of younger leaves caused by rasping of the epidermis by young larvae, or gross feeding by older larvae.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Weed-free maize crops greater than 50 cm high are unlikely to become infested by newly hatched larvae of *S. exempta* because the leaves are too tough to allow them to establish. However, if larvae are able to develop on grass weeds, subsequent infestation of the crop may occur.
- ✓ Only the larval stage is accessible to control by insecticides
- ✓ Recommended insecticides include organophosphorus compounds, carbamates and synthetic pyrethroids, several of which (especially fenitrothion and cypermethrin) are effective when applied at low dose rates by Ultra Low Volume (ULV) spraying.

15.4.3 Insect Pest of Onion

Introduction

The onion is attacked by a number of pests some of them are described as below

ONION FLY (*Delia antiqua*)

Identification

- ✓ The onion fly looks similar to a small house fly and can be found flying around early summer as it lays eggs in seedlings or the soil at the base of plants.
- ✓ Male relatively large (6-7 mm long) with densely grey to yellow-grey dust on thorax and abdomen.

Onion fly

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ Onions fly lay eggs which hatch into maggots and eat into onion seedlings usually between the leaves and small bulbs or roots.
- ✓ In older onions the onion fly maggots eat away at the bottom of the onion bulbs.
- ✓ These onion pests will eventually cause the onion leaves to go pale, wilt then die off, the bulb, or at least the inside of it to become rotten and stinky and the plant to keel over and die.
- ✓ After 3 days the eggs hatch and the larvae tunnel into the onion, where they dine non-stop for 3 weeks growing into full-sized 8mm long reddish-brown maggots.
- ✓ Fat and happy they burrow back into the soil and pupate, emerging as a new generation of flies 17 days later.
- ✓ At the end of summer after a few generations, the final pupae overwinter until next spring.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Crop rotation can provide effective control. Other methods include removal of all infested plants, autumn digging of the ground to destroy the pupae, and early or late planting in different parts of the world.
- ✓ Early planting results in pest avoidance, whereas late planting reduces the time available for the overwintered flies to oviposit on the plants.
- ✓ Yellow sticky cards and pheromone traps are in use.
- ✓ Drenching the soil with Spinosad or organophosphate insecticides provides effective control. Some resistance to the pesticides has been reported
- ✓ Entomopathogenic nematodes, entomopathogenic fungi and a braconid parasitoid attack the onion fly in different parts of the world

LESSER BULB FLY (*Eumerus funeralis*)

Identification

- ✓ They have a similar lifestyle pattern as the onion fly, but are slightly smaller at about 5mm

- ✓ These prefer narcissus bulbs but occasionally can be an onion pest
- ✓ The larvae of wheat bulb fly are white and legless

Lesser bulb fly

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ The maggots scrape away the bulb tissue and tunnel in. The infested bulbs begin to decay and the interior of the bulb fills with a semi-liquid mass.
- ✓ The bulb may be killed completely, or damaged to the point that only stunted leaves appear the following year.

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Pull up and destroy all plants infected with these onion pests at the time you know they are in the bulbs and before they have burrowed back into the soil.
- ✓ Bulbs in marginal condition can be treated in hot water (43 to 44°C) for 3 hours to control lesser bulb flies as well as stem nematodes.
- ✓ Removing bulbs after they have died back and separating those with damage from the healthy bulbs can reduce springtime populations of adults.
- ✓ Scattering onion planting throughout the garden helps, and removing the soil is also a good idea.
- ✓ Spreading a fine layer of sand or wood ash around the onion plants is also a good deterrent to adult onion flies from laying their eggs at the base of the plants.

ONION THRIPS (*Thrips tabaci*)

Identification

- ✓ adult onion thrips is some 1 to 1.3 mm long.
- ✓ The body is some shade of yellow, yellowish-brown or brown
- ✓ the antennae have seven segments,
- ✓ Adults are elongated with body color varying with temperature from yellow to brown

Onion thrips

Damage Symptoms

- ✓ These onion pests can wreak havoc in onion cultivation.
- ✓ They cut the epidermis of leaves or stems and suck the plant sap.
- ✓ This results in white silvery blotches on deformed leaves.
- ✓ Onion thrips have very distinctive feeding behaviors by punching through the leaf surface and then extracting sap from plant cells.
- ✓ Severe feeding injury by onion thrips is also associated with tiny black “tar” spots, which is excrement from thrips
- ✓ Thrips also may feed on onion bulbs following harvest and during storage, and this can cause scars that reduce the aesthetic appearance and quality of bulbs
- ✓ Thrips are the only vectors of tospoviruses and onion thrips is the principal vector of the tospovirus IYSV (Iris Yellow Spot Virus) in onion

Prevention/Control Measures

- ✓ Early detection of a pest problem is a key element for designing integrated pest management strategies.
- ✓ Thrips activity can be monitored using sticky cards
- ✓ The use of insecticides is the most common management tactic for onion thrips infestations in commercial onion production.
- ✓ Host plant resistance is another tactic that has received attention, but no onion cultivars that have a high level of thrips resistance are commercially available.

- **15.5 DISEASES OF CEREALS (Rice, Maize, millet, sorghum etc)**

15.5.1 Diseases of Maize

Brown spot (*Physoderma maydis*)

The disease normally occurs in areas of high rainfall and high mean temperatures. It attacks leaves, leaf sheaths, stalks, and sometimes outer husks. The first noticeable symptoms develop on leaf blades and consist of small chlorotic spots, arranged as alternate bands of diseased and healthy tissue. Spots on the mid-ribs are circular and dark brown, while lesions on the laminae continue as chlorotic spots. Nodes and internodes also show brown lesions. In severe infections, these may coalesce and induce stalk rotting and lodging.

Downy mildews (Several species of the genera *Peronosclerospora*, *Sclerospora*, and *Sclerophthora*) are responsible for downy mildews: **Crazy top downy mildew** (*Sclerophthora macrospora*); **Brown stripe downy mildew** (*Sclerophthora rayssiae* var. *zeae*); **Green ear disease** (*Sclerospora graminicola*); **Java downy mildew** (*Peronosclerospora maydis*); **Sugarcane downy mildew** (*Peronosclerospora sacchari*); **Sorghum downy mildew** (*Peronosclerospora sorghi*). These diseases are of serious concern to maize producers in several countries of Asia, Africa, and throughout the Americas. Symptom expression is greatly affected by plant age, pathogen species, and environment. Usually, there is chlorotic striping or partial symptoms in leaves and leaf sheaths, along with dwarfing. Downy mildew becomes conspicuous after development of a downy growth on or under leaf surfaces. This condition is the result of conidia formation, which commonly occurs in the early morning.

The diseases are most prevalent in warm, humid regions. Some species causing downy mildew also induce tassel malformations, blocking pollen production and ear formation. Leaves may be narrow, thick, and abnormally erect.

Maize rusts: The three leaf rusts on maize are common rust, polysora rust, and tropical rust.

Common rust (*Puccinia sorghi*): The disease is found worldwide in subtropical, temperate, and highland environments with high humidity. Common rust is most conspicuous when plants approach tasseling. It may be recognized by small, elongate, powdery pustules over both surfaces of the leaves (Photo 10). Pustules are dark brown in early stages of infection; later, the epidermis is ruptured and the lesions turn black as the plant matures.

Curvularia leaf spot (*Curvularia lunata*, *C. pallescens*, and *C. maculans*)

These fungi produce small necrotic or chlorotic spots with a light colored halo. Lesions are about 0.5 cm in diameter when fully developed. The disease is prevalent in hot, humid maize areas and can damage the crop significantly.

Fusarium and gibberella stalk rots (*Fusarium moniliforme* syn. *Fusarium verticillioides*)

(Teleomorph: *Gibberella fujikuroi*), *Gibberella zeae* (Anamorph: *Fusarium graminearum*). These two species of *Fusarium* are responsible for stalk rots in maize: *Fusarium moniliforme* is most common in dry, warm areas. It is particularly severe if it begins just before tasseling. *Gibberella zeae* is prevalent in cool regions. It is one of the most potentially damaging stalk-rotting agents. Symptoms produced by these pathogens resemble those caused by *Stenocarpella* or *Cephalosporium*, and cannot be differentiated until spore-producing structures are observed. Wilted plants remain standing when dry, and small, dark-brown lesions develop in the lowest internodes. When infected stalks are split, the phloem appears dark brown, and there is a general conspicuous browning of tissues. In the final stages of infection, pith is shredded and surrounding tissues become discolored.

Aspergillus ear rots (*Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus* spp.)

The disease may be a serious problem when infected ears are stored at high moisture contents.

Several species of *Aspergillus* can infect maize in the field. *Aspergillus niger* is the most common; it produces black, powdery masses of spores that cover both kernels and cob. In contrast, *A. glaucus*, *A. flavus* and *A. ochraceus* normally form yellow-green masses of spores. *Aspergillus parasiticus* is ivy green and less common in maize. *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* produce mycotoxins known as aflatoxins that are harmful to birds and mammals.

Bacterial stalk rot (*Erwinia chrysanthemi* pv. *zeae*, syn. *Erwinia carotovora* f. sp. *zeae*)

This pathogen appears in areas with high temperatures and high relative humidity. It spreads rapidly in the host plant and quickly kills it. Infected plants show a dark color and water soaking at the base of the stalk (Photos 80, 81) and lodge, dying shortly after tasseling. The bacterial decomposition produces a characteristic, unpleasant odor.

Maize chlorotic mottle virus (MCMV)

In early stages, the youngest leaves show fine chlorotic spots that coalesce and develop into broad chlorotic stripes along the veins. These chlorotic stripes contrast with dark green tissue when observed against the light. Leaves showing chlorosis finally die. Plants are stunted because of shortened internodes. Infected plants produce fewer and smaller ears. In most cases, the male inflorescence is malformed. The virus is transmitted mainly by several chrysomelid leaf beetles such as *Chaetocnema pulicaria* and *Diabrotica* spp., over a short period of time. Reports indicate that it is transmitted at very low rates via infected seed. When MCMV occurs in combination with maize dwarf mosaic virus (MDMV) or wheat streak mosaic (WSMV), it produces a severe reaction known as maize lethal necrosis.

15.5.2 Diseases of millets and sorghum

Smut

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Sorghum smut Causal organisms: Head smut (*Sporisorium reilianu*), Covered smut (*Sporisorium sorghi*), Loose smut *Sporisorium cruenta*, Long smut (*Tolyposporium ehrenbergii*).

Survival & spread: Head smut: soil-borne; Loose & covered smut: externally seed-borne; Long smut: air-borne. Loose smut infected plants become stunted, thin-stalked and flower earlier than healthy plants. All spikelets in a panicle get malformed. The membrane like fungal structure ruptures soon after head emergence and smut spores are blown away leaving the empty spikelet. In head smut, a sorus fully covered with a grayish-white membrane emerges from the boot leaf in place of normal panicle. Later the membrane ruptures and releases spore masses. In covered smut, a fungal sorus is formed in the place of grain. Most of the grains in an earhead are infected. The membrane like structure persists unless it is broken by mechanical force. In long smut, the sorus is covered by a whitish to dull yellow, fairly thick membrane. Sori are much longer (~4.0 cm) than those of the covered and loose smuts.

Pearl millet smut

Causal organisms:

Tolyposporium penicillariae (syn., *Moesziomyces penicillariae*)

Survival & spread: Survives as teleutospore in infected seed or in soil; air-borne sporidia cause infection.

In an infected floret ovary is converted into a sorus. Initially the sorus is bright or shiny green in color which later turns brown. The sorus is larger than grain and appears as enlarged body in place of grain. Mature sorus ruptures and releases spore balls containing teleutospores. The pathogen has a long latent period therefore secondary infection in the same aged crop is rare unless late sown or late flowering plants are available. The fungus survives as teleutospore in infected seed or in soil. Teleutospore germinates to produce sporidia, which become air-borne, fall on stigma and cause infection.

Downy mildew

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Sorghum downy mildew Causal organisms: *Peronosclerospora sorghi* (Syn., *Sclerospora sorghi*) **Survival & spread:** Survive as oospores in host tissues and soil; Primary infection in soil, secondary infection through conidia.

Symptom is visible as either systemic or localized infection. Systemically infected seedlings are pale yellow or have light-color streaking on the leaf, chlorotic and stunted and may die prematurely. First symptoms are visible on the lower part of the leaf blade, which later progress upward. In cool, humid weather, the lower surfaces of chlorotic leaves become covered by a white, downy growth consisting of conidia and conidiophores of the pathogen. The leaves emerging from the whorl subsequently exhibit parallel stripes of vivid green and white tissue. The infected striped areas die, turn brown, and disintegrate, resulting in a shredded appearance of the leaf. Conidia produced in the infected plants become air-borne and cause rectangular shaped local lesion on the leaf.

Anthracnose

Millet host: Sorghum

Causal organisms: *Colletotrichum graminicola* (Syn., *C. sublineolum*, Perfect state: *Glomerella graminicola*).

Survival & spread: survives on crop residues & wild sorghum; spread by air-borne conidia Initial symptoms of anthracnose on the leaf appear as small, elliptic to circular spots, with straw-color centre and wide margin. The lesion margin may be red, orange, blackish purple, or tan, depending on the pigment present in the cultivar (purple or tan). Adjoining spots may coalesce to give a blighted appearance on the leaf. A black dot like acervulus is often seen at the centre of the necrotic spot, which is the characteristic diagnostic symptom for leaf anthracnose. Apart from leaf the symptom may appear on the mid-rib, leaf sheath on the stalk and on spikelet tissues. In case of severe infection, plants get defoliated and die before reaching maturity. Infected mature stalks may develop reddish internal lesions, which may be continuous or discontinuous giving the stem a ladder-like appearance. Nodal tissues are rarely discolored. If the infection is early and severe, pre emergence damping-off may occur and the seedlings wilt and die.

Rust

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Sorghum rust Causal organisms: *Puccinia purpurea*

Survival & spread: survives on ratoon or successively grown sorghum, perennial & collateral hosts; spread by air-borne conidia. Sorghum rust appears as reddish brown pustules first on both the surfaces of the lower leaves. Generally the upper half of the leaf gets more severe infection than the lower half. As the disease advances the infection spreads to the younger leaves. Several adjoining pustules may coalesce to form large patch on the leaves and the infected leaves die prematurely giving the plants an unhealthy appearance

which becomes visible from a distance. The pustules may appear in any parts of the plant including mid-rib (arrow), peduncle and stem.

Helminthosporium leaf spot

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Causal organisms: **Sorghum:** *Bipolaris sorghicola* (Target leaf spot) **Pearl millet:** *B. setariae* **Proso millet:** *B. panici-miliacei* **Finger & Little millets:** *Drechslera nodulosum* (Perfect state: *Cochliobolus nodulosus*) **Foxtail millet:** *Cochliobolus setariae*

Survival & spread: Survive on crop residues, stray crops, collateral hosts and a few may be seed-borne; spread by air-borne conidia. Target leaf spots on sorghum appear as oval to cylindrical, purple to red spots with irregular margin and straw-colored centre. Spots may coalesce to form large lesion. The disease is known as Bipolaris leaf spot on pearl millet and appears as small, brown flecks or oval to oblong or rectangular spots. Lesions may expand and coalesce. Lesions usually are tan or grayish brown with a more or less distinct dark brown border. On finger millet the disease is known as brown spot. The characteristic symptoms appear as brown to dark brown spots on leaf, sheath. Infection on the neck and fingers may occur. Early infection may cause seedling blight.

Cercospora leaf spot

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Causal organisms: **Sorghum:** *Cercospora sorghi* (Grey leaf spot) **Pearl millet:** *C. penniseti* **Finger millet:** *C. eleusinis*

Survival & spread: survive on crop residues, stray crops, collateral hosts and seed; spread by air-borne spore Grey leaf spots on sorghum appear narrow rectangular lesions delimited by veins; longitudinally spot enlargement to develop irregular blotches; Lesions turn gray with age. On pearl millet it appears as oval lesion with dark brown margins and pale tan to grey or white centers, dotted with rows of black conidiophores. Lesions can be formed on stems. On finger millet the symptoms are usually observed on the older leaves and then spread to the younger leaves. Initial symptoms appear as reddish-brown specks with yellow halo. Later several such specks coalesce to form large lesions showing burnt appearance. During rains the fungus sporulates and produces grayish white growth at the centre of the spot and then it looks like brown spot.

Bacterial leaf spot

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Finger millet

Causal organisms: Sorghum: *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *Syringae*, **Pearl millet:** *P. syringae* , **Finger millet:** *Xanthomonas eleusinae*

Survival & Spread: Survives on crop residues in soil; spread by rain-splash. Bacterial spots are formed on the leaves of sorghum, pearl millet and finger millet. Initial symptoms on **sorghum** appear as small, elliptical or irregular shaped spots with straw color center and dark margin; spots coalesce to form large bands. On **finger millet** linear spots may be seen on both the surfaces of the leaf spreading along the veins. In the beginning, spots are light yellowish brown, but soon become dark brown. In advanced stage, the leaf splits along the streak giving a shredded appearance. All the leaves in a plant may be affected. The bacterium, mainly affects the leaves, but at times characteristic streaks may be found on the peduncle.

Bacterial stalk rot

Millet host: Sorghum

Causal organisms: *Erwinia chrysanthemi*

Survival & spread: Survives on crop residues in soil; spread by rain-splash, irrigation water. The disease is also known as *Erwinia* soft rot. Initial symptoms are visible on the tip of the uppermost leaf in the form of longitudinal patches and premature withering of the leaf. Subsequently lower leaves develop drying symptoms and the whole plant turns brown. The top leaves come out easily when pulled up. The base of the stalk shows water-soaked symptoms that later turn reddish dark brown color. When the infected stalk is cut and put into clear water bacterial oozes are seen to come out slowly like a white thread. The infected stem pith is disintegrated and show slimy soft-rot symptoms with foul-smell and eventually the whole plant wilts. The rot may invade a few nodes or the entire stalk turning it brown, which finally dries up and its interior turns into a shredded mass of fibrous tissue. Early infection causes premature death of the plant while late infection induces widespread lodging of the crop

15.5.3 VIRAL DISEASES

Millet host: Sorghum, Pearl millet, Small millets

Causal virus: Maize stripe virus (Sorghum) Maize streak virus (Sorghum, Pearl millet, Finger millet) Maize mosaic virus (Sorghum) Maize dwarf mosaic virus (Sorghum, Pearl millet) Sugarcane mosaic virus (Sorghum, Finger millet) Ragi mottle streak virus (Finger millet).

Maize stripe (MStV-S)

Transmission: Plant hopper *Peregrinus maidis*

Characteristic symptoms on sorghum are appearance of continuous chlorotic stripes/ bands between the veins of the infected leaf, which become yellow with continuous stripes progressing from the base towards the tip of the leaves. Affected plants appear stunted and height depends on stages of infection. Infected plant often fails to exert earhead (arrow). The disease is also known as chlorotic stripe stunt or sorghum stripe disease (SStD).

Maize mosaic (MMV-S)

Transmission: Plant hopper *Peregrinus maidis*

Appearance of fine, discontinuous, chlorotic streaks between the leaf veins and stunting of the plant characterize MMV infection (Plate 29a). The lesions become necrotic as the disease progresses. Early infected plant dies sooner or later without emergence of ear head. Plants infected at later stages may develop earhead with or without grain. In case of infection of multiple viruses the symptoms may vary and that may create confusion at field level identification.

15.5.4 DISEASES OF RICE

- Diseases are considered one of the major constraints militating against rice production in Nigeria.
- Rice diseases are mainly incited by fungi, viruses and bacteria.
- Early detection of pests and diseases is important in pest management.

Rice blast

- Rice blast is caused by a fungus called *Magnaporthe oryzae*, previously, *Magnaporthe grisea*, the asexual name is *Pyricularia oryzae*.
- The disease attacked Rice and a number of wild grasses, with many weeds as alternate hosts.
- The pathogen infects and produces lesions on the following parts of the rice plant:
 - leaf (leaf blast),
 - leaf collar (collar blast),
 - culm, culm nodes,
 - panicle neck node (neck rot) and
 - panicle (panicle blast).
 - Look for the oval or diamond-shaped spots with white centres and dark borders on the leaves.
 - Look for rots on the stems, especially at the nodes, and flower heads.
- ❖ Use disease free seeds
- ❖ Use of resistant varieties
- The main method of blast control is the use of resistant varieties which is the most practical and economical approach.

- cultural practices help to lessen the disease impact and should always be considered.
- ✓ Before planting:
 - Where it is possible to alter the planting date, select a time to avoid flowering coinciding with periods of high humidity.
 - Ideally, neighbouring farmers should plant at the same time to avoid spread of blast from older infected crops to those that are younger.
- ✓ During growth:
 - Avoid any cultural practices that weakens the plants and makes them more susceptible to blast:
 - Divide nitrogen applications into two or three splits, rather than applying it all at once.
 - Reduction of fertilizer application (e.g. urea) on attacked plots.
- ✓ After harvest:
 - Collect and burn or bury the remains of the crop, including the stubble as soon as possible after harvest.
 - Do not plant another crop while the last crop is still in the ground, otherwise spores will easily spread from the old crop to the younger one.
 - Removal of collateral hosts such as *Panicum repens*, *Digitaria* spp. etc.

RICE BLIGHT

- Blight is a broad range of plant diseases that cause browning, yellowing and withering followed by death of plant tissues.
- On rice the disease is caused by a bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*.
- Bacterial blight is a vascular disease affecting rice.
- Plants attacked by the disease have discoloured stems, fruits and leaves.
- Symptoms appear from the tip or edges of leaves as yellow, water soaked, undulate lesions, parallel to the veins, later turning yellow.
- In systemic infection the seedlings wilt and die.
- Rain splash and wind aid disease spread
- Irrigation also aids in dissemination of the pathogen.
- Disease management is effective using cultural practices such as use of resistant varieties, split application of nitrogenous fertilizer.

RICE MOTTLE VIRUS

- The host range of Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) is narrow, being restricted to species in the Poaceae, mainly in the tribes Oryzeae.
- The occurrence of RYMV was also reported in the wild species *Oryza longistaminata*, a rhizomatous rice species commonly seen growing in marshy areas.

- Symptoms of the virus consist of a linear chlorotic mottle on the newly emerged leaves which later spreads into broken or continuous pale-green to yellowish streaks.
- Symptom expression may be strongly influenced by light intensity, day length, humidity, temperature and growth stage of the plant, among other factors.
- Tillering is reduced, with a weakening of the plant, partial emergence of panicles and spikelet sterility.
- Plants of highly susceptible cultivars may die following severe infection
- Young seedlings at the 3-4-leaf growth stage are most susceptible to infection

MANAGEMENT

- **D**estruction of crop residues,
- the use of tolerant varieties,
- Burning of rice straws after harvest,

• 15.6 DISEASES OF VEGETABLES

15.6.1 Tomato Diseases

Bacterial Canker

The disease is often confused with cloudy spot disease, bacterial cankers start as yellow dots on ripening red tomatoes. If you look carefully at the spots — using a magnifying glass if you have one — you'll see a dark, birds-eye-type rim around each of the yellowed spots. This is what distinguishes bacterial canker from cloudy spot disease.

Early Blight

- You'll find brown spots on tomato leaves, starting with the older ones. Each spot starts to develop rings, like a target. Leaves turn yellow around the brown spots, then the entire leaf turns brown and falls off. Eventually the plant may have few, if any, leaves.

Septoria Leaf Spot

- After the plants begin to develop tomatoes, the lower leaves break out in yellow spots.
- Within the yellow spots, dark gray centers with dark borders appear.
- Black dots appear in the center of the spots. Foliage dies and falls off.

Powdery Mildew on Tomatoes

- Powdery mildew is easy to find on tomato plants as it looks like someone brushed the leaves with a white powder.
- You might find white spots on tomato leaves or even the stem.
- If you let the fungi thrive it will turn your tomato leaves yellow and then brown.

Fusarium wilt

- Symptoms of attack first appear as slight vein clearing on the outer portion of the young leaves followed by epinasty of the older leaves.
- At the seedling stage, plants may wilt and die soon after symptoms appear.
- In older plants, vein clearing and leaf epinasty are often followed by stunting, yellowing of the lower leaves, and formation of adventitious roots, wilting of leaves and young stems, defoliation, marginal necrosis of remaining leaves and finally death of the entire plant.

Blossom End Rot

- The tomato plants appear healthy, but as the tomatoes ripen, an ugly black patch appears on the bottoms.
- The black spots on tomatoes look leathery.
- When you try to cut off the patch to eat the tomato, the fruit inside looks mealy.

Blossom Drop

- Flowers appear on your tomato plants, but they fall off without tomatoes developing.

Fruit Cracks

- Cracks appear on ripe tomatoes, usually in concentric circles. Sometimes insects use the cracks as an opportunity to eat the fruit, or birds attack cracked fruit.

Sunscald

- The plants look healthy, and the fruit develops normally. As tomatoes ripen, yellow patches form on the red skin. Yellow patches turn white and paper-thin, creating an unpleasant appearance and poor taste.

MODULE 16: POSTHARVEST PESTS AND DISEASES OF SOME CROPS AND THEIR MANAGEMENT

• 16.1 TRAINING OBJECTIVES

1. To identify and classify postharvest diseases of dry, bulk materials, such as seeds and grains, and diseases of fleshy storage organs, such as vegetables (tubers, rhizomes, bulbs etc.) and fruits;

2. To state major toxins of postharvest diseases;
3. To state postharvest diseases of vegetables and fruits;
4. To state different control measures post-harvest diseases;
5. Health and Economic Implication of Aflatoxins Contamination
6. To state pre-harvest and postharvest ways of managing Aflatoxins
7. To identify and classify postharvest insect pests of different stored grains and
8. To state and identify common methods of controlling pests of stored produce (grains)

- **16.2 Post-Harvest Diseases: Meaning, Classification, Types and Control**

The diseases which develop on harvested parts of the plants like seeds, fruits and also on vegetables are the post-harvested diseases. The harvested products may get infected on the way to storage or to market or even before their final consumption. The plant parts may get infected in the field, but expression of symptoms may take place later, at any stage before final consumption. The plant products may get infected by microorganisms and cause rotting or decaying — partially or totally. The quantity of plant products becomes reduced due to the above infection. The seeds or grains may get damaged by accumulation of toxic substance, the mycotoxin produced by the infected microorganism. The fleshy fruits, vegetables etc., like tomato, banana, citrus, strawberries, rhizome of zinger, bulb of onion, tuber of potato etc., may get damaged. This results in reduction of quantity, quality or both of the affected parts or products as a whole.

The amount or extent of damage depends mainly on the pathogen(s) involved, on the condition of the products and the condition of storage. The pathogens involved are mainly fungi like *Pythium*, *Phytophthora*, *Rhizopus*, *Aspergillus*, etc. and some bacteria like *Pseudomonas*, *Erwinia*, etc.

16.2.1 Classification of Post-Harvest Diseases

Cristensen and Kaufmann (1965) divided the pathogens into two categories:

1. Field pathogen, and
2. Storage pathogen

1. Field Pathogen: The field pathogens are those, which cause infection during development of plants or their products before harvest.

2. Storage Pathogen: The pathogen which cause infection during storage are the storage pathogen.

Symptoms from infection caused by the 'field pathogens' may be very inconspicuous to be noted at the time of harvest. In fleshy and/or juicy fruits and vegetables, infection by field pathogen continues to develop even after harvest. They may become infected during storage by the same field pathogen(s) or by other pathogen(s). In seeds and grains, the disease caused by field pathogens ceases to develop further soon after harvest. But they may be infected further by the other pathogens during storage.

16.2.2 Types of Post-Harvest Diseases:

1. Diseases of dry, bulk materials, such as seeds and grains, and
2. Diseases of fleshy storage organs, such as vegetables (tubers, rhizomes, bulbs etc.) and fruits.

Observations of many investigators indicate that the real cause of the spoilage of vegetables and fleshy fruits in transit and also in storage are due to high moisture, high temperature, and injuries caused during marketing. Due to high moisture content and nutrient in harvested vegetables and fruits, they are vulnerable to attack by the pathogenic organisms. Injuries of fruits and vegetables may be caused during harvesting, packing and transposition they help the pathogen to enter the host and cause damage. But the seeds and grains can be stored for long time due to low moisture content (about 12-14%), where most of the pathogens cannot grow favourably.

I. Diseases of stored seeds and food grains: Field fungi, like *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Cladosporium*, *Verticillium*, *Helminthosporium*, *Colletotrichum* etc., attack seeds and grains on growing crops, but are unable to grow in storage due to low relative humidity i.e., below 90%. During storage or transit the seeds and grains are damaged by the different species of *Aspergillus* and *Penicilium*, which can grow well at a relative humidity ranges from 70-90%. The commonly available *Aspergillus* species are *A. repens*, *A. ruber*, *A. flavus*, *A. candidus*, etc. *Aspergillus* and a number of other storage fungi invade the embryo of the seeds and grains and they discolour the embryo or seeds as a whole, thereby the germination percentage reduces markedly. In some cases, spoilage of stored grains and seeds results in drastic increase of temperature up to 70°C or more, which encourage the growth of different thermophilic and thermotolerant fungi such as *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Absidia* spp., *Mucorpusillus*, etc.

In addition to storage fungi, other microorganisms may grow in/or on seeds and accelerate the deterioration process. During breeding period of insects, the moisture content and temperature of seeds increase, thereby rapid growth of the pathogen takes place producing enormous amount of spores. During

storage, the fungi produce mycotoxins that cause great damage to both domestic animals and human beings. The important fungi in this respect are *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*, which produce aflatoxin and other toxins.

Most Important Toxins are:

1. Yellow Rice Toxins: Produced in grains of rice, barley etc., by species of *Penicillium*.
2. Tremorgenic Toxins: Produced on prepared food during storage in refrigeration or in other places and also on food produced from infected grains and/or seeds.
3. Penicillic Acid: It is a carcinogenic substance produced by the different species of both *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* in molded cereal grains.

Control: The above-mentioned loss or damage by decay and spoilage of seeds and/or grains by storage fungi can be controlled by the following procedures:

1. Low Moisture: The moisture content of the rooms for storage should be kept below 70%.
2. Low Temperature: Temperature in store house should be maintained below 30°C, because most of the storage fungi can grow well at temperatures between 30°C and 55°C.
3. Ventilation: Proper ventilation should be maintained during storage and also during holding period before sending to market.
4. Sanitation: Proper sanitation should be maintained to keep storage products clean.
5. Use of Insecticide: Insecticides like methyl bromide and some other fumigants are used to treat the harvested seeds, thereby they regulate the storage fungi and reduce economic loss.
6. Clean: Clean, uninjured and properly ripened seed should be selected for storage, then only they are able to resist the action of the storage pathogen(s).

II. Diseases of Vegetables and Fruits: Different members of *Ascomycotina* and *Deuteromycotina* cause the major post-harvest diseases of fruits and vegetables. These are *Alternaria*, *Botrytis*, *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Sclerotinia* etc.:

1. *Alternaria*: Different species of *Alternaria* cause rot of many fresh fruits and vegetables, e.g., black rot of orange, tuber rot of potato, rot of sweet potato, purple blotch of onion, *Alternaria* rot of onion, *Alternaria* rot of cabbage, etc.
2. *Botrytis*: It causes “grey mold rots” of fruits like pear, apple, citrus etc., and vegetables like onion, tomato etc. Every year it causes great economic loss.
3. *Fusarium*: It causes different diseases, commonly called “pink or yellow molds”. Different species of *Fusarium* cause damage to tubers, bulbs, storage

roots etc. and frequently on cucurbits, tomato etc. It also cause brown rot of fruits like lemon, orange etc.

4. *Penicillium*: Species of *Penicillium* are commonly called “blue or green molds”, these cause rots of different fruits like onion, sweet potato etc. They also cause spots on different fruits. Under storage, the spotted fruits bear tufts of spores. Though most of the *Penicillium* species prefer relatively high temperature for their growth in storage, they still remain active near freezing temperature — at a slow rate. A few species produce ethylene which increases respiration of fruits, thereby it reduces the storage life of the fruits. It also produces patulin — a mycotoxin — which directly contaminates the sauces and fruit juices prepared from infected partly rotten fruits.

5. *Sclerotinia*: It infects different fruits and vegetables. Most common diseases are cottony rot of lemon, watery soft rot of bean pods, cucurbits etc. Storage diseases like bacterial soft rot of vegetables such as onion, carrot, potato etc. are mainly carried out by different species of *Erwinia*, such as *E. carotovora*, *E. chrysanthemi* etc.

16.2.3 Control of Post-Harvest Diseases:

The diseases can be controlled or reduced following the preventive procedures are:

1. The fruits and vegetables should be harvested and handled carefully to avoid any injury which may facilitate the pathogen to cause infection.
2. The infected region on the vegetables should be cut off to avoid further infection during transportation and storage.
3. Storage container, warehouses etc., should be properly cleaned with CuSO_4 , formaldehyde etc. to avoid contamination.
4. The crop should be stored or transported at a temperature low enough to slow down the development of disease.
5. Proper ventilation in storage reduces the spread of further development of disease.
6. The crops should be free from Insects and other pests; thus, creation of new wounds and disease can be avoided.
7. Hot water and hot air treatment help to reduce further spread of the disease.
8. Chemical control. Post-harvest diseases may be controlled by the application of thiabendazole, dichloran, etc. These chemicals help to prevent infection and suppress the development of pathogen on the host surface. Some other chemicals, such as vapours of acetaldehyde, biphenyle/nitrogen chloride forming chemicals etc., are used as supplementary measures to control the post-harvest diseases during storage and transportation.

- **16.3 Post-Harvest pests of crops**

- i) Grain storage pests: Rodents, Birds and Insects,
- ii) Common methods of controlling pests of stored produce

16.3.1 Insect pests of stored grains

I. Maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*)– Family: Curculionidae

Main Hosts: Maize and rice in storage and in the field.

Alternative hosts: Sorghum and other cereals in storage.

Geographical Distribution: This species and *S. oryzae* are virtually cosmopolitan throughout the warmer parts of the world, extending as far as Japan and southern Europe.

Significance:

- These are serious major (or primary) pests of stored grain throughout the warmer parts of the world.
- Infestation usually starts in the field and is later transferred into the grain stores during harvest where they continue to reproduce and damage the grains.

Life History:

- Eggs are white and oval.
- The female lays the eggs inside the grain after chewing a minute hole in which she deposits her eggs, then seals the hole with a secretion.
- The eggs hatch into tiny grubs which stay and feed inside the grain and are responsible for most of the damage.
- The mature larvae are plump, legless and dirty white, about 4mm long with a characteristic curved appearance.
- Pupation takes place inside the grain.
- The pupa is white, later turning to a dark brown.
- The adult beetle emerges by biting a circular “exit hole” through the outer layers of the grain.
- They are small brown weevils, about 3.5 – 4mm long with large conspicuous rostrum and thorax.
- The elytra are uniformly dark brown.
- Each female can lay about 300-400 eggs.
- The adults can live for up to 5 months and are capable fliers.
- The total life cycle takes about five weeks at 30⁰ C and 70% RH, but optimum conditions for development are 27-31⁰ C and more than 60% RH.

Control:

- In order to achieve successful control of *Sitophilus zeamais* and other stored products pests, a combined approach involving several aspects of

cultural control and pesticide treatments should be carried out simultaneously.

- Cultural control programmes such as use of sound buildings, use of sealable containers, store hygiene and use of resistant maize varieties are effective.
- Pesticide treatment which involves the use of insecticides include 2% malathion either as emulsifiable concentrate (e.c.) or dust, 1% fenitrothion, permethrin at 100mg a.i./m² (as wettable powders (w.p.)) or pirimiphos-methyl dust at 10-12 parts per million (p.p.m.) (250-500 mg a.i./m² for surface treatment).

2. Rice weevil (*Sitophilus oryzae*)-Family: Curculionidae

Main hosts: Rice, wheat, barley, occasionally peas

Alternative hosts: Raw processed cereals such as pasta

Geographical distribution: Prefers tropical or subtropical environment but can survive temperate regions in protected situations

Damage:

- Adults feed on whole seeds or flour.
- Larvae develop in seeds or pieces of seeds or cereal products large enough to house larvae but will not develop in flour unless it has been compacted.
- Feeding contributes to heating and infested grain is often damp due to moisture added by the insects' respiration.

Life history:

- Females generally lay eggs within a kernel but they may lay multiple eggs per kernel and more than one (1) larvae can develop within a single kernel.
- Larvae are white, legless grubs that develop within the kernel and will not be detected in sieve samples or Berlese funnel samples.
- Adults make a small, circular emergence hole, compared to large, oblong emergence hole made by the granary weevil.
- Adult is small (2.5 to 4 mm), dark brown with 4 distinct reddish to reddish yellow patches on the elytra. Adults are able to fly.
- Adults live 4 to 5 months. Adult is identical in external appearance to the maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*); dissection is required to distinguish between the species.

Control: Same as in *S. oryzae*

3. Larger grain borer (*Prostephanus truncatus*) -Family: Bostrichidae

Main Hosts: Maize

Alternative hosts: Sorghum and other cereals in storage, dried root crops, bamboo, rattan, cassava, dried sweet potato

Geographical Distribution: Throughout the tropics and other warmer parts of the world

Damage:

- Damage is distinctive and heavy.
- Adults burrow extensively leaving tunnels and irregular shaped holes. Feeding produces large quantities of flour.
- Larval feeding and burrowing contribute further to adult damage. Copious amounts of flour are produced.

Life history:

- Females lay eggs singly or in batches in or near food.
- Newly hatched larvae bore into grains or feed on damaged grain and flour produced by adult feeding.
- Larvae can successfully develop within a single seed. Adults are black or brown and cylindrical in shape, heads face down.
- Adults are slightly larger (3 to 4 mm) than the lesser grain borer.
- Posterior end of the elytra slopes back with two strong lateral ridges with sharp edged corners.
- Larvae are grub-like with poorly formed legs and are less mobile as they mature.

Control: Same as in *S. zeamais*

4. Lesser grain borer (*Rhizopertha dominica*) - Family: Bostrychidae

Main hosts: Nearly all grains, especially wheat, barley, sorghum and rice

Alternative hosts: Seeds, dried fruit, drugs, cork, wood and paper products

Geographical distribution: Found worldwide both in tropical and warm temperate countries

Pest status: A very serious pest of stored cereal grains in warmer parts of the world.

Damage:

- Damage is distinctive and heavy.
- Adults and larvae feed on germ and endosperm usually in a rather haphazard manner, reducing kernels to shells of bran.

Life history:

- Lesser grain borer is one of the most injurious pests known to attack grain.
- Adults are mobile, able to fly and are long-lived.
- Females lay eggs one at a time or in batches of up to 30 eggs.

- Larvae live within the seed and are rarely found in sieve samples. Larvae pupate within grain kernel.
- The insect is capable of developing on food of very low moisture content.
- Adults are dark reddish brown and 3 mm long with distinctly shaped, loose 3-segmented club.
- Larvae are white and c-shaped. They are immobile at maturity with dark head capsule.
- The life cycle can be completed in about 30 days at 34 °C under warm conditions breeding is usually continuous.

Control: Pirimiphos-methyl is particularly effective against this pest, and the pyrethroids are also widely used.

5. Indian meal moth (*Plodia interpunctella*) – Family: Pyralidae

Hosts: Mostly meals and flours, but also some dried fruits, nuts, pulses and cereals

Geographical distribution: Cosmopolitan through the tropics and warmer temperate regions.

Pest status: A serious pest of stored products (mostly foodstuffs) throughout the tropics

Damage:

- Larval feeding produces large cavities within infested grain.
- With most infestations of grains, the destruction of the germinal parts is the most serious damage; with foodstuffs contamination harms the food quality.

Life history:

- The eggs are stuck on to the substrate; each female laying 200-400 eggs; hatching takes 4-6 days.
- The larvae are small pale caterpillars that grow rapidly reaching 8-10 mm in about 12-20 days, according to temperature and humidity.
- The adult is of distinctive appearance with the distal parts of the forewings coppery-red and basal parts cream; body length about 6-7 mm and wing span of 14-16 mm.
- In the tropics, there may be up to 8 generations per year.
- Under optimum conditions the life cycle can be as short as 24-30 days.

Control: Cultural control measures are effective against this pest. Chemical control is same as in *S. zeamais*.

6. Khapra beetle (*Trogoderma granarium*) - Family: Dermestidae

Main host: Cereal grains, groundnuts, maltings, spices and dried vegetable seeds

Geographical distribution: Thrives in hot, dry climates

Pest status: A very serious pest of stored grains throughout the warmer parts of the world and is one of the most serious grain pests in the world.

Damage:

- Larvae initially feed on damaged grain pieces.
- As larvae mature, they are able to attack whole grains.
- Larvae may completely destroy commodity.
- Initial discoveries are often based on the presence of accumulations of cast larval skins.
- This pest can practice facultative diapauses in the absence of food, for a year or longer.

Life history:

- Females lay eggs amongst the commodity.
- Larvae may enter diapause (dormant state) and remain inactive for up to 8 years if conditions are unfavourable.
- Diapause may be initiated by cooler temperature, poor food quality or low population densities.
- Larvae moult multiple times and duration of life cycle depends on conditions.
- If conditions are favorable, life cycle is shorter in duration with fewer molts. Adults are about 3-4 mm in length and wingless.
- They cannot fly, do not feed and only live for about 14 days.
- Beetle only has competitive advantage in hot dry grain where other more prevalent species do not have the advantage they have when humidity is normal.

Control: As in *S. oryzae*

7. Grain beetles (*Oryzaephilus surinamensis* and *S. mercator*) - Family: Silvanidae

Main host: Stored grains and most other types of stored plant and animal products, oats (beetle is most often found here), wheat, barley, animal feed, flax, sunflower, milled and processed products, dried fruit and packaged foods

Geographical distribution: Both species are cosmopolitan in tropical areas and occur in heated buildings in the cooler parts of the world.

Pest status: Widespread and abundant stored product pests, but secondary in nature, usually associated with *Sitophilus* infestations of grain.

Damage:

- General feeders, with diet consisting of fragments and debris.
- *O. surinamensis* is more usually associated with cereal products,
- *O. Mercator* with oil-seed products.

- Severe infestations can cause grain to become overheated contributing to further damage.

Life history:

- Eggs are laid among the produce and hatching requires 4-12 days.
- Larvae are white to pale yellow and flattened.
- They are free-living and only spend part of their time inside the grains.
- When inside the grains they show preference for the germ region.
- The larvae prefer higher humidities for development, 60-90 % relative humidity, which takes 12-20 days.
- Pupation occurs either freely or within a cocoon consisting of particles of grain and this takes about 5-15 days
- Adults are small, brown, slender beetles, about 3 mm in length with serrated sides on pronotum.

Control: Neither species is able to breed at temperatures less than 19 °C. General control strategy same as in *S. zeamais*

8. Cowpea Bruchid (*Callosobruchus maculatus*) - Family: Bruchidae

Main Host: Cowpea

Alternative Hosts: Soybean, pigeon pea, green gram, Dolichos, chickpea and other pulses.

Geographical Distribution: This pest and its related species are cosmopolitan throughout most of the tropics and sub-tropics.

Significance:

- These are important pests of various pulse crops in Africa, India, the middle and Far East, both in the field crops and in stores.
- The larvae bore into the pea or bean.
- Infestations usually originate from farm stores but the adult beetles can fly for up to about half a mile, and so field crops within about this distance down-wind of the farm stores are likely to be infested by the adults.
- The infested pods are then harvested and taken into the farm stores where further development takes place.

Life History:

- Eggs are laid, stuck on to the outside of the pods, by the female beetle.
- Each female lays up to 90 eggs.
- If the pods have dehisced, eggs are laid directly onto the seeds.
- Hatching takes about six days. The larvae spend their entire life within the pea or bean.
- On hatching, the larva is scarabaeiform and the larval period is about 20 days.
- Pupating takes place in a chamber just under the testa of the seed.

- This stage is called the window stage and pupation takes about seven days to complete.
- The adults are small brownish beetles, with characteristically emarginated eyes along the inner edges, where the antennae are inserted.
- They are about 3mm in length.
- The whole life cycle takes about 4 – 5 weeks, and about 6-7 generations are common in many countries.

Control:

- Cultural control such as store hygiene, use of sealable containers and sound building can be effective in growing vulnerable crops at least half a mile distant from farm crop stores which are the primary source of infestation.
- Prompt harvesting in areas at risk will also reduce attack levels.
- Fumigation with methyl bromide or Aluminum phosphide (phostoxin) is effective.
- Other effective pesticides include malathion 2% either as e.c. or dust, permethrin at 100mg a.i./m² (as w.p.) etc.

16.3.2 Rodents Damage and their Control (Rats and Mice)

Identification of rodents

Three species of urban rodents, *Mus musculus* (house mouse), *Rattus norvegicus* (Norway rat) and *Rattusrattus* (roof rat) create the principal rodent problems.

1. House mouse

- ✓ The most common household rodent is the house mouse, which resembles the roofrat in that they both have **large ears, pointed muzzles and slender bodies.**
- ✓ The house mouse is a small, slender, dusky-gray rodent with a slightly pointed nose; small, black, protruding eyes; and large, scantily haired ears.
- ✓ Adults weigh 0.5 to 0.8 grams and are 2½ to 3½ inches long in head-and-body length
- ✓ The hairless tail is 3 to 4 inches long. The faeces are about ¼ inch long and are rod-shaped.
- ✓ These wild populations often move into buildings when weather becomes severe. House mice have poor vision and are color-blind.
- ✓ Mice use their sense of smell to locate food items and recognize other individual mice.

Damage symptoms

- ✓ House mice are considered among the most troublesome and economically important rodents.
- ✓ Although house mice are commonly found living in man-made structures, they are also well adapted to **living outdoors**, being common inhabitants of **grassy fields and cultivated grain crops**.
- ✓ House mice feed on a wide range of foods, although they seem to prefer cereals over other items.
- ✓ In particular, most mice favor the germ of grains. As supplemental diet items, mice often show preference for foods high in fat and protein, such as lard, butter, nuts and dried meats.

2. Rats.

Identification

Two types of urban rats are broadly distributed, the Norway rat and the roof rat.

- i) **The Norway rat** (synonymous with brown, dump, barn, sewer, gray or wharf rat)
 - ✓ It's a burrowing rodent.
 - ✓ The Norway rat has a blunt muzzle, small eyes and short, close-set ears. Its fur is coarse and usually brownish or reddish-gray, with whitish-gray hair on the belly.
 - ✓ Its **nearly naked**, scaly tail is dark on the top and light on the underside and is shorter (6 to 8½ inches) than the combined length of the head and body (7 to 10 inches).
 - ✓ Adults weigh 340 to 510 grams. The faeces are capsule-shaped and about ¾ inch long.

Damage symptoms

- ✓ Norway rats can be found in warehouses, farm buildings, houses, sewers, rubbish dumps, wood piles and building foundations.
 - ✓ They are good climbers and can reach a distance of 13 inches while standing on the ground and jump 24 inches vertically.
 - ✓ Norway rats are mainly nocturnal, but they may be active in undisturbed places during the day. They feed on virtually anything edible.
- ii) **The roof rat** (black or ship rat)
 - ✓ It's somewhat smaller and is a more **agile climber**. It has several color phases, a **slender body**, prominent ears and **large eyes**.
 - ✓ The unicolored, nearly hairless tail (7½ to 10 inches) is usually longer than the head and body combined (6½ to 8 inches).
 - ✓ The adult weighs 226 to 340 grams, and the faeces differ from those of the Norway rat in that they are about ½ inch long and spindle-shaped.

Detection of rodents

- ✓ To determining population levels of these rodents, some of these signs are burrows, gnawing activity, faecal droppings, runways, rub marks, tracks and carcasses.
- ✓ Reproduction, mortality and movement into and out of an area determine the potential size of rodent populations.
- ✓ whereas physical environment, food, shelter, water, predation, parasitism and competition control the actual population size.
- ✓ **Urine:** House mice urinate at intervals along well-used runways, occasionally creating small mounds (urinating pillars) that consist of a combination of grease, urine and dirt that fluoresces under ultraviolet (black) light.
- ✓ **Smudges or rub marks:** Dirt and oil from the fur of the rodent may sometimes leave smudge marks on pipes and beams. Smudge marks left by rats are much more conspicuous than those produced by house mice.
- ✓ **Gnawing marks:** Sawdust-like wood chips are produced by the gnawing of house mice and rats around baseboards, doors, windows and frames, and kitchen cabinets. Recent gnawing on wood is light in color, darkening with age. The size of the tooth marks left in the wood can help distinguish the presence of rats or mice.
- ✓ **Droppings:** The age of the droppings indicates whether the infestation is current. Old droppings are dry, gray and crumble easily when pressed. Fresh droppings are dark and moist. Droppings are most numerous along runways, near burrow entrances and at feeding sites.
- ✓ **Pet excitement:** Pawing and excitement of cats and dogs can indicate the presence of rodents. Pets respond most commonly when the premises have been invaded only recently.
- ✓ **Odour:** Rodents produce characteristic odours. With experience, the musky scent of house mice can be differentiated from those produced by rats.
- ✓ **Runways:** Rats and mice are creatures of habit and will travel the same pathways between their shelter, food and water sources. Outside these appear as packed earth paths; they are also evident in dense vegetation. Indoors, runways are usually along walls, under boards, behind stored objects and similar places.
- ✓ **Tracks:** Fresh tracks are distinct, old ones faint. Tracks are more easily seen by side illumination with a flashlight than by direct light from above. Tail drags, as well as footprints, may show up. A smooth patch of flour or talc laid down in a runway may show activity

Prevention of Infestation by Rodents

- i) Drying platform

- ii) Environmental factors
- iii) Sanitation
- iv) Exclusion

Rodents Control

When rodents are found harboring a place, one or combinations of the following control measures should be employed in order to control them:

- i) **Trapping:** such as Trigger traps, cage traps, Ketch-All
- ii) **Glue boards:** catch and hold mice and rats trying to cross them
- iii) **Noise and electrical devices**
- iv) **Bait selection and placement**
- v) **Tracking powders**
- vi) **Fumigants**
- vii) **Rodent competition**
- viii) **Rodenticides:** such as Cholecalciferol (Vitamin D3), Bromethalin and Zinc phosphide

Safety precautions on the use of rodenticide:

Certain general **safety precautions** should be followed besides those appearing on the labels of products.

- ✓ Consider all rodenticides dangerous, and place baits where only rodents can get them. There are no known rodenticides that don't present some degree of hazard to animals other than rodents.
- ✓ People who formulate rodent baits for their own use should use extreme care in handling the materials and wear rubber gloves, an apron and a proper respirator.
- ✓ **Wash hand thoroughly** after preparing baits, **using soap**, a brush and plenty of water.
- ✓ **Clean bait-mixing utensils** thoroughly, and use them only for bait preparation. Whenever possible, it is best to buy prepared or ready-to-use baits to reduce risks involved in handling concentrated toxicants.
- ✓ **Label all bait** containers and stations clearly with appropriate warnings. Store unused baits and concentrates in a locked cabinet, out of reach of children or animals. Follow the label directions on all rodenticide products carefully.
- ✓ Pick up dead rats and mice after a poisoning program. Handle the carcasses with tongs or rubber gloves. Especially in Hantavirus areas, spray rodent carcasses and traps with disinfectant and place the rodents in a plastic bag for disposal.
- ✓ Dispose of large numbers of rats and mice by incineration or burial. With only a few, especially mice, place them in a plastic bag, close it tightly and dispose of it with other refuse. Remove and destroy all uneaten bait at the end of the poisoning period.

- ✓ Do not leave single-dose baits exposed for more than three or four days.

16.3.3 BATS

Introduction

Bats are mammals of the order Chiroptera with their forelimbs adapted as wings, they are the only mammals naturally capable of true and sustained flight. Bats are manurable than birds flying with their very long spread out digits covered with a thin membrane.

Physical identification features

- ✓ They have very long tongue that they use for eating, drinking and pollination
- ✓ They have a small dot nose
- ✓ They have very short legs
- ✓ Bats have tiny teeth that are razor sharp
- ✓ Bats have long arms and hands with long fingers
- ✓ They have large, pointed ears and gray or brown fur
- ✓ The largest ones have a wingspan up to 1.5m, others are 15cm wide
- ✓ Their wings are much thinner and consist of more bones than the wing of birds

Sign of their detection

- ✓ Flying two and fro in our homes
- ✓ Oily steaks around certain parts in our homes
- ✓ Their guano (bat droppings) around home
- ✓ Hearing their sound in attic
- ✓ Pungent odour (ammonia type odour) in an attic
- ✓ Seeing their dead bodies in an around our property
- ✓ Seeing piles of black droppings on our attic insulation
- ✓ Seeing stain on the ceiling

Preventive measures against bats

- ✓ Ensure all doors to the outside are close tightly
- ✓ Swapping outdoor light bulbs with yellow ones which attract fewer bugs that are primary source of food to the bats
- ✓ Use of window screens, chimney caps and draft guards beneath door to sticks
- ✓ Check where the fascias meet the roof caulk any opening s larger than a quarter inch by a half inch
- ✓ Check any loose or broken tiles on the roof
- ✓ Check the chimney
- ✓ Ensure that there are no vents open or with holes to allow entrance
- ✓ Always check soffits

- ✓ Seal up all secondary exist holes and install one-way exclusion devices on the main exist areas
- ✓ Watch the hose and identify all bats entry

Control measures against bats

- ✓ Introduction of natural enemies such as owl near the bats rooting place
- ✓ Use of moth balls: they are naphthalene balls that use to repel bats in a place
- ✓ Use of water spray: spray water on the nest of the bat when they are sleeping
- ✓ Use of phenol repellent: this repels the bats; it makes the place very unpleasant and unbearable for them to reside
- ✓ Hanging of aluminum foil: it should be hang in a place where they are as this will reflect light and keep irritating and annoying them
- ✓ Use of christmas decoration: the shinning and the moving object of a of christmas décor tree will scare the bats and they will be very frightened to come back again
- ✓ Bat roofing: it is used to block the entry of bats and never see them.

16.3.4 Agricultural Bird Pests

Quelea Birds (*Quelea quelea*)

Description

- ✓ The red-billed quelea is a small sparrow-like bird, approximately 12 cm (4.7 in) long.
- ✓ Weight about 15–26 g (0.53–0.92 oz), with a heavy, cone-shaped bill, which is red (in females outside the breeding season and males) or orange to yellow (females during the breeding season).
- ✓ Males have a black facial "mask", comprising a black forehead, cheeks, lores and higher parts of the throat.
- ✓ Occasionally males have a white mask.
- ✓ The mask is surrounded by a variable band of yellow, rusty, pink or purple.
- ✓ White masks are sometimes bordered by black. This coloring may only reach the lower throat or extend along the belly, with the rest of the underparts light brown or whitish with some dark stripes.
- ✓ The tail and upper wing are dark brown.
- ✓ The flight feathers are edged greenish or yellow.
- ✓ The eye has a narrow naked red ring and a brown iris.
- ✓ The legs are orangey in color.
- ✓ The bill is bright raspberry red.

Signs of their detection

- ✓ Their presence can be detected by their feathers which fall on the ground.
- ✓ Also, they can be detected by opening of holes.
- ✓ They can be detected by their noisy sound.

Prevention

- ✓ In rice field a fishing net can be applied on top to prevent destruction of paddy rice.
- ✓ Use of frightening device to chase them away from crop field.

Control

Their wide range, enormous population and fecundity make control of quelea difficult. To date, measures to control quelea birds have included the use of Chemical Control, Mechanical Control, Cultural Control and Biological Control.

i) Chemical Control:

- ✓ Avicides can be used to kill queler bird.
- ✓ Bird repellents

ii) Mechanical Control:

- ✓ Explosions/fire-bombs: Fire bombs can be used in wet land to control.
- ✓ Nest destruction and chick harvesting
- ✓ Trapping: such as Chad Traps, Kondoa basket traps, Kondoa basket traps made of wire mesh, Funnel traps, Miscellaneous indigenous trapping methods, Mist nets, Roost traps

iii) Cultural Control:

- ✓ Planting and harvest time manipulation,
- ✓ Weeding,
- ✓ Alternative Crops,
- ✓ Quelea resistant crops,
- ✓ protecting crops with netting,
- ✓ Trap roosts, scaring by humans,
- ✓ Scaring with falcons and
- ✓ Commercial bird-scaring devices

iv) Biological control

• 16.4 AFLATOXIN CONTAMINATION IN CROPS

16.4.1 AFLOTOXIN CONTAMINATION

Molds are spread by spores which often cannot be seen by the human eye. They are in the soil, on plants, in the air, left on old bags, or in poor storage spaces. When these spores fall onto moist grains, under warm, humid conditions, they start growing. As these fungi grow, they release poisons called

mycotoxins. There are over 500 types of mycotoxins, but the most important in maize are produced by *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Penicillium* species. These fungi species occur naturally in the soil. The most dangerous mycotoxin, aflatoxin – which can cause death or long-term health problems in both humans and animals – cannot be seen by the human eye, and only special tests will show its presence. Important control mechanisms include post harvest handling, storage and biological control technologies which work to prevent the production of mycotoxins. Once aflatoxin is produced on or in the grain it is not destroyed by cooking or heating the grain. The only way to prevent these fungi/molds from growing and spreading is to dry the grain quickly at harvest to moisture levels of less than 16.5% and to keep the grain in clean bags, in dry conditions and off the ground of the storage space. Aflatoxins have been found in all grains; however they are more prevalent in grains such as maize and ground nuts.

16.4.2 Aflatoxins: Health and Economic Challenges

In 2004, several hundred Kenyans became severely ill, and 125 died, of acute aflatoxicosis. Greater global public attention drawn to aflatoxin and associated health risks. People continue to suffer from chronic levels of aflatoxin consumption. Over 5 billion people in developing countries (including Nigeria) remain exposed to aflatoxins through contaminated foods. Groundnuts and maize are the main sources of human exposure to aflatoxin.

Health Challenges:

Acute exposure to Aflatoxins (extremely high doses of aflatoxin) lead to the following conditions:

1. Haemorrhage (excessive bleeding),
2. Vomiting,
3. Abdominal pain,
4. Acute liver damage (liver necrosis),
5. Pulmonary edema, and Death in humans: There have been several reported cases of acute aflatoxicosis in Africa due chronic exposure to Aflatoxins.
6. Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) as a result of chronic aflatoxin exposure has been well documented, presenting most often in persons with chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection. For individuals chronically infected with HBV, aflatoxin consumption raises the risk of liver cancer up to thirty-fold, compared with either exposure alone.

Other consequences of chronic exposure include:

1. Decreased immune and reproductive function; Children chronically exposed may experience stunted growth. Infants may be exposed through breast milk. The fetus may be exposed during pregnancy if the mother consumes aflatoxins

2. Economic impacts/damages due to consumption of aflatoxin contaminated food by humans come from health impacts of aflatoxin toxicity. The estimated damages to human health were also valued Viz: Disability Adjusted Life Year (DALY) lost, Monetised Health Impact. At the national level, aflatoxin contamination in maize and groundnuts was estimated to be 7,761 liver cancer cases resulting in a total burden of 100,965 DALYs (Number of healthy life years lost due to death or disability caused by disease). At a prevalence rate of 20 µg/kg, the monetised burden of aflatoxin contamination was between \$112 and \$942 million (2010 Us dollars) which was about 0.5 % of Nigeria GDP.

Economic Impact of Aflatoxin

1. A Reduction in marketable volume,
2. Loss in value in the national markets,
3. Inadmissibility or rejection of products by the international market, and
4. Losses incurred from livestock disease, consequential morbidity and mortality.

16.4.3 ENVIRONMENTS THAT ENCOURAGE AFLATOXIN DEVELOPMENT

For these fungi and molds to grow, they require the following environment:

1. Moisture content of 14-30% in grains
2. Temperature range of 10-40 degrees Celcius.
3. Relative humidity above 70%
4. Unclean environment
5. Prolonged rains after crop has matured preventing harvest
6. Periods of drought stress while the plant has been growing

16.4.4 KEY STEPS THAT PREVENT AFLATOXIN

1. To avoid the growth of the fungi and molds which produce mycotoxins, dry your grain quickly at harvest and very well before storage, and keep it in a dry and clean and well ventilated storage area.
2. Avoid insect and rodent damage which can open up the grain by offering easy access to grain by fungus and mold.
3. Avoid contact of the grain with the soil.

4. Do not add water to the grain to add weight before the sale.
5. Handle the grain carefully when harvesting and moving.
6. Store grains in clean sacs on pallets.
7. Ensure sacks are in good condition, are full and well closed so grain does not fall out and it is more difficult for rodents to get in.
8. Ensure that no grain is left on the ground in the store.

SECTION V: VALUE ADDITION TO AGRICULTURAL COMMODITIES

MODULE 17: VALUE ADDING ACTIVITIES AND CUSTOMER VALUE

• 17.1 Objectives

1. Understand value adding activities
2. Understand customer value and how to create value
3. Identify value chain activities and how to add value in agricultural commodity value chain
4. Differentiate traditional value addition and emerging aspects of value addition

17.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

17.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

17.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

17.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts

- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

17.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

Participants will be evaluated before and after the training exercise.

17.2 Adding Value to Agricultural Commodities.

17.2.1 Introduction

Value-added agriculture is an important strategy to both agricultural entrepreneurship, rural development, federal and state programs support entrepreneurs' and communities' value-added agriculture efforts. Agricultural producers receive a much smaller portion of the consumer's income compared with food processors, especially processors who produce brand name items. Capturing those additional income by adding value to farm or livestock products is a goal of many producers. This module defines value-added activities, outlines the economic forces that make adding value important, and provides guidelines for starting your own business.

17.2.2 What is Value Addition and how is Value Added?

Value Addition: This is the addition of time, place, and or form utility (satisfaction) to a commodity in order to meet the tastes or preferences of consumers.

Value added means adding value to a raw agricultural commodity by taking it to at least the next stage of the value chain. This can be as simple as retaining ownership of your ruminants and fattening them on green pasture or placing them in a feedlot. Value can be added through sorting, grading and packaging grains or it may be as elaborate as going all the way to the consumer with a "branded and ready to consume" food product (e.g maize flour).

How is Value Added to Agricultural Commodities: Simply, figure out what consumers want, when they want it, and where they want it and then make it and provide it to them.

Benefits of Value Addition: Value addition provides substantial benefits which include:

- Increase ability to capture a percentage of the farm-to-retail price spread,
- Minimize post-harvest losses by enhancing/increasing the shelf-life of many perishable agricultural commodities,
- Capture premium price thereby improving income/livelihoods
- Ensure availability of agricultural commodities over space and time dimensions.
- Increase consumer satisfaction by providing products in the form, place and time desired.

If you are considering a value-added enterprise, there are two key questions to answer:

- What is customer value?
- What creates a value-added product?

17.2.3 Customer Value

Customer value reflects the relationship between the benefits customers receive from consumption of a product and the price they pay for that product. The more benefits relative to the price, the higher the customer value. This does not necessarily mean that greater value results from a low price. The price of a particular product may be high, but if the associated benefits are high as well, the customers perceive the product as valuable. This interaction creates customer value and, thus, the opportunity to add value to your product.

Creating customer value is critical in building a profitable and substantial business. However, one must bear in mind that it is the customers' perception of value, not the producers', that is critical. It is also important to recognize that different customers have different perceptions of added value. These perceptions correspond to their expectations of quality, service, convenience and selection.

17.2.4 What Add Value to Agricultural Commodities

Value is usually added by focusing on the benefits associated with the agribusiness product or service that arise from:

- a. Quality:** Does the product or service meet or exceed customer expectations?
- b. Packaging:** Is the package appealing, informative, protective and of required size?
- c. Functionality:** Does the product or service provide the function needed of it?

- d. Form:** Is the product in a useful form?
- e. Place:** Is the product in the right place?
- f. Time:** Is the product in the right place at the right time?
- g. Ease of possession:** Is the product easy for the customer to obtain?
- h. Affordability:** Is the product affordable to the targeted consumer?

A product must have one or more of these qualities to generate additional value. Remember that a product is simply a bundle of benefits, and that the more benefits there are the more customers will perceive the product as having value.

17. 2. 5 Creating a Value-Added Product

To take advantage of opportunities in this area, one must know and understand customers.

What consumer segments might want your product?
Buyer of smaller quantities: As in the case of rice consumers buying 2.5Kg (one <i>Tiya/Mudu</i>) at regular intervals.
Buyer of relatively larger quantities: As in the case of rice consumers buying 25Kg 50Kg bags periodically.
Segment of consumers willing to pay the price for destoned, polished and branded parboiled rice
Segment of consumers in Low, medium, high income class?
What are the benefits/Criteria for product selection by these potential customers?
Quality: Meeting the customer expectations
Packaging: Package which is appealing, informative, protective and in the desired size
Functionality: Meeting the desire/needs of the consumer/customer
Form: Fresh, Processed, clean,
Place: Availability at the required place e.g. retail outlet within community.....
Time: Availability at the time needed (control over seasonality of agricultural commodities)
Ease of possession: Easily accessible

Any business enterprise can be thought of as a value chain. Each activity that is performed should add value to the product. To do this, one must control the activities at each step in the value chain: procurement of inputs; converting inputs into products; marketing and sales; supply chain logistics; and customer service activities.

- **17.3 Agricultural Commodity Value Chain**

The general value chain is “the complete range of activities and services required to put a product or a service from its design up to its sale on the final markets - local, national, regional or international”.

Value chains in agriculture may be considered as a series of procedures and flows ranging “from the field to the table” - from production to the consumer. The basic goal sought in the value chain is competitiveness, while ensuring a better return on investments at all levels. The market ensures the quality and quantity control of products and services.

A value chain links the steps a product takes from the farmer to the consumer. It includes farmer, processors, marketers and consumers. The farmer combines resources (land, labor and capital and skills) to produce commodities (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Local Agricultural Commodity Value Chain

In an agricultural commodity value chain, farmers are linked to the needs of consumers, working closely with suppliers and processors to produce the specific goods required by consumers (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Possible Value Addition Options for Farmers

A new value-added business should focus on the product’s uniqueness. The uniqueness of your product or service (the value you add) is what ultimately attracts customers. Obviously, this value-added strategy is very different from the commodity-oriented strategy with which most farmers are familiar. In a commodity strategy, a producer focuses on the costs of production with the goal of being a low-cost producer. This is, in essence, a “supply-side” focus

The value-added strategy, in contrast, involves a “demand-side” focus—determining who the customers are and what they want. Then, after assessing your resources and source of uniqueness, you provide a product or service that efficiently reduce production costs while meeting the needs of the potential market. Unlike a commodity-driven business, a value-added business cannot erode benefits or lower input specifications just to lower costs (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Traditional versus value delivery system (Christopher & Ryals 2014)

17.4 Exercises

Exercise I: (This can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objective

- To obtain a clear understanding of the sequence of activities in an agricultural commodity value chain.

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of presentation

Steps 1: What to do:

Prepare the value chain of your product from the supply of input to the retail of the commodity to the end consumers

Step 2: How to do it:

- a. Name the product you are producing or plan to process
- b. Identify the main activities carried out in the value chain from the supply of input to the retail of the commodity to the end consumers.
- c. Identify the operators/actors involved in these activities and what are their roles.
- d. Draw the flow of activities in a “flow chart”
- e. Identify where the commodity originates from and where does it go using the locality coverage.

Exercise 2: (This can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objective

- To obtain a clear understanding of the key actors and relationships involved in an agricultural commodity value chain.

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of presentation

Steps 1: What to do:

Prepare a table to show actors and their activities along the agricultural commodity value chain of your product from the supply of input to the retail of the commodity to the end consumers.

Step 2: How to do it:

Fill-up the information asked in Table 1.

Product.....

Actor	Activities	Product (Output)	Price (NGN)	Value Added
Farmer	Rice paddy production	Rice paddy	NGN200/Kg	Selling Price NGN/Kg – Cost of production (NGN/Kg)

MODULE 18: MARKETING OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCE

- **18.1 Objectives**

1. Define marketing within the context of farm management, agribusiness or entrepreneurship.
2. Develop marketing strategies along product, place, price, and promotion (marketing mix) in farm management, agribusiness or entrepreneurship.

18.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

18.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

18.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

18.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers

- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

18.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

- **18.2 Marketing**

Discussion of marketing concepts in this training module shall revolve around the 4Ps of marketing within the context of agribusiness collectively referred to as the marketing mix.

The 4Ps (Product, Price, Promotion, Place) of marketing are the factors that help a business to sell its product or service.

i. **Product:** Getting the right product (as desired by consumers) to the market. Product planning involves new and existing products. A new product may be a modification, a minor innovation, or a major innovation. After innovation, products are managed from growth to decline. New products offer differential advantages. Creativity/Idea generation is the key to searching for new products opportunities

ii. **Price:** The right price (the price consumers are willing/afford to pay considering the benefits/satisfaction from consumption of the product). Some factors to consider in determining the selling price of the product/service are:

- Cost of production
- Market value of similar and competing products

iii. **Promotion:** Advertising and marketing of the product or service. This is one of the most neglected aspects of marketing a product. Promotion is necessary to encourage and convince buyers to purchase the product and not the competitors. Promotion is generally divided into advertising, sales promotion, and personal selling.

iv. **Place:** The most convenient location for the consumers to buy the product. Location of the business is essential to either reduce cost, increase the chances of customers stopping at the business to look at the products or at least make inquiries. If the business is retail-oriented, it should be near the

market. If it is production-oriented, it may be better to be close to its raw material sources or near infrastructure facilities, transport and utilities centers. Important factors to consider include:

- Proximity to essential raw materials
- Proximity to markets and distribution channels
- Availability of transport facilities
- Availability of efficient and cheap skilled labor
- Existence of related industries
- Infrastructure facilities
- Communication facilities

Marketing of farm products involves activities which facilitate the movement of products from the farm to the ultimate users. It requires good transportation and communication system in order to ensure an efficient transfer of farm products to the consumers. Likewise, processing, warehousing and storage facilities should be adequate to expand the benefits of raw products and stabilize supply of farm goods.

In the traditional view, marketing was confined to activities which involved the physical transfer of goods and services from the producers to the consumers. This concept of marketing however has been replaced by a wider perspective to meet the demands of modern and complex business society. Under the modern setting, exchange does not only involve goods and services but also money, time, attention, energy, devotion, and so on. For agricultural economies in the rural areas, which do not even have the most basic marketing facilities, what is needed is an efficient transportation system for the farm products and understanding market behaviour to take advantage of good prices and reaching out to customers.

• 18.3. Functions of Marketing in Agribusiness

18.3.1 Assembling

These are activities which involve the gathering and consolidating of small quantities of products into larger lots. They begin at the farm until the products reach the consumers. Advantages of assembling include the following:

- Reduces transportation cost
- Economizes the cost of grading
- Helps in product processing
- Facilitates in fulfilling specific orders of customers

18.3.2 Storage

It refers to the keeping of products over a period of time in a warehouse, cold storage plant, or other storage facilities. Its advantages comprise of the following:

- Maintains an adequate supply for processing
- Takes advantage of expected increase in prices
- Preserves the products, especially the perishables
- Improves the quality of certain products such as tobacco etc
- Regulates the flow of supply, thus minimizing price fluctuations

18.3.3 Standardizing and grading

The sorting of products based on kind, quality and size is called grading. The establishment of these grades is standardization. The advantages of grading are the following:

- The need for inspection of the product by buyers is reduced or eliminated.
- The sale of the product by description is made easier.
- Cost of transportation is reduced.
- Appearance of the product is improved and thereby commands a better price

18. 3.4 Transportation.

It is the movement of goods from one place to another. The presence of road and transportation systems facilitates the efficient movement of farm products to the different locations.

18.3.5 Processing.

It is the transformation of a raw product into a more usable form. Products require processing to extend their life span and increase their market value. The advantages of processing are:

- Improves the quality of the product
- Makes the product more usable
- Prevents the contamination of the product
- Prolongs the perishability of the product
- Increases the nutrients of the product
- Provides the manufacture of by-products for consumption
- Transforms some raw products into other products, such as milk into cheese

18.3.6 Packaging.

This is the process of placing goods in bags, containers or wrappers. The advantages are the following:

- For easier handling
- Protects from possible damage
- Reduces storage and transportation cost
- Prevents loss of weight and food value

18.3.7 Retailing.

This is the ultimate selling of products to the final consumers. The advantages are the following:

- Provides consumers with various goods
- Keeps goods which are for immediate delivery
- Makes buying convenient for the consumers

18.4 Factors Considered in Packaging and Branding Decisions

18.4.1 Factors to Consider in Packaging

1. Package design – color, shape and material influence consumer perception about the company and the product. In selecting a package size, shelf life, convenience, and competition must be considered.
2. Package costs – based on a total and per-unit cost (various packaging materials entail different costs: paperboard, plastic, metal, glass, Styrofoam, and cellophane, among others)

18.4.2 Factors to Consider in Branding

An important part of product planning is branding. A brand is a name, design, or symbol that identifies the products of a seller or group of sellers.

Types of brand designation:

- a. Brand name – a word, letter (number), group of words, or letters (numbers) that can be spoken
- b. Brand mark – a symbol, design, or distinctive colouring or lettering
- c. Trademark – a brand name or brand mark that is given legal protection

Importance of Branding

- Product identification is eased
- Customers are assured that a good or service has a certain level of quality
- A company is able to advertise its products in the buyer's mind

- Product prestige is increased as social visibility becomes meaningful

Effective Brand Names

- Suggests something about the product's use, benefit or attributes
- Easy to spell and remember and pronounceable in only one way
- Can be applied to a whole line of product line
- Capable of legal protection from use by others
- Has a pleasant or at least neutral meaning in international markets

Note: After branding and packaging comes the labelling. A label is used to identify, grade, describe and promote a product.

18.5 Product Life Cycle

Stages of Product Life in the Market

1. Introduction Stage: A period of slow sales growth as the product is introduced in the market. Profits are non-existent in this stage because of the heavy expenses incurred with product introduction.

2. Growth Stage: A period of rapid market acceptance and substantial profit improvement.

3. Maturity Stage: A period of slowdown in sales growth because the product has achieved acceptance of most potential buyers. Profits stabilize or decline because of increased marketing outlays to defend the product position.

4. Decline Stage: The period when sales show a downward drift and profits erode.

• 18.6 Basic Steps in Planning the Marketing Process

Marketing processes entails ways in which value can be created for the customers to satisfy their requirements. Basic steps in marketing process are:

1. Situation analysis: Before developing any sort of action plan, decision makers should acquire information on the problems and opportunities imposed by input suppliers, other producers and its consumers. The business

environment should be explored, including such areas as: i) technologies used; ii) cost structures within the industry; iii) regulations and standards affecting the business; as well as, iv) strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise itself.

2. Setting objectives: Based on the situation analysis specific targets need to be established with respect to anticipated future performance of the enterprise.

3. Developing strategies and action plans: To achieve the stated objectives enterprises should formulate and develop short- and long-term strategies.

4. Set up coordination and control mechanisms: These must be designed and implemented to guarantee effective implementation of the strategies and action plans.

• 18.7 Market Intelligence

Market intelligence is the permanent collection, analysis, monitoring, evaluation, storage and distribution of information on markets. It is a continuous process, which focuses on what happens outside the enterprise and provides on-going information about the market.

Information needs to be wide-ranging and diverse. It may include:

- i. Price information concerning raw materials, inputs and output.
- ii. Development of new processes and related inputs
- iii. Investments
- iv. Launch of new products
- v. Information on competitors
- vi. Policies affecting enterprise' competitiveness
- vii. Promotional events.

There are several information sources, which are used by market intelligence agents: Internal company information: sales records, production costs, technical efficiency ratios, customer records, etc.

1. Suppliers, intermediaries and customers. These are excellent sources of information which should not to be left untapped.
2. Secondary information such as the press reviews, radio, television, trade fairs, advertising, official gazettes, newsletters from professional associations and chambers of business and industry.
3. Information on competitors, on prices, product qualities and promotion strategies.
4. National licensing or patent offices and research and development institutions.

• 18.8 Exercises

Exercise I: (This can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objective

- To obtain a clear understanding of the concepts of marketing mix

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of presentation

Steps 1: What to do:

Discuss the 4Ps of marketing in relation to a selected agricultural commodity.

Step 2: How to do it:

Create working groups to discuss the 4Ps of marketing; prepare presentation to showcase understanding of the concepts and its relevance to agribusiness.

MODULE 19: SAVINGS, SAVINGS MOBILIZATION AND RECORD KEEPING

• 19.1 Objectives

1. Explain the various sources and principles of funding for agribusiness, entrepreneurship or farm ownership.
2. Identify possible sources of funds for the business.
3. Internalize the basic elements of fund management
4. Explain record keeping and types in agribusiness
5. Identify risks in business and types of risks

19.1.1 Activities

- Lectures (Power point presentations)
- Discussion
- Video/Practical/Demonstration
- Feedback Presentation
- Case studies/Success Stories

19.1.2 Time Required

3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

19.1.3 Learning Exercises

- Brainstorming
- Group discussion
- Energizers

19.1.4 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop
- Writing-pad, sticky-notes, pens/Information Education Communication materials (IEC)

19.1.5 Pre and Post Training Evaluation

Participants will be evaluated before and after the training.

- **19.2 Savings and Savings Mobilization**

19.2.1 What is saving?

Saving means withholding something (resources) for future use. This simple statement describes two key elements of any saving activity:

- **Discipline and sacrifice:** Withholding something valuable for future use instead of consuming it immediately.
- **Planning for the future:** Saving is all about the future, about anticipating and preparing for possible consumption, expenditures (purchase of production inputs), risks (bad harvest), starting a new business or expanding an existing one.

19.2.2 Concept of Savings

- i. Savings literally mean “not spending all our income on goods and services”.
- ii. It is a sacrifice of current consumption that provides for the accumulation of capital, which in turn, provides additional output that can potentially be used for consumption in the future (Gersovitz, 1988).
- iii. It is the difference between current earnings and consumption; where current earnings are greater than consumption.

- iv. It is also defined as “deferred consumption” or part of income, which is not spent.
- v. It can further be referred as a surplus of production/earnings over consumption, which can be achieved by either reducing consumption or by increasing production/earnings.

19.2.3 Why people save

Everybody can save, even the poor. It is just that the poor have fewer resources to start with, and so can only save in small amounts.

Savings and Savings Mobilization is an old tradition to people all over the world

- “A penny saved is a penny earned” (England)
- “Manny pebbles make a mountain” (Korea)
- “Save now or never” (Mexico)
- “Save today for a better tomorrow” (Zambia)

19.2.4 Benefit of Savings

Saving is a function of income and income is a function of investment. Savings provides independence and allows the saver to plan for the future, as well as to secure investment for enhanced production and growth. The reasons why people save are:

- To prepare for future emergencies or risks (natural disaster, lost of investment,)
- To smooth out variations in income and consumption: Saving during surplus periods to use during difficult periods.
- To educated children.
- To invest in opportunities potentially profitable (purchase a cow, starting a small enterprise, storing grain to resell during high prices season, buy inputs for the coming cropping season etc.).
- To fulfil social and religious obligations (marriage, Pilgrimage).

19.2.5 How People Save

People save in many ways, as individuals or in a group. They may save:

In kind: (save in food grains, like maize or rice, or in livestock, such as cattle, goats, or chickens, and sometimes in other valuable items easily resold for cash at a later date such as land, jewellery)

In cash: Cash is portable, storable and can be exchange for almost anything. Saving in cash is sometimes preferable but it can easily lose its value during high inflation that is why many prefer the mixed strategy of saving in kind and in cash. Saving in cash is either at home or at bank. Each has its advantage.

By giving: People give gifts or offer services not just out of generosity, but also sometimes with the hope of receiving the favour back when needed.

19.2.6 What about borrowing?

On the surface, using someone else's money and then paying it back, later, seems easier than saving. Borrowing does not require any immediate sacrifice. You get the money quickly and don't have to worry about paying it back until later. **But is it really easier than saving?**

- Borrowing can be expensive
- Borrowing can be risky
- Borrowing can be difficult
- Borrowing can be stressful
- Borrowing can bring delays

19.2.7 Savings Mobilization

I
+

Informal Savings Institutions

The major source of increased domestic capital formation is to increase savings. Farmer Associations should prepare activities on domestic savings to improve the capital base of their associations and members to ensure that capital moves into the most productive uses. It is important to stimulate savings among the farmers because of the role which agriculture has to play in economic development.

Informal sources of credit are still much more important than formal sources in Africa, Asia and Middle East. The informal sources of finance consist of individuals and intermediaries such as:

- i. Moneylenders.
- ii. Traders
- iii. Friends and Relations
- iv. Landlords
- v. Adashe or Esusu
- vi. Rotating savings and credit associations
- vii. Cooperative or thrift societies.

Formal Savings Institutions

Financial resources are a very important factor in economic development. Since financial resource mobilization problem is very closely tied up with savings problem, it requires an institutional arrangement which encourages and mobilizes savings on one hand, and which channels mobilized savings into productive investment on the other. Greater dependence on domestic sources

of capital requires a wide range of independent well-organized and adapted financial institutions, which have to mobilize internal resources for the purpose of capital formation. These forms of savings include:

- i. Commercial Banks.
- ii. Development Banks.

19.2.8 Setting up Savings Associations

How can the poor save more?

The poor do save. It may be just a few bags of rice, sorghum or maize, money to pay school fees, but they usually save something. However, they have difficulties in becoming better off since they face a lot of problems. By adopting group saving approaches they can overcome some of these problems.

In setting up an effective saving association one should be guided by the following measures:

- i. Mobilize individuals with like minds or self-help groups with a common objective of advancing their private business and living standard.
- ii. Develop acceptable bye laws that will guide the activities of the association towards progress.
- iii. Register the association with the appropriate institution.
- iv. Conduct regular meetings to discuss matters of common interest.
- v. Ensure the payment of dues as deemed appropriate for the successful running of the association.
- vi. Execute projects approved by the association.

19.2.9 Features of a successful saving group

- Members have common bond.
- Members have clear objectives.
- Members have agreed upon rules to follow.
- Members are honest and work hard to achieve their objectives.
- Members hold regular meetings and participate in discussions and decision –making.
- Members demonstrate leadership.
- Members keep accurate records of their activities and meetings.

19.2.10 Developing Byelaws for Farmers' Savings Association

Byelaws of the association should be comprehensive enough to include the following:

- i. Name of association
- ii. Location of association
- iii. Objectives of the association

- iv. Definition of membership
- v. Rights and duties of members
- vi. Services to be provided by the association
- vii. Governing structure and sub-committee of the association
- viii. Rules governing election of officials and terms of office
- ix. Fixing registration fees and membership dues
- x. Frequency and type of meetings
- xi. Investment and profit-making procedure
- xii. Profit sharing arrangements
- xiii. Withdrawal of membership
- xiv. Amendment of byelaws
- xv. Discipline

19.2.11 Guidelines in Obtaining Farm Credit

1. Know your credit needs. Plan your project well. Consult your loan officer about the credit needs of your project.
2. Prepare your farm plan and budget. This can be done through the help of a production technician. To accomplish a good farm plan and budget, one should keep a complete and accurate record of the resources, income, and expenses. The record should show the performance of the project during the previous years. Also, it will determine if the credit was applied properly.
3. Acquire loan from an authorized bank. It is advisable to get credit from only one bank for simplicity in planning one's credit needs. The bank employs an agricultural technician to assist borrowers on modern concepts and better methods of production.
4. Be honest in providing credit information. Inform the loan officer about the true facts of the project and its financial requirements.
5. Use the credit for the intended project. The loan should be used only in accordance with the approved farm plan and budget. Borrow only the actual cost of the project.
6. Prepare a repayment plan in advance. Before applying for a loan, one has to prepare a repayment plan. Repayments should come from incomes generated by the project such as the sale of crops or livestock. Limit the credit within one's ability to repay the loan.
7. Maintain good savings and repayment habits. Prompt repayment of one's credit enhances one's credit rating. If one saves regularly in the bank, one reduces dependence on credit. This is more economical.

• 19.3 Basic Record Keeping

Record keeping is the systematic compilation of certain types of information. Reliable and accurate records are used to make better decisions affecting the farm. It is important for farmer and enterprise group members to know what actions have been taken or what or how much has been bought, sold or repaid, baseline of each farmer, what was the contribution of each farmer in the group, profit of each farmer according to their respective contribution. If these actions are not recorded, misunderstandings may develop between members. An important building block in group development, therefore, is record-keeping. Like other processes in group formation, the development of record-keeping is a step-by-step process.

Regarding value chain enterprise, it is important to record all incomes and costs as soon as they are incurred. These are then summarized periodically, e.g. weekly, monthly, quarterly or annually. By comparing annual income to annual costs, you can determine whether you have made a profit or a loss over the year. Prices received from buyers every time a sale is made. This will help identify periods during the year when higher prices can be obtained, or buyers who offer a better price.

With this information, farmers can adjust production so that they have more produce available when prices are higher. Yields obtained and total sales (by volume and price) for products in order to enable comparison with previous years and forecasting for future years.

19.3.1 Reasons for Keeping Farm Records

1. Performance evaluation
2. Farm management decisions
3. Institutional requirements (credit purposes)
4. Taxation and insurance purposes
5. Environmental regulations
6. National agricultural and economic planning purposes

19.4 Types of Farm Records

Generally, there are two distinct groups of business records that are used:

1. Production (Physical) Records
2. Business Record

19.4.1 Production Records

Crop production (from input supply → production → harvesting) e.g. yield, labour, equipment ...

Livestock production (from the introduction of a new breed up to maturity) e.g. feed, weaning weight, calves born, pounds of milk produced, weaning weights, death/ loss, breeding, feeding, harvesting, field records

Processing e.g quantity of rice milled, quantity of wheat threshed, quantity of millet ground, amounts of kunu/cheese produced, etc

Inventory Records

- Stock of all assets and liabilities
- all the unused inputs and unsold business outputs
- Miscellaneous (special/supplementary) Records

Examples: certificate of occupancy , soil map, business layout

19.4.2 Business Records

Financial Records

- Income and expenditure, cash flow, budgeting, depreciation records, loan balances and price information, purchases and wages, sales made
- Miscellaneous (special/supplementary) Records eg: tax payment and insurance

- **19.5 Record Keeping System**

Record-keeping can be accomplished through a variety of methods:

- Manual record-keeping method (Note book, pen, design)
- Computerized system (Computer system, Software)

Selecting a record-keeping system should depend on the expected use of the records. A good record keeping system should:

- Provide accurate and necessary information;
- Fit into the farm organization or framework;
- Be available in a form that could aid decision-making

- **19.5.1 Criteria for selecting a Record Keeping System**

- Ease of use
- How well the system closely match one's information needs and management level
- Flexibility of the system
- Ability of the system to use multiple components for an overall record-keeping system
- Understanding the system before starting to use it with records that matter

- **19.6 Business Record Design**

The nature of the design depends on several factors:

- The type of enterprise (Crop or livestock)
- Interest of the farmer/manager

Any design adopted should be **simple, precise and comprehensive**. A typical farm business record is normally presented in **columns**

19.6.1 Samples of Farm Business Records

Crop Record

Types of crop	Date of planting	Quantity of seed planted	Crop Output (bags or kg etc)	Land Size Cultivated (Ha)	Remarks (if any)
Rice	12/06/2019	22Kg	10 bags of 100Kg each	1.2 Ha	Average crop performance

Power Tiller, Machinery and Equipment Records

Date of operation	Type of operation	Type of machinery and equipment used	Total area covered (Hectares)	Time spent (hours)	Cost of service (Naira)

Labour Records

Date of operation	Types of operation	Amount of hired labour used (No.)	Amount of family labour used (No.)	Total amount of labour used	Time spent (Hours)	Wage rate (Naira)	Total cost of hired labour (Naira)	Total value of family labour (Naira)

Harvest Record

Date of harvest	Quantity harvested	Quantity of crop after drying and threshing or milling

Sales Record

Date	Quantity sold (kg)	Price per unit (Naira)	Total sales (Naira)	Quantity given out as gift (kg)	Value of the gift (Naira)

• 19.7 Exercises

Exercise 1: (This can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objective

- To obtain a clear understanding of the farm record types and design

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of presentation

Steps 1: What to do:

Prepare a table to show Crops/livestock production records

Step 2: How to do it:

Prepare (design) record keeping template and fill-up the information.

SECTION VI: NATURAL RESOURCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

MODULE 20: WATER CONSERVATION

- **20.1 Intended Learning Outcome:**

At the end of the module, extension agents should be able apply the different methods of water conservation for sustainable agricultural production.

Definition:

Water conservation is defined as those activities designed to reduce the demand for water, improve the efficiency of its use, and reduce losses and waste.

Aim:

The aim of conservation is to protect water resources and to achieve, at lower costs, the benefits from its use.

- **20.2 Methods of Water Conservation**

Preambles:

- Water is a jewel for arid agriculture farmers.

- Rainfall being the chief source of water for cropping purposes in these areas is precious.
- Arid areas are characterized by very low rainfall (less than 100mm as defined by FAO) high temperature and barren land.
- Even after the rainfall, the rate of evaporation and evapotranspiration from water body structures and plants is high that available water loses at a fast pace.

Water conservation techniques in arid or dry lands include:

20.2.1 Micro or Drip Irrigation

- This is the most effective and efficient way of water conservation technique suitable for arid lands.
- Not only this method helps in water conservation, but it also help in soil conservation.
- In this method, water is delivered to plants from soil surface using a system of tubes that bear small holes and other destructive outlets.
- This method also allows the application of fertilizer by mixing it with irrigation water through Drip irrigation.
- It has been estimated that drip irrigation saves 50-70 percent water as compare to traditional methods of irrigation and also it supplements more crop production by 20-90 percent due to direct availability of fertilizer to plants.

Drip Irrigation in Arid Agriculture

20.2.2 Zai Pits

- Zai is a term that farmers in northern Burkina Faso use to refer to small planting pits that typically measure 20-30 cm in width, are 10-20 cm deep and spaced 60-80 cm apart.

Plate I: Zai Planting Pits

- Zai is an efficient method of water conservation in arid agriculture systems.
- These planting pits are made around the plants and trees to conserve water and moisture.
- The pits are prepared with hands.
- The excavated soil generated during digging is used to make small ridges around the pits.
- This helps in capturing maximum rain water.
- Usually these are 10 inches deep and wide and 3 feet apart (25cm x 25cm holes one meter apart).
- The objective is to trap rain water to increase moisture around the plant. It also aids in increasing soil fertility especially in dry land or arid regions where occurrence of crusty and degraded soil is common.
- These pits are then planted with a mixture of crop residues, compost, animal manure and seeds.
- These are then covered with mulch made of leaves or grass to conserve moisture.
- This simple looking technique can increase the agriculture produce by 50 percent within three years of practice.

Plate 2: Millet grown in Zai Pits

20.2.3. Ripper-Furrow Planting System

- This technique is famous in Africa where water is scarce and agriculture suffers.
- Farmers are using this technique by employing Ripper-Furrower to rip 2 feet deep and form furrows.
- The function of this structure is to harvest rain water to sustain agriculture.
- Tractors are used during the first year to start this system.
- However, in next years, farmer crops directly into the rips lines using direct seeder powered by animal.
- The seed are then planted in the rips along-with the compost or fertilizer.
- With the occurrence of rainfall, water is funneled by the furrows and reaches to crop roots.
- This technique gives best output for drought tolerant varieties of sorghum, maize and millet.
- Crop rotation with legume cropping is encouraged while following this system.

Ripper-Furrow Planting System

20.2.4. Subsurface Irrigation Systems

- It is an expensive system to setup; however, the returns in the long run are good.
- It is suitable for arid agriculture lands. In this system; water is supplied directly to the roots of plants.
- The advantage is water saving, zero nutrients loss as runoff, chances of weeds are less as they will not get desired water and nutrients, increased crop yield and production, zero surface evapo-transpiration, labor expense is saved, uniformity in application of water and nutrients and is most suitable for those agriculture areas where winds are frequent.

Subsurface Irrigation System

- The cost of initial installment is high.
- On the other hand leaking and clogging are some issues common in this system.
- If the system is installed with the help of professionals of the field, then these issues can be minimized.
- Its life is more than 15 years and if maintained properly, it can easily last for 25 years.

20.2. 5. Gated Pipe Irrigation

- In this technique, water is supplied to agriculture fields through plastic or aluminum pipes.
- Quite popular in arid zones.
- This techniques reduces the leakage and evapo-transpiration losses and saves 30-50 percent of water.
- It also aid in reducing the soil erosion.
- An advantage of this technique is that the gates can be opened and closed as per need that is; one can irrigate the selected furrows only.

Gated Pipe Irrigation System

- This system can be installed by supplying water into pipe using a concrete box.
- This box contains a tight screen or a filter that hinders the entering of debris into the pipe.
- The size of the pipe is around 15 inches in diameter.

- A gate in the form of plastic slide is present on the pipe after every 2 feet that can be opened or closed as per requirement.
- Irrigating shovel is used for closing and opening the gates.
- The cost of establishing this irrigation system is less as compare to other modes.
- It is best suited for vegetable farming, cultivating corn, sugarcane, nuts and fruits.

20.2.6. Harvesting and storage of Rain Water

- A relatively deep exaction is done.
- Cover the excavated land with thick impervious polythene sheet to prevent water loss through seepage.
- If the cost of the polythene sheet is high, the water may be left open though losses are high.
- Water crops using the water from the earth dam during scarcity periods.

Rainwater harvesting in 'Jalkund' and utilization for vegetable cultivation

Rain water Harvesting

MODULE 21: SOIL MANAGEMENT

• 21.1 Intended Learning Outcome

At the end of the module, participants should be able apply the different methods of soil management techniques for sustainable agricultural production.

Definition:

Soil management is defined as the protection of the soil from physical and chemical degradation as a result of continuous cultivation so as to maintain the general soil quality required for sustainable agricultural production.

• 21.2 Soil Management Practices

Preambles:

- Loss of soil quality due to crop production over a long time without proper soil management practices put in place to maintain the existing and/or the increased soil fertility has been a major problem affecting soil productivity all over the world.

Major management practices normally employed include:

1. Controlled grazing
2. Organic and Inorganic Fertilizer Application
3. Agroforestry (Alley Farming which is discussed in module 21)
4. Green manuring

21.2.1 Application of Manures

The sources of organic matter in the tropics include:

I. POULTRY MANURE

- This is obtained from the droppings of domesticated poultry (chicken, turkey, goose, etc.).
- Poultry has high nitrogen content, which is quickly made available to plants upon incorporation to the soil.
- Poultry manure can be of great value to crops requiring a great deal of nitrogen for growth at a particular time.

II. FARMYARD MANURE

- This is obtained from domesticated animal pens.
- It is divided into horse and cow manure; and sheep and goat manure.
- Horse and cow manure is a mixture of straw and droppings which rotted down to become humus in the soil.
- Fresh horse manure should never be used because the ammonia in it will burn the roots of young plants.
- Cow manure is not harmful when fresh and may be applied on top of soil or dug in to prevent loss of nitrogen.
- Sheep and goat manure are not as rich as horse or cow manure, but they are also good source of organic manure.
- They must also be covered up immediately to prevent loss of ammonia by leaching.

III. FISH WASTE AND FISH MEAL

- These contain a good supply of readily available nitrogen and phosphorus.
- The manure has an unpleasant smell and should be dug into the soil immediately.

IV. GREEN MANURE

- Green manures are usually fast growing annual legumes or grasses.
- They are incorporated into the soil when they are green and succulent where they will gradually decompose to give humus.
- The advantages of green manure is that it increases the organic matter content, improves soil structure, makes phosphorus and certain trace elements available to plants, checks soil erosion and leaching and helps to control weeds by acting as a smother crop. Some plants, such as *mucuna*, *centrosema*, *calopogonium* and *pueraria* are especially grown for this purpose since they produce an abundance of soft, green manure which decomposes easily in the soil.

V. COMPOST

- Throughout the world there are many options for replacing the plant nutrients lost from soil, but, in our case in Nigeria and especially in northern parts where agriculture is mostly done by smallholder farmers, the best option is compost often produced using the natural materials available to farmers and others, such as students and youth, from their surroundings.
- Good quality compost can be made from organic household wastes in urban areas and be used to grow healthy vegetables in gardens at home or by school environment club or youth group members.
- Composting is the rotting of down of plant and animal remains before it is applied to the soil.
- Compost is a mixture of partially decayed organic material and it may also include ashes, urine, lime and organic wastes.
- Composts are made by decomposing plant and animal materials (straw, grasses, weeds, refuse, animal dung and urine) in a 1.4m x 60cm x 60cm pits as shown pictorially (plate I).
 - Cover the pit and leave for a fortnight before transferring the content into a second pit. Repeat the transfer 2 – 3 times and finally into storage pit (1.6m x 1.6m x 60cm). The compost should be ready to use from the storage pit.

Plate I: Compost making Procedure

- Well decomposed compost should look dark and friable is shown in Plate 2

Plate 2: Well developed humus; this can be applied to farms to reduce the burden on inorganic fertilizer

VI. WOOD ASH

- Wood ash provides a good source of potassium which is usually lacking in acid soils.
- The potash from wood ash is in the form potassium carbonate and is extremely soluble and can even be leached away.
- It is best used immediately, but if this not possible it should be stored in wooden boxes.
- A good sample may contain up to 12% potash but the percentage varies considerably according to the wood from which it is obtained.

VII. SEWAGE OR NIGHT SOIL

- This is the waste materials of humans.
- It is one of the important sources of organic manures.
- It may be composted with other organic materials and soil or it may be fermented in pits and then spread on the soil in liquid form.
- Untreated night soil should not be used as manure.
- This is because of the health risks involved.
- It is however used effectively to make compost by mixing it with town refuse.

Foliar Fertilizers

- Foliar fertilizer is a fertilizer product which is designed to be applied directly to the leaves of a plant.
- A number of companies manufacture a range of foliar fertilizers, from organic products safe for use on food crops to more aggressive chemical fertilizers for ornamentals.
- There are a number of advantages to using a foliar fertilizer which make such fertilizers popular for some gardening applications.
- With foliar feeding, as it is known, the nutrients are absorbed directly through the leaves of the plant.
- They work their way down the roots, but they also stimulate activity in the leaves, which in turn stimulates root development, because the plant starts to demand more water.
- Applying foliar fertilizer can increase uptake of nutrients from the soil by encouraging plants to take up more water, in addition to providing immediate benefits for a plant which may be suffering from deficiency.

- A foliar fertilizer is not designed as an alternative to soil fertilizer and soil conditioning, but rather as a supplement which will increase efficiency and improve plant health.
- Uptake of nutrients from the soil can be very inefficient, and it can take several days for noticeable effects to occur. Foliar fertilizers act more quickly, and far more efficiently, as most of the fertilizer ends up in the plant, rather than in the soil.
- There are some precautions which need to be observed when applying foliar fertilizer.
- It must be diluted before application to prevent fertilizer burn, and it also needs to be applied when plants are most likely to benefit.
- The best time to do this is when temperatures are cool and some dew is present on the leaves, as in the evening and early morning, as the stomata on the leaves will be open and able to absorb the nutrients.
- Applying during the heat of the day is inefficient, and can in fact damage the plant.

Foliar Application

MODULE 22: AGROFORESTRY

• 22.1 Objectives, duration and methods of training

Objectives

This module provides an overview of agroforestry systems; it also describes how to identify the most appropriate agroforestry system and to design, adapt, establish and manage it.

Duration

2 hours

Methods for the Training

Demonstration, use of videos and pictures, exercises

- **22.2 Introduction**

The USDA defines agroforestry as the combination of agriculture and forestry technologies to create more integrated, diverse, productive, profitable, healthy and sustainable land-use systems.

Agroforestry - comprising all land-use systems and practices in which wood perennials are deliberately grown on the same land management unit as crops and/or animals - is a rapidly evolving approach to resource management. Agroforestry combines agriculture and forestry to create a more integrated, diverse and sustainable land-use systems. It seeks to utilize several different ways of doing forestry that break with tradition and attempt to generate long term and responsible returns from harvesting trees.

Plate 1: Agro-pastoralism; here livestock is integrated with fodder trees on the same piece of land

22.2.1 But why practice agroforestry?

Agroforestry can provide many more benefits than just better returns on a particular plot of land. One major benefit to the deliberate practice of agroforestry is the fact that it has many possible uses. Specifically, agroforestry can produce significant benefits, if done correctly:

Diversification

Agroforestry allows the land on which it is practiced, as well as the rural community it is a part of, to diversify, biologically and economically. One problem with modern forestry or agriculture is that it usually involves "putting all of your eggs in one basket." If a tree-killing disease sweeps through a forest, years of investments and care are ruined. The same goes for crops and field pests. By combining forestry and agriculture in innovative ways, the farmer or forester can diversify their holdings and give themselves better overall value on their property. Also, good diversification can stimulate rural economic development by creating additional and more stable income streams into the community.

Pollution Control

Evidence is mounting that shows the long-term negative effects intensive agriculture can have on a particular area of land. The inputs (fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, others) build up over time and leak into water systems and nearby properties, producing a potential health hazard and costly environmental problem. Also, on the edges of urban sprawl, different kinds of pollution (soil, water, air) are making their ways into rural environments. Property utilized agroforestry can put trees in place that filter out many of these pollutants and keep them from further contaminating surrounding environments.

Biodiversity

Agroforestry can help return true biodiversity to the world's farmland. Forests or tree stands provide natural cover for animals and allow them to regain a foothold in the area. Biodiversity can also have strong economic benefits as well, such as income from land used as for hunting or as a nature conservation area.

Erosion Control

Any landowner would take sensible action to prevent gradually losing his land to erosion, as any erosion of the land translates directly into a gradual loss of value in one's portfolio. Agroforestry provides an easy, inexpensive and potentially valuable way to help keep land around water sources intact, without having to resort to environmentally dangerous and costly artificial structures, like walls or shore dams.

Climate Moderation

While some crops require a high-temperature to germinate and abundant sunlight to grow, agroforestry can provide climate moderation in other areas. This can make the surround area much more livable for all creatures, while not damaging the productivity of the surrounding agricultural projects.

Integrated Production Systems

In agricultural or forestry production today, efficiency is key. You simply must generate more returns with fewer inputs, such as land and management expertise. Yet, around the world, most plots of land can produce a variety of valuable products rather than just one or two intensively produced crops or types of lumber. Combining agriculture and forestry into agroforestry maximizes one's potential earnings while making best use of the resources at hand.

- **22.3 System and Practices**

Agroforestry has been practised for a very long time in many parts of the world. Its forms vary considerably from landscape to landscape, country to country, and region to region, depending on human needs and capabilities and the prevailing environmental, cultural and socioeconomic conditions. There are three main types of agroforestry systems:

a. Agrisilvicultural systems are a combination of crops and trees, such as alley cropping or homegardens.

b. Silvopastoral systems combine forestry and grazing of domesticated animals on pastures, rangelands or on-farm.

c. Agrosilvopastoral systems where trees, animals and crops can be integrated.

The most common agroforestry systems are:

- a. *Agrosilvicultural systems* (crops – e.g. annual crops and vines – plus trees)
- b. improved fallow
- c. taungya
- d. alley cropping
- e. multilayer tree gardens
- f. multipurpose trees in croplands
- g. plantation–crop combinations
- h. homegardens
- i. trees for soil conservation and reclamation
- j. shelterbelts, windbreaks and live hedges
- k. woodfuel production.
- l. *Silvopastoral systems* (trees plus pasture and animals)
- m. Trees or shrubs on rangelands or pastures
- n. Protein banks (blocks or lines of trees or shrubs established and managed for fodder production)
- o. Plantation crops with pastures and animals
- p. *Agrosilvopastoral systems* (trees plus crops plus pasture and animals)
- q. homegardens involving animals
- r. multipurpose woody hedgerows
- s. apiculture with trees
- t. aquaforestry
- u. multipurpose woodlots.

In particular alley farming is the most promising in the drylands which Yobe State lie on. Therefore it should be encouraged using the procedure below;

Alley Cropping:

Alley cropping is an agroforestry practice in which perennial, preferably leguminous trees or shrubs are grown simultaneously with an arable crop. The trees, managed as hedgerows, are grown in wide rows and the crop is planted in the interspace or 'alley' between the tree rows.

During the cropping phase the trees are pruned and the prunings used as green manure or mulch on the crop to improve the organic matter status of the soil and to provide nutrients, particularly nitrogen, to the crop.

The hedgerows are allowed to grow freely to shade the inter-rows when there are no crops.

Alley cropping retains the basic restorative attributes of the bush fallow through nutrient recycling, fertility regeneration and weed suppression and combines these with arable cropping so that all processes occur concurrently on the same land, allowing the farmer to crop the land for an extended period.

The use of *Acacia* trees in alley cropping is highly recommended in the area under discussion. The following information is therefore important. Notable *Acacia* species in *Acacia nilotica* (Bagaruwa in Hausa and *Acacia senegal* (Dakwara in Hausa).

Acacia senegal is highly suitable in agroforestry systems where it is intercropped with short seasoned agricultural crops such as millet, sorghum, sesame and groundnuts. *Acacia senegal* which is a leguminous tree or shrub produces an

extensive, deep root system in addition to its potential to fix atmospheric nitrogen.

Leguminous trees have been estimated to annually fix about 40-580 kg of N per ha, compared to 15-210 kg per ha for grain legumes.

Acacia senegal's strong tap root system allows the plant to establish and grow to produce forage for livestock, wood and gum, improve the microclimate by buffering winds, provides shade and acts as bee forage.

Acacia litter contributes greatly to soil fertility due to the tree's ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. The most important nutrient in the semi-arid areas is N and its major source is N₂ fixed biologically by legumes through their symbiosis with rhizobia.

Acacia species in general are multipurpose trees providing a wide range of products and services. The trees produce gum that can be harvested and sold by farmers to improve their livelihood.

THE GUM

- Physical properties: colorless, tasteless, odorless, readily soluble in water

PROCEDURE

I. Site Selection

- The area to be devoted to alley cropping should have a flat to gently sloping topography and should be less productive for purely food crop production.

2. Land Preparation

- After clearing and weeding the area, layout the rows of trees or shrubs and food crops in an east-west direction with the following distances: in between rows of tree crops, 5 meters; in between rows of tree and food crops, 1 meter; in between individual tree plants, 25 to 150 centimeters.
- Distances between rows and individual food crops shall depend on the type of plant to be grown. With use of a harrow or hoe, cultivate only the rows where tree and food crops will be planted.

3. Planting of trees and food crops

- Plant trees with food crops during the planting season. Allow the tree crops to grow one full year while conducting normal farming operations on the food crops.

4. Maintenance

- Conduct pruning of the tree crops in the second year, twice or every three months at 0.5 meter height. Leaves and small stems should be used as mulching materials for food crops.

• 22.4 Benefits

Agroforestry addresses 4 SDGs: Goal 1: Poverty, Goal 2: Zero Hunger, Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production and Goal 15: Life on Land. Beyond that it has many benefits in the in light of prevailing economic, social and environmental conditions.

22.4.1 Economic benefits

Most agroforestry systems aim to increase or maintain the production and productivity of farming systems; reduce agricultural inputs and thus production costs; and diversify production by the use of trees or other woody perennials to produce, for example, food, fodder, lumber, building materials and woodfuel.

Agroforestry systems may also create opportunities for small-scale forest-based enterprises. Agroforestry can help reduce rural poverty by increasing on-farm production and household income and by providing employment opportunities, and it can reduce the risk of economic failure by increasing the diversity of production within farming systems.

22.4.2 Social benefits

An increase in production, productivity and product diversity through agroforestry can help improve the health and nutrition of the rural poor. The on-farm production of fuel, fodder and other tree products, otherwise collected from off-farm sources, can reduce the time and effort needed to obtain them (often lessening the burden on women) or save money if the products would otherwise be purchased. When the supply of labour changes at the household or community level (e.g. due to the seasonal out-migration of men), agroforestry offers options for maximizing output per labour input. The perpetuation of traditional agroforestry practices can help maintain social bonds established through mutual-help arrangements (e.g. in the case of shifting cultivation).

22.4.3 Environmental benefits

Agroforestry systems can provide a range of environmental services. For example, they can improve soil fertility, protect crops and livestock from wind, restore degraded lands, improve water conservation, limit pests and prevent soil erosion. If properly designed and managed agroforestry systems can contribute to biodiversity conservation and climate-change adaptation and mitigation. If deployed inadequately, however, they may lead to decreases in production because of competition among trees and crops.

- **22.5 Establishing and Managing Agroforestry Systems**

The establishment of an agroforestry system involves, among other things, site preparation, plant and animal material selection, planting, and marketing. The availability of suitable materials and adequate financial and technical inputs is crucial. The following steps should be taken in the adoption of an agroforestry system.

22.5.1. Identifying appropriate agroforestry options

The first thing to determine is whether agroforestry is already practised in an area and if there is potential for the adaptation or wider adoption of local systems. If agroforestry is not practised, the question is whether it is an appropriate land-use option in the area.

Agroforestry systems are more complex than monocultures and may need considerable effort, time and expertise for their successful uptake. It is important, therefore, to consider the costs and benefits of agroforestry.

The suitability of an agroforestry system for a particular site depends on the needs of the family or community and the potential benefits of the system. Reasons for agroforestry adoption include: increasing farm production or income; diversifying production, such as of food, fibre, fodder, fruit, construction materials, medicine, honey, dyes, resins and gums; and providing environmental services that help increase food security and improve household livelihoods.

If it is considered that agroforestry can help meet the needs of land users, the next step is to determine which agroforestry system is most suitable in the prevailing economic, social and environmental conditions.

22.5.2 Key elements to be considered in this decision-making process:

Land characteristics: such as topography, soil fertility and drainage, and water resources, and climate and other environmental conditions, such as precipitation, temperature and seasonal variations.

The needs and priorities of landowners: such as products for their own consumption and to sell in the market, and environmental services. Needs may vary by scale (e.g. smallholders versus big landowners) and conditions (e.g. ownership regime and management system). Participatory rural assessments, other means of collecting information on stakeholders, and market analyses can help in identifying household needs and the opportunities for agroforestry in an area.

The availability of resources: such as land, labour, technology and capital.

Note that agroforestry does have limitations. Trees may compete with food crops for space, sunlight, moisture and nutrients, thereby reducing crop yields. Food crops may be damaged during tree-harvesting. Trees that form part of agroforestry systems may be hosts of insects and birds that can damage crops. Finally, the rapid regeneration of trees may displace food crops and even take over entire fields.

22.5.3 Choice of trees

The choice of species of trees and other woody perennials should be based on: the goals and objectives of the farmer, the potential products/functions (e.g. fruits, nuts and nitrogen fixation); the environmental suitability of species for the site; the tree/shrub characteristics that influence their interactions with other components of the agroforestry system (e.g. growth rate, crown shape and rooting pattern); and the origin (native/exotic) and availability of planting material.

For example, if food production is the top priority, fruit or nut trees suitable for the local environment and markets could be included. Domesticated wild plant or animal species used by local people may be particularly well suited for locally adapted agroforestry systems.

22.5.4 Factors to be considered in the Design of an Agroforestry System

Design principles differ according to the planned **duration** of the agroforestry system. For example, one system may be introduced to address an immediate problem, such as soil erosion, to be replaced when the problem has been resolved by a (possibly more profitable) system. Design depends on four factors:

Land ownership: This affects the feasibility of agroforestry designs and the motivation for adopting an agroforestry system. For example, farmers are more likely to invest in the planting and management of fruit trees and lumber trees, and to plan a succession of annual and perennial understorey crops, if their tenure to the land is secure.

Size of plots available for agroforestry: This can vary significantly, from less than one hectare to many hectares. Some agroforestry systems may not be practical (or economically feasible) below a certain size; for example, very small plots may be unable to sustain livestock.

Location of a plot: in terms of access, slope, and possibilities for future land-use change can also affect agroforestry design.

Environmental factors: such as climate, soil, drainage, sunlight and precipitation will help determine the trees, agricultural crops and livestock that can be grown or raised in a given area.

22.5.5 The selection of plant and animal material

Plants

1. Tree seedlings can be purchased from commercial nurseries or produced by the land owners/managers themselves, depending on needs and situations. Smallholders may be able to purchase tree seedlings at competitive rates from local nurseries. High-quality seedlings should be selected to ensure high tree survival rates.
2. Community forestry nursery – in which community members share costs and provide inputs – could be an efficient way of producing low-cost seedlings. Individual enterprises may consider producing tree seedlings in their own nurseries, as described below.
 - *Seed collection and handling* usually includes the following activities:
 - selection of seed provenance
 - selection of mother trees
 - seed collection
 - seed extraction (e.g. from pods, cones or fruits)
 - seed storage
 - Record keeping
 - pre-sowing treatment
 - inoculation
3. Trees can be propagated in different ways. E.g.:
 - collection of wildings
 - direct seed sowing in the field
 - farmer-managed natural regeneration
 - cuttings
 - budding and grafting
 - grafting
4. Crop seeds may be purchased in local markets or obtained from self-production. High-quality crop seeds should be chosen (this may be indicated, for example, by parameters such as size and colour); experienced local farmers are likely to be good sources of information. Trials should be conducted to test the quality and survival rate of seeds.

Animals

Animals can be bought in markets or from neighbours; only healthy animals should be purchased, and they should be provided with adequate shelter and food to ensure their continued growth and good health. In any given agroforestry system, it should be clear who has primary responsibility for the care and security of the animals and for obtaining animal products such as milk, eggs and fibre.

22.5.6 Planting

This may simple technology or involves special machinery or tools and requires adequate knowledge. The planting of trees and annual crops should be timed to coincide with favorable climatic conditions (e.g. the onset of the rainy season).

22.5.7 Marketing

This is another essential element of agroforestry, in which the products generated by the system are converted into actual income. It involves the following steps:

- selecting target markets;
- adding value to products;
- getting products to prospective buyers;
- setting the price; and
- promoting the products.

• 22.6 Maintaining and Monitoring an Agroforestry System

Maintenance is needed to ensure that an agroforestry system functions effectively. Common maintenance practices include:

- seedling protection
- weed control
- pest control
- animal browsing
- fertilization
- irrigation
- thinning
- pruning
- coppicing
- harvesting
- post-harvesting operations

- **22.7 Gender and Agroforestry**

Emphasis will be given to the role of women in agroforestry because of the substantial benefits it provides to households: food, fuelwood, fodder and other products and services particularly in times of need. Women are often vulnerable in dry areas despite their central role in managing trees and agriculture: planting, weeding and watering.

Women also play important roles in small enterprises such as processing indigenous fruits and vegetable e.g. *Butyrespermum parkii* (shea butter), *Tamarindus indica* (Tamarind), *Vitex doniana* (edible fruit), *Magnifera indica* (mango), *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (edible leaf), *Gnetum africanum* (edible vegetable). These indigenous fruits can provide a significant source of income which improves households' economy and health.

How can we improve the participation of women in agroforestry?

1. *Technological interventions*

- a. Domesticate agroforestry species
- b. Develop appropriate storage and processing methods

2. *Policy interventions*

- a. Increase women's access to extension services
- b. Support women's access to market information
- c. Improve women's access to finance from microcredit institutions

3. *Institutional interventions*

- a. Strengthen local institutions and women farmers' organizations.
- b. Develop new, diverse, high-value products such as oil, soap, juice, body lotion, and leaf meal. Many of these products can be made from the same raw materials. e.g oil and soap from *Butyrespermum parkii* (shea butter).

MODULE 23: TREE PLANTING

- **23.1 Training Objectives:**

At the end of the training, the trainees should be able to:

- ✓ Describe climatic conditions of the planting site
- ✓ Recall the ways of production and acquisition of planting stock
- ✓ Understand plantation operations
- ✓ Carry out plantation tending operations

- **23.2 Module One**

23.2.1 Climatic Conditions of the Planting Site (Northern Yobe)

- The northern part of Yobe (planting site) is situated between latitude 12° 00' and 13° 28' N and longitude 9° 45' and 12° 30' E
- It has tropical climate characterized by distinct wet and dry seasons.
- The dry season is associated with dry continental air mass of the north east trade wind which originates from the Sahara desert while the wet season is associated with moist maritime southern air mass which originates from the Atlantic Ocean.
- The area experience uniform weather with rainfall attaining its peak in August; even though, there seems to be a shift in the recent times.
- The mean annual rainfall is about 450mm with an average onset and secession date in June and September.
- The site is characterized with low rainfall that last only three to four months.
- The average daily temperature is 25°C with the maximum of up to 40°C (April to June).
- The average relative humidity for the month of December and January is about 30% (driest period) and goes to as high as to an average of 70% in wettest months (August and September).
- The area has tropical vegetation characterized by scattered shrubs, thorns of Acacia species, Tamarinds, Baobab and Edulious plants
- ✓ The trees are xerophytic in nature

23.2.2 Planting season

- ✓ Wet season should be targeted and is the most preferred (see 1.1 above)
- ✓ Dry season can also be used, especially if the scheduled time cannot be amended, but it requires extra establishment cost.

23.2.3 The choice of the tree species; this should be guided on the following:

- ✓ Ecological consideration
- ✓ Biotic factors
- ✓ Silvicultural systems
- ✓ Ease of establishment
- ✓ Rate of growth and rotation
- ✓ Resistant to insect pest and diseases
- ✓ Relative expenditure and return

23.2.4 Tree Species for Agroforestry

Some recommended agroforestry tree species that provides both ecological and socioeconomic benefits includes but not limited to:

- *Parkia biglobosa* (Dorowa, Daddawa)
- *Ficus Spp.*
- *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* (Turare)
- *Adansonia digitata* (Kuka, Kwame)
- *Azadirachta indica* (Dogon yaro)
- *Acacia species including seyal and nilotica*
- *Khaya senegalensis* (Madaci)
- *Tamarindus indica* (Tsamiya)
- *Leucaena leucocephala*
- *Vitex doniana* (Dinya)
- *Prosopis juliflora*
- *Vitellaria paradoxii* (Kadanya, Kade)
- *Moringa oleifera* (Zogale)
- *Ceiba pentandra* (Rimi)
- *Faidherbia albida* (Gawo)
- *Balanites aegyptiaca* (Aduwa)
- *Hyphene thebaica* (Goriba)
- *Acacia Senegal* (Dakwara)
- *Phoenix dactylifera* (Dabino)
- *Ziziphus spina-christii* (Magariya)

• 23.3 Preparation, Production and Acquisition of the Planting Stock

23.3.1 Preparation

Decision has to be taken on how to get the planting stock and what should be source of the planting stock

23.3.2 Production and Acquisition of the Planting Stock

Planting stock can be obtained from the following sources:

- ✓ Commercial nurseries
- ✓ Government nurseries
- ✓ Individual
- ✓ Temporary nursery for the Program

The selection of any of the above should be based on the following:

- The proximity to the planting site
- Cost of production
- Cost of transportation
- Level of engagement and commitment

• 23.4 Plantation Operation

23.4.1 Plantation Materials

The materials that may be needed for smooth running of plantation activity may include: cutlass, axe, shovel, head pan, blades, wheel barrows, watering materials, manures, measuring tapes etc

23.4.2 Handling of Planting Stock

The planting stock (seedlings/cuttings) must be properly handled to avoid unnecessary stress which may lead to failure.

23.4.3 Transportation of the Planting Stock

Wheel barrows, tractors, head pan etc can be used to transport the planting stock to the field.

23.4.4 Site Preparation

These should include the following:

- ✓ Site clearing (Manual, Machine, Chemical or fire)
- ✓ Ground preparation
- ✓ Demarcation
- ✓ Planting distance/spacing (2mx2m, 2.5mx2.5m, 3mx1m, 3mx3m, 4mx4m etc)
- ✓ Lining and pegging
- ✓ Pit digging and depth
- ✓ Manuring
- ✓ Watering

- **23.5 Tending Operations**

The following operations should be carried out after planting activity, for success of tree establishment process:

- ✓ Initial survival and beaten-up
- ✓ Weeding
- ✓ Watering
- ✓ Pruning
- ✓ Protection
- ✓ Caging/fencing

MODULE 24: PESTICIDES APPLICATION, HANDLING AND MANAGEMENT

- **24.1 Training Objectives**

UNIT 1: Pest identification, Recognition and Control

Objectives: Define the term pests and understand the different group of pest; Identify and recognize pests; General control measures in managing pests.

UNIT 2: Pesticide Classification and Application

Objectives: Define what pesticides are; state the advantages and disadvantages of pesticides application; state the factors affecting pesticide use; Give reasons why some pesticide applications failed; Classify pesticides based on type of pests they control, mode of action, and formulation; State different pesticides application Methods.

UNIT 3: PESTICIDE LABELING AND BANNED PESTICIDES

Objectives: State the meaning and importance of pesticide label; give the different parts of the label; state when to read the label; list banned pesticides in Nigeria; State the effect of pesticides on the environment

UNIT 4: SAFETY PRECAUTIONS WHEN HANDLING PESTICIDES

Objectives: State and understand the precautionary measures when buying; transporting pesticides; storing pesticides; during and after application; Know the importance of waiting period after application of pesticides; State safety precautions for using sprayers

UNIT 5: TYPES OF SPRAYING EQUIPMENT AND CALIBRATION SPRAYER

Objectives: State the types of sprayers and their components; Procedures of sprayer calibration; proper mixing of pesticides; how to make tank mixtures

UNIT 6: APPLYING PESTICIDES DURING STORAGE

Objectives: Identify and understand ways of disinfecting storage facilities; how to determine the right quantity of pesticides to apply on grain during storage; state the precautionary measures to be observed during grain storage with chemicals.

UNIT 7: HERBICIDE APPLICATION

Objectives: Classify herbicides based on types and formulation; state factors affecting sprayer calibration.

UNIT 8: PESTICIDES POISONING AND FIRST AID

Objectives: State the meaning of pesticides poisoning and identify *common ways in which pesticide handlers are exposed to pesticides*; state how to give first aid for pesticide poisoning; state how to induce vomiting in case ingesting pesticides (if needed).

UNIT 9: PRACTICALS

- i) Identification of different types of pesticides
- ii) Identification and use of protective covers when applying pesticides
- iii) How to spray a pesticide
- iv) Demonstrations on how to mix and apply pesticides

Methods of Presentation: Lecture and discussion; Demonstration and field practical

Materials required: Personal protective equipment, sweep nets, pesticides (fungicide, insecticides, nematicides, rodenticides etc.), Knapsack sprayers, buckets, detergents and hand gloves.

• 24.2 Pest identification, Recognition and Control

A pest is anything that competes with humans, domestic animals, or crops for food, feed, or water or injures humans, animals, crops, structures, or possessions or spreads disease to humans, domestic animals, or crops. There are four main groups of pest organisms: Weeds (undesirable plants),

invertebrate animals (insects, mites, ticks, spiders, snails, and slugs), Disease agents or pathogens (bacteria, viruses, fungi, nematodes etc) and Vertebrates (birds, reptiles, amphibians, fish, and rodents and other mammals). Never classify an organism as a pest until it is clearly determined to be one. Be certain any injury or observed damage is actually due to the identified organism and not to some other cause. Some plants, for example, can be damaged by factors in the environment. These factors include weather extremes, air pollutants, road salt, and inadequate or excessive fertilization. This damage may be mistaken for that caused by living pests. For effective pests control there is need to be familiar with the pests likely to be encountered in the area covered by your certification category. To be able to identify and control the pests, you need to know about some aspects of: the common features of pest organisms, characteristics of the damage they cause, and pest development and biology. To solve pest problems, the applicator must:

- a) identify the pest
- b) know what control methods are available
- c) evaluate the benefits and risks of each method or combination of Methods
- d) choose the methods that are most effective and least harm and
- e) use each method correctly.

The three main objectives of pest control are: prevention—keeping a pest from becoming a problem; suppression—reducing pest numbers of damage to an acceptable level; eradication—destroying an entire pest population from a limited defined area.

PEST CONTROL METHODS

Once a pest problem is identified, you can begin planning how to manage the pest. Determine what management methods are available and the benefits and limitations of each. Select methods that are most effective in controlling the pest yet the least harmful to people and the environment. Pest control methods can be classified into abiotic and applied. Abiotic control are natural control measures within the environment that injure or destroy plants and animals, including pests. They include climatic factors (e.g., wind, temperature, sunshine, and rain), air or water pollution, and topographic features (rivers, lakes, and mountains) that can affect pest movement. Applied controls include biological, chemical, cultural, genetic, mechanical/physical, and regulatory methods.

I. Biological Control

Biological control is the use of natural enemies predators, parasites, pathogens, and competitors to control pests and their damage. These biological control

(biocontrol) agents are being used successfully to manage certain insect, mite, fungal, fish, and weed pests.

2. Chemical Control

Chemical control is the pest management method that involves using naturally derived and/or synthetic chemicals to manage pests. These chemicals are often called pesticides. A pesticide is defined as any material that is applied to plants, soil, water, harvested crops, structures, clothing and furnishings, or animals to kill, attract, repel, regulate or interrupt the growth and mating of pests, or to regulate plant growth.

3. Cultural Control

This involves regular agronomic practices employed in crop production which have a profound influence on the incidence and populations of crop pests. The manipulation of these practices for pests control is generally called cultural control. The basic principle of cultural control is the disruption of the development and life cycles of pests either by denying them their food or by exposing stages in their life cycle to adverse conditions so that they are killed. Cultural pest control is relatively cheap and effective. It poses minimal danger to the environment. Cultural control methods include cultivation of the soil, variation in planting and harvesting dates, crop rotation, close season, trap cropping, use of resistant crop varieties, mixed cropping, good husbandry practices, good drainage and fertilizer application.

4. Mechanical/Physical Control

Mechanical and physical controls can kill a pest directly or make its environment unsuitable. Rodent traps are examples of mechanical control. Several types of traps are commonly used. Some kill animals that come across them; others scare animals and make them relocate. Traps can be mechanical devices or sticky surfaces, some with pheromones incorporated to increase trapping efficiency.

Physical controls include mulches for weed management, steam soil sterilization for disease control, deer fences, screens to keep insects out, and cloth mesh to exclude birds from fruit trees. Another example is sealing cracks, crevices, and other small openings in buildings to exclude insects, rodents, bats, birds, and squirrels. A band of sticky material painted around tree trunks prevents crawling insects from reaching the tree's leaves.

5. Legislative Control Method

This involves the use of laws and regulations to prevent the importation of pest organisms into a country and to restrict the spread of pest in areas where

they are already established. The main objective of legislation is to prevent dangerous pests from colonizing new areas. Legislative control involves quarantine, eradication regulation and certification.

Quarantine: In order to prevent importation of plant material and plant products containing pests into the country, quarantine laws stipulate that such imported products must be thoroughly inspected in the country of origin and certified free of pest organisms. A phytosanitary certificate by the appropriate authority must be enclosed with the product exported. The importation of some plant materials may be totally prohibited by a country. The movement of plant materials and products within Africa is monitored by the Inter-African Phytosanitary Council of the African Union (AU), the headquarters of the Commission is in Yaounde, Cameroon. The Commission issues periodic newsletters which give information on pests and diseases in different African countries.

Eradication regulation: Sometimes serious pests are subject to a notification order which stipulates that their presence must be reported immediately to the appropriate authorities, including the police. Pictures of such pests, their host plants and the symptoms of their damage are widely displayed at ports of entry and all over the country for the information of all concerned. Warehouses at seaports and ships are regularly inspected and fumigated to eliminate the pests (e.g. rodents) and thereby prevent their spread.

Certification: Plants, seeds and other susceptible materials must not be sold unless they have been vigorously inspected and certified free of pests. Certification regulations are sometimes enforced by the National Seed Service (Nigerian Seed Council) or other appropriate authorities of different countries.

6. Integrated pest control and integrated pest management

The problems arising from the use of pesticides are in themselves serious and therefore, attempts must be made to ensure that whatever pesticides are used to control pests, they must be used sensibly. These problems have led to the development of integrated control as an alternative system whereby pesticides are combined with other appropriate methods of pest control. Integrated Pest Control (IPC) or Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is simply defined as “the application of the best mix of environmentally sound techniques in order to keep pests below the damage threshold”. It can further be defined more specifically as “a pest-management system that in the context of the associated environment and the population dynamics of the pest species, utilizes all suitable techniques and methods in as compatible manner as possible and maintains the pest populations at levels below those causing economic injury.

• 24.3 PESTICIDE CLASSIFICATION AND APPLICATION

Pesticides are chemicals used to destroy pests, control their activity, or prevent them from causing damage. Some pesticides either attract or repel pests. Chemicals which regulate plant growth or remove foliage may also be classified as pesticides.

The most common and easily applicable method for reducing or preventing economic pest damage is the use toxic substances or pesticides to kill or repel pests on their host crops or animals. Chemical control plays a significant role in solving the food and wealth problems of tropical countries. Many crops e.g. cowpea and cotton cannot be grown successfully without pesticide application and malaria eradication programmes all over the world depend largely on the use of pesticides.

The advantages of chemical pest control include:

- i) It is a relatively easy method of pest control.
- ii) It produces quick and easy results.
- iii) It can be repeated as often as desirable.
- iv) It is cheap and individual farmers can take independent action on their own farms.
- v) The broad-spectrum action of many pesticides makes it possible to control a complex of pests with one or a combination of pesticides.

The disadvantages of chemical pest control include:

- i) Chemical pest control is repetitive and must be applied whenever there is a pest outbreak. It is therefore, wasteful.
- ii) The pesticide applied rarely kills all the pests and the residual population which survives soon develops to cause economic damage.
- iii) Pesticides can be toxic to beneficial insects especially parasites, predators and pollinators. They are potentially toxic to wildlife, fish and humans.
- iv) Pesticides may cause environmental pollution and ecological disturbance. Toxic residues may remain in agricultural procedure.
- v) Pest may develop resistance to a pesticide which reduces the effect of that pesticide on that pest.
- vi) Chemical control provides only a temporary solution to pest problems.
- vii) Pesticides are expensive to manufacture and usually have to be imported by tropical countries at the expense of their hard currency.

Factors Affecting Pesticide Use

- a) Soil Factors: Organic matter in soils may “tie up” pesticides, limiting their activity. Soils with high organic matter content may need higher

rates of some pesticides for best control. Soil texture also affects the way pesticides work. Soils with fine particles (silts and clays) have the most surface area. They may need higher rates for total coverage. Coarser soils (sands) have less surface area. Use lower rates on them.

- b) **Surface Moisture:** Pesticides work best with moderate surface moisture. Wetness may keep the pesticide from adequately contacting the protected surface. Dryness may prevent the pesticide from spreading evenly over the surface and contacting the target pest. Rain may interfere with pest control by causing pesticides to run off or to leach down through the soil. Rain during or soon after foliar applications may wash pesticides off the plant. However, some protectant fungicides are sometimes purposely applied just before periods of expected high humidity and light rain. When pre-emergence pesticides are applied to the surface, moderate rainfall aids in carrying them down through the soil to the pests. Rain may also release pesticide action after some granular applications.
- c) **Humidity and Temperature:** Humidity also affects the way pesticides work. Herbicides often work best when weeds are growing fast—usually in high humidity and optimum temperature. However, these same conditions may make the protected plant more susceptible to pesticide injuries. High temperature and sunlight will cause some pesticides to break down when they are left exposed on top of the soil or on other surfaces. Low temperatures may slow down or stop the activity of some pesticides.
- d) **Wind:** Wind speed and direction can greatly alter the effectiveness of a pesticide application. Excessive wind can blow the pesticide off target and result in inadequate control. Even moderate winds can greatly alter the coverage of Ultra Low Volume Concentrate Solutions (ULV) and mist blower applications.

Why Pesticide Applications Fail

- a) **Pest identification:** Sometimes a pesticide application fails because the pest was not identified correctly. Being able to accurately identify pests requires patience and practice. For example, knowing the difference between a caterpillar and a sawfly will result in success (control) or failure when using *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt). Bt is effective on caterpillars but not on sawflies. Even nonchemical tactics may fail if the pest and susceptible life stages are not accurately identified.
- b) **Dosage—**Make sure that you have applied the correct pesticide at the correct dosage, according to label instructions.

c) Correct use—Some herbicides are formulated to kill grasses, others for broadleaf weeds, and still others can kill both types of weeds. Always read the pesticide label to see if the target pest is listed.

d) Application timing—Other applications fail because the pesticide was not applied at the correct time. The pest may not have been in the area during the application, or it may have been in a life cycle stage where it was not susceptible to the pesticide. Insects are usually more vulnerable when they are immature, and weeds are most easily controlled before they flower and go to seed. Also, remember that current pests may be part of a new infestation that developed long after the chemical was applied.

e) Application equipment—Concealed pests (under leaves or bark, in the soil, or within stems or fruits) are difficult to reach. This means that knowing the best type of application equipment to use is very important. For example, use an air-blast sprayer for pests hiding under apple tree leaves but a granular applicator during planting granular applicator during planting operations for soil-dwelling agronomic pests.

f) Environmental conditions—In general, do not apply pesticides just before a rainstorm. The pesticide may be washed off the target plants and away from the application site. Temperature extremes and windy conditions can move pesticides away from the target pests and site.

g) Pesticide degradation—Pesticides may degrade when stored. Under some conditions, pesticides can change into a form that is ineffective. This might be due to the age of the product or the pesticide storage conditions. For example, granular pesticides stored in wet or very humid conditions will draw moisture. This may cause clumping and possible deactivation of the pesticide.

h) Pesticide Resistance

Pesticide resistance is the ability of a pest to tolerate a pesticide that once controlled it. Resistance develops when intensive pesticide use kills the susceptible individuals in a population but leaves the resistant ones to reproduce. Resistance may develop to a single insecticide, fungicide, herbicide, or rodenticide. More often, however, pest populations become resistant to chemically related pesticides in a class of compounds. It is also possible for a pest to develop resistance to pesticides in two or more classes of compounds with different modes of action. Continual use of pesticides from the same chemical class increases the likelihood that resistance will develop in a pest population. Frequent applications and greater persistence of the chemical further increase the chances of pesticide resistance. Finally, resistance can spread through a pest population much more rapidly in pests that have many generations per year and many offspring per generation, such as many insects, mites, fungi, and rodents.

Several pest management tactics help prevent or delay the occurrence of pesticide resistance. One approach is the use of new or altered pesticides. Using new compounds with different modes of action will lessen the likelihood of resistance developing in a population. Changing pesticide use patterns is an important step in preventing resistance. When dosages are reduced, fewer pests are killed, so the pressure to develop resistant pest populations is decreased. Applying pesticides over limited areas reduces the proportion of the total pest population exposed to the chemical. The result is a large pool of individuals still susceptible to the pesticide. This tactic tends to delay the development of a resistant population because pesticide-susceptible individuals continue to interbreed with resistant ones, thus diluting the resistance in the population. Also, treating alternate generations of pests with pesticides that have different modes of action decreases the selection pressure for resistance.

CLASSIFICATION OF PESTICIDES

Pesticides can be classified into four categories based on: type of pests they control, mode of action, chemical nature and formulation.

I. Classification based on the type of pests they control:

The table below summarizes the classification of pesticides based on the type of pests they control:

Table 1: classification of pesticides based on the type of pests they control

Type of pesticides	Target pests
Acaricides	Kill Mites, ticks, spiders, scorpions
Algicides	Control algae in lakes, canals, water tanks and other sites
Avicides	Kill birds
Bactericides	Kill bacteria
Biocides	Generally kill micro organisms
Fungicides	Kill fungi
Herbicides	Kill weeds or any plant growing where it is not wanted
Insecticides	Kill insects and other arthropods
Molluscicides	Kill snails and slugs
Nematicides	Kill nematodes
Ovicides	Kill eggs of insects and mites
Pheromones	Biochemicals used to disrupt the mating behavior of insects
Rodenticides	Control mice and other rodents

2. Classification based on Mode of Action

- i. Stomach poisons: These type of pesticides act when ingested into the alimentary canal of the target pest. Their use is mostly limited to surface feeding insects with chewing mouthparts (grasshoppers, crickets, caterpillers), e.g. Gammalin 20 (banned pesticide), AldrexT (banned pesticide) and Dithane.
- ii. Contact pesticides: These kill by direct contact with external portion of the pest. They may be used on both chewing and sucking insects, e.g. Vetox 85 and Cymbush.
- iii. Residual contact pesticides: These are contact pesticides with extended residual toxicity, although body contact with the insect pest is not necessary for it to be effective e.g. Furadan, Carbofuran and Delfuran.
- iv. Fumigants: These are pesticides that have high enough vapour pressure to produce lethal concentrations of vapours or gases. They are used in enclosed space or the soil to destroy the pest present. E.g. Phostoxin, pirimiphos-methyl and propagyl bromide.
- v. Systemic pesticides: These are pesticides that are soluble enough to be absorbed harmlessly by plant through their seeds, stems or foliage and can be translocated by the sap to the point of pest attack e.g. Dimethoate.
- vi. Repellants: These are common compounds that usually do not kill pests but are distasteful, or irritating enough to keep pests from feeding or drive them away for a while when applied to the host plant. Examples include: Ethyl hexanediol, which repels mosquito, biting flies and ticks.
- vii. Attractants: These are chemicals that act as lures for insects, for example, pheromones which function as mating, food, ovipositing, alarm and aggregating stimulants. They have been found and extracted from a number of insect species and can be synthesized in the laboratory.
- viii. Anticoagulants: These are usually rodenticides that cause internal bleeding and reduce the ability of blood clot. Most anticoagulants have to be eaten to be effective, and are prepared with bait to be placed along known runway or feeding sites. Examples include: Ethyl hexanediol Raccumin, Klerat and Warfarin.

Types of Formulations:

- Any particular active ingredient is often sold in several different kinds of formulations.
- You must choose the formulation that will be best for each use.
- In making your choice, consider: the plant, animal, or surface to be protected (phytotoxicity, animal absorption, pitting or marring surface),
- application equipment available and best suited for the job,
- hazard of drift and runoff (nearness to sensitive areas, likelihood of wind or rain),

- safety to applicator, helpers, and other humans and pets likely to be exposed,
- cost, type of environment in which the application must be made (agricultural, aquatic, forest, urban, etc.)

The common types of formulations include:

1. Wet formulations: These are pesticides in liquid forms and include the following:

- i. Concentrated solutions: these are pesticides soluble in water. They require dilution with water to the appropriate strength for spraying.
- ii. Emulsifiable concentrates: these are pesticides that are in the form of oils dispersed in water (oil-water-emulsion) or water dispersed in oil (water-oil-emulsion). They can be diluted with water to an appropriate strength.
- iii. Oily formulations: these are pesticides used straight without emulsification in water for ultra-low volume applications, ULVs (e.g. pirimor and cymbush).
- iv. Miscible liquids: here the technical product is usually a liquid and is dissolved in an organic solvent which is then diluted and dissolved in the water carrier.

2. Dry formulations: these are pesticides presented in solid or dry forms. Examples include:

- i. Wettable powders (WVP)- these are powdery pesticides that are miscible with water and readily form suspension as they do not resist water penetration.
- ii. Water dispersible powders – these are powdery pesticides that resist penetration of water. They remain as individual particles in suspension in water.
- iii. Dusts (dustable powders) – these pesticides contain the a.i. highly directed with an inert filler-finely ground e.g. apron plus, pestox, Rambo or pifpaf.
- iv. Wettable granules- these are pesticide formulation in small solid particles of about 2.5mm diameter. They are very safe to the applicator and to the environment. They are convenient for soil drillings to control soil insects and nematodes.
- v. Micro-encapsulations- these are insecticides encapsulated in a non-volatile casket of gelatin. They are very tiny capsules resembling a slightly coarse powder. They are usually non-toxic by contact, but are toxic to insects/human when ingested by them.

Pesticide Application Methods

The pesticide application method you choose depends on the nature and habits of the target pest, characteristics of the target site, properties of the pesticide, suitability of the application equipment, and cost and efficiency of

alternative methods. Your choice is often predetermined by one or more of these factors. The following are some common application methods:

- a) Directed-spray application—specifically targeting pests to minimize pesticide contact with nontarget plants and animals.
- b) Foliar application—directing pesticide to the leafy portions of a plant.
- c) Soil application—placing pesticide directly on or in the soil instead of on a growing plant.
- d) Soil incorporation—using tillage, rainfall, or irrigation equipment to move pesticide into the soil.
- e) Soil injection—applying a pesticide under pressure beneath the soil surface.
- f) Tree injection—applying pesticides under the bark of trees.
- g) Band application—applying a pesticide in parallel strips or bands, such as between or over rows of crops.
- h) Basal application—directing herbicides to the lower portions of bush or small trees.
- i) Broadcast application—uniformly applying a pesticide to an entire area or field.

• 24.4 PESTICIDE LABELING

- The pesticide label is the main method of communication between a pesticide manufacturer and pesticide users.
- The information printed on and attached to the pesticide container is the label.
- By law, pesticide users are required to comply with all instructions and use directions found on the pesticide product label.
- Labeling includes the label itself plus all other information about the product referenced on the label and given when you buy the product.
- For example, the labeling may include information that accompanies the product in the form of a comprehensive product-use manual, brochures, leaf lets, and/or Safety Data Sheets.
- Pesticide labeling includes instructions on how to use the product safely and correctly.
- Each pesticide you buy has a label that gives instructions on how to use the product. The manufacturer may also provide additional forms of labeling.

that name. The brand name shows up plainly on the front panel of the label. Applicators must beware of choosing a pesticide product by brand name alone.

- ii) **Ingredient Statement:** Each pesticide label must list what is in the product. The list is written so you can quickly see what the active ingredients are and the amount (in percentage) of each ingredient listed. The ingredient statement must list the official chemical names and/or common names for the active ingredients. Inert ingredients need not be named, but the label must show what percent of the total contents they comprise.
- iii) **Chemical Name:** The chemical name is a complex name which identifies the chemical components and structure of the pesticide. This name is almost always listed in the ingredient statement on the label. For example, the chemical name of atrazine is 2-chloro-4-ethylamino-6-isopropylamino-1, 3, 5-triazine.
- iv) **Common Name:** Because pesticides have complex chemical names, many are given a shorter “common” name. The official common name may be followed by the chemical name in the list of active ingredients. For example, a label with the brand name Sevin 50% WP would read: Active ingredient: carbaryl (1-naphthyl N methyl carbamate)..... 50%, Inert ingredients..... 50%. By purchasing pesticides according to the common or chemical names, you will always be certain of getting the right active ingredient.
- v) **Type of Pesticide:** The type of pesticide usually is listed on the front panel of the pesticide label. This short statement usually indicates in general terms what the product will control. Examples: insecticide for control of certain insects on fruits, nuts, and ornamentals; soil fungicide; herbicide for the control of trees, bush, and weeds.
- vi) **Net Contents:** The front panel of the pesticide label tells you how much is in the container. This can be expressed as pounds or ounces for dry formulations and as gallons, quarts, or pints for liquids. Liquid formulations may also list the pounds of active ingredient per gallon of product.
- vii) **Name and Address of Manufacturer:** The law requires the maker or distributor of a product to put the name and address of the company on the label. This is so you will know who made or sold the product.
- viii) **Registration and Establishment Numbers:** These numbers are needed by the pesticide applicator in case of accidental poisoning, claims of misuse, or liability claims. They are also used by regulatory agencies in cases of misbranding, adulterated products and other regulatory actions. An EPA registration number must appear on pesticide labels (for example, EPA

Reg. No. 3120-280). This indicates that the pesticide label has been approved by the federal government.

- ix) **Signal Words and Symbols:** Every label contains a signal word giving you a clue to how dangerous the product is to humans. Knowing the product's hazard helps you choose the proper precautionary measures for yourself, your workers, and other persons (or animals) which may be exposed. The signal word must appear in large letters on the front panel of the pesticide label. It immediately follows the statement, "Keep Out of Reach of Children," which must appear on every pesticide label. **DANGER**—This word signals you that the pesticide is highly toxic. A taste to a teaspoon taken by mouth could kill an average-sized adult. Any product which is highly toxic orally, dermally, or through inhalation or causes severe eye and skin burning will be labeled "DANGER." All pesticides which are highly toxic orally, dermally, or through inhalation will also carry the word **POISON** printed in red and the skull and crossbones symbol. **WARNING**—This word signals you that the product is moderately toxic. As little as a teaspoon to a tablespoon by mouth could kill the average-sized adult. Any product which is moderately toxic orally, dermally, or through inhalation or causes moderate eye and skin irritation will be labeled **WARNING**. **CAUTION**—This word signals you that the product is slightly toxic. An ounce to more than a pint taken by mouth could kill the average adult. Any product which is slightly toxic orally, dermally, or through inhalation or causes slight eye and skin irritation will be labeled **CAUTION**.
- x) **Precautionary Statements:** All pesticide labels contain statements to help you decide what precautions to take to protect yourself, other people, or animals from pesticide exposure. Sometimes these statements are listed under the heading "Hazards to Humans and Domestic Animals." Precautionary statements may be found in several sections of the label.
- xi) **Routes of Entry Statements:** Routes of entry statements indicate which route or routes of entry into the human body are particularly hazardous. Because many pesticide products are hazardous by more than one route, you should study these statements carefully.
- xii) **First Aid Statements:** First aid statements (formerly known as the Statement of practical Treatment) list emergency treatments recommended in case of poisoning or accidental exposure. Typical statements include:
- a) In case of contact with skin, wash immediately with plenty of soap and clean water.

- b) In case of contact with eyes, flush with water for 15 minutes and get medical attention.
 - c) In case of inhalation exposure, remove victim from contaminated area and give artificial respiration, if necessary.
 - d) If swallowed, induce vomiting.
- xiii) **Environmental Hazards:** Pesticides can be harmful to the environment. Look for special warning statements on the label concerning environmental hazards. The label will say if a particular pesticide is especially hazardous to wildlife. Examples include:
- a) This product is highly toxic to bees.
 - b) This product is extremely toxic to fish and aquatic invertebrates.
 - c) This product is toxic to birds and other wildlife.

Special toxicity statements alert you to the special hazards of a product. They will help you choose the safest product for a particular job and remind you to take extra precautions.

xiv) **Storage and Disposal:** All pesticide labels contain instructions for the appropriate storage and disposal of the pesticide, its remnant, and its container. State and local laws may vary considerably, so specific instructions usually are not included. These statements typically appear in the “Storage and Disposal” section of the label or under headings such as “Important,” “Note,” or “General Instructions.” Examples include:

- a) Store herbicides away from fertilizers, insecticides, fungicides, seeds, and food/feed items.
- b) Store at temperatures above 32°F (0°C).
- c) Non-refillable container. Do not reuse or refill this container.
- d) Do not contaminate water, food, or feed by storage or disposal.
- e) Triple rinse container promptly after emptying, and put content in to sprayer
- f) Puncture and dispose off in a sanitary landfill appropriately.

LIST OF BANNED PESTICIDE IN NIGERIA

S/N	PESTICIDE	CATEGORY	STATUS
1	ALDRIN	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
2	BINAPACRYL	FUNGICIDE	BANNED
3	CAPTAFOL	FUNGICIDE	BANNED
4	CHLORDANE	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
5	CHLORDIMEFORM	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
6	DDT	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
7	DIELDRIN	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
8	DINOSEB & DINOSEB SALTS	HERBICIDE	BANNED

9	HEPTACHLOR	HERBICIDE	BANNED
10	LINDANE	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
11	ETHYLENE DICHLORIDE	FUMIGANTS	BANNED
12	PARATHION	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
13	METHYL PARATHION	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
14	PHOSPHAMIDON	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
15	MONOCROPTOPHOS	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
16	METHAMIDOPHOS	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
17	CHLOROBENZILATE	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
18	TOXAPHENE	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
19	PENTACHLOROPHENOL	HERBICIDE, INSECTICIDE	BANNED
20	ETHYLENE OXIDE	FUMIGANT, DISINFECTANT	BANNED
21	HCF (MIXED ISOMERS)/BHC	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
22	EDB(1,2-DIBROMOETHENE)	FUMIGANT	BANNED
23	2,4,5 TRICHLOROPHENOXY ACETIC ACID	HERBICIDE	BANNED
24	ENDRIN	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
24	MIREX	INSECTICIDE	BANNED
26	ETHYLENE DIBROMIDE	FUMIGANT	BANNED
27	HEXACHLOROBENZENE	FUNGICIDE	BANNED
28	ENDOSULPHAN	ACARICIDE, INSECTICIDE	BANNED
29	DELTA HCH	AGRICUTURAL INSECTICIDE	BANNED
30	FLOURACETAMIDE	RODENTICIDE	BANNED

- xv) **Directions for Use:** The “Directions for Use” section provides instructions on how to use the product. These instructions cover:
- a) The pests that the manufacturer claims the product will control.
 - b) The crop, animal, or site the product is intended to protect.
 - c) The proper mixing instructions.
 - d) How much to use (rate) and how often.
 - e) How close to harvest the product can be applied.
 - f) Phytotoxicity (damage to plants) and other possible injury.
 - g) Where and when the material should be applied.
 - h) Plant-back, composting, grazing, and other restrictions.
 - i) How to minimize drift.

EFFECT OF PESTICIDES ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Modern technology is constantly placing stress on biological and physical processes that sustain the ecological system in which man lives. Assessing the present practices in handling and application of agrochemicals, particularly pesticides, is the first step towards improving utilization and minimizing their harmful effect on man and the environment. The adverse effect of pesticides on the environment may be caused by the following:

1. Many of the pesticides being used are organochlorines: These chemicals have high persistence coupled with their ability to accumulate along the food chain. Most rural farmers handle these pesticide products without caution, endangering themselves, their families, livestock and the environment. These products are toxic in nature and most people are not aware of the health risk associated with their use.
2. Toxicity to non-target organisms: Pesticides directly or indirectly affect non-target organisms such as bees, especially the wild type that are very common in Nigeria, with a consequence of decrease in both plant pollination and honey production. Predators are also harmed through the consumption of poisoned prey. Consequently their egg-shells develop abnormally causing them to break more easily.
3. Toxicity to beneficial insects: Pesticide misuse has a negative impact on beneficial insects, which other insects need for their subsistence and the preservation of their species (e.g. parasites are often destroyed along with the pest and can no longer exercise their regulatory functions). This usually leads to the development of problems with new pests or an increased outbreak of existing pest whose damage continue to increase until it becomes relatively significant. Most pesticides in use in Nigeria have the disadvantage of low selectivity; they harm both beneficial organisms as well as the target pest.
4. Development of resistance by target pests: Pesticide misuse also leads to the development of pesticide resistance by the insect pests. In most instances the more the pesticide is sprayed, the more frequent the treatment and the faster the development of resistance. This is because the detoxification mechanism of the insect now responds faster and more effectively. There are about 47 resistant insect species and mites, most of which are well-known pest of crops and many of these insects are resistant to one or more substance group.
5. Interfere with decomposition process in the soil: The presence of pesticides directly or indirectly influences soil microfauna and can alter

decomposition of organic matter. Pesticides residues in the soil can be directly toxic to soil organisms or can exert subtle effects by influencing their activities, behavior, reproduction and metabolism. Soil organisms such as earthworms suffer strong toxic reaction due to the use of chlordane, heptachlor and HCH even at the recommended dosages.

6. Reduction of soil fertility:

- A large proportion of pesticide being used end up in the soils and open water bodies.
- It is common for most pesticide users to pour away left-over without thought.
- The breakdown of active ingredient of pesticide into several decomposition products and from these into natural soil components occurs less quickly.
- Pesticide misuse contaminates soil and produce adverse effect on soil fertility in a number of ways.
- These include the direct effect of decimating population of soil organisms, and indirect effects such as eradication of prey and predatory soil insects,
- and accumulation of toxic substances such as lead and mercury.
- Pesticides also bring out changes in the substances contained in plants. For example 2, 4, D increase nitrogen content in maize plants, this leads to increase in aphid concentrations.

7. Water pollution: Pesticide contamination of ground water is of great health concern. Heavy metal pollution in the drinking water has a debilitating consequence; it attacks many organs and tissues throughout the body including digestive, nervous and excretory organs. Water pollution by pesticides also causes destruction of aquatic micro and macroflora and fauna such as zooplanktons, phytoplanktons, arthropod larvae, as well as aquatic invertebrates and vertebrates.

8. Air pollution: Air pollution by pesticide is the most studied environmental hazard to human and livestock health. However, Its impact is grossly underestimated. More than half of the amount of pesticide applied may go directly into the atmosphere during spraying. Pesticides contaminate the air in the atmosphere in various ways: through wind drift during spraying, evaporation of active ingredients from the surface of plants and soil and through wind erosion of contaminated soils. These may cause adverse effects on the environment, including damage to the ozone layer leading to global warming.

• 24.5 SAFETY PRECAUTIONS WHEN HANDLING PESTICIDES

Pesticides are toxic chemicals therefore they must be handled with extreme care. Most farmers and junior level extension workers have no formal training or information on proper use of pesticides – majority of them take no precautions when working with pesticide. The result is that pesticides are handled, transported and applied in a way that can lead to deadly consequences. It is therefore critical to observe the following:

- A. Before buying the chemical ask the following questions:
 - ✓ Which pest is to be controlled?
 - ✓ How much damage has the pest done?
 - ✓ What are the recommended pesticides for the pest problem?
 - ✓ Which is the least toxic and least persistent among the recommended pesticides?
- B. When buying pesticides observe the following:
 - ✓ Buy only from reputable and reliable licensed dealer- never buy in the open markets
 - ✓ Buy only as much as you expect to use within a short period – never buy in bulk
 - ✓ Buy pesticides only in their original packages with proper labeling
 - ✓ Never buy banned, restricted or highly toxic pesticides.
- C. When transporting pesticides:
 - ✓ Avoid carrying them on public transport if possible (especially large quantities).
 - ✓ Do not transport pesticides together with food products, animal feeds or other commodities.
 - ✓ Make sure the pesticide containers are not leaking or spilling out.
 - ✓ If the pesticide has leaked or spilled out, wash the vehicle that was used for the transportation. For this purpose, apply bleaching lime paste (1kg of lime for every 4 litres of water) and wash it off with water twice or thrice within an hour after offloading.
- D. When storing pesticides:
 - ✓ Do not keep them in the kitchen or living room. Keep them away, from food, animal feed or fodder and container of water or food
 - ✓ Keep pesticides locked away and ensure that they are out of reach of children and pets, preferably store pesticides in a separate room that is well ventilated and away from sunlight, fire and water.
 - ✓ To avoid cross – contamination, store herbicides separately from insecticides.
 - ✓ Do not keep human and animal medicine together with pesticides.

- ✓ Reseal containers after partial use.
- E. During application:
- ✓ Read the label and the instructions very carefully before opening the pesticide container or use
 - ✓ Never work alone while handling or applying pesticides
 - ✓ Never allow children, animals or unauthorized people near the site of mixing and application.
 - ✓ While mixing, add the chemical to water and never water to the chemical in order to avoid instantaneous reactions. Pour the liquids carefully to avoid splashing, avoid pesticides blowing into your face – mix with a long stick to prevent splashing liquids onto your hands. Mix pesticides only in the field to be sprayed. Never mix pesticides at home.
 - ✓ Never eat, drink or smoke while mixing or applying pesticides.
 - ✓ Wear protective clothing such as rubber boots, a rubber apron, goggles, facemask and respirator. If a face mask is not available, cover your mouth and nose with a clean cloth. Never wear loose clothing (e.g. floppy gown) during mixing and application, keep a clean set of clothing to wear after handling and applying pesticides.
 - ✓ Avoid application of pesticides on rainy or cloudy days.
 - ✓ Spray early in the morning or in the evening; suspend spraying during midday in the hot weather to avoid pesticide decomposition by sun.
 - ✓ Avoid excessive spraying to prevent pesticide drip on to the soil.
 - ✓ Use the correct nozzle for the type of pesticide e.g. use only fan nozzle for herbicides and cone nozzle for insecticides.
 - ✓ Maintain the correct pressure of the spraying equipment in order to prevent over or under application.
 - ✓ Check the wind direction before starting to spray. Start spraying at the downwind edge of the field and move upwind so you are always moving into an unsprayed area. Always move along the wind while spraying and dusting so that the spray or dust is directed by air current away from you.
 - ✓ Always know the size of the farm in order to determine the amount of chemical to use.
 - ✓ Never spray when there are strong winds.
 - ✓ Avoid spraying when large number of bees are visiting the crop (during flowering)
 - ✓ Use a broom stick or pin to clear out clogged nozzles or hoses- never blow with your mouth.
 - ✓ Make sure you have a first aid box close by in case of any accident.
- F. After Application:
- ✓ Take bath and change your clothes immediately after spraying

- ✓ All clothes must be washed immediately after spraying – wash them separately from other clothes.
- ✓ Never leave pesticide in the sprayers or dusters. Clean the equipment with soap, detergent, or soda solution and fresh water. Rinse with clean water at least twice before returning the equipment to store.
- ✓ Dispose of all empty pesticide containers by burning or burying them in the field.
- ✓ Do not use them to store food, water, or as cooking utensils. Never sell empty containers to hawkers because they might end up being misused.
- ✓ Return unused pesticide to the store and keep it under lock and key.
- ✓ Never go into a treated field until the recommended safety period (waiting period) has passed.
- ✓ Sick persons e.g. asthmatic patients must never come into contact with pesticides.

G. Waiting Period.

Pesticides leave residues on crops. Observe the waiting period specified on the label or recommended by skilled extension workers. The waiting period depends on the type of crop, the pesticide used, and the dosage. Waiting period is the minimum length of time you must wait after applying the pesticide before it is safe to harvest the crop. Never harvest crops (especially vegetables) until the waiting period for the pesticide has passed.

SAFETY PRECAUTIONS FOR USING SPRAYERS

1. Always calibrate a sprayer, and check for leaks before spraying.
2. Sprayers should always be shut off when nozzles are to be cleared or changed.
3. Concentrated chemicals should not be put into an empty tank, the tank should be half-filled with water first before adding the chemical.
4. When changing from one chemical to another, the tank should be drained first and washed twice with clean water and detergents. All filters should be rinsed properly.
5. Make sure pressure gauge is working properly.
6. Do not allow chemicals to remain in tank for long period of time during storage.
7. At the end of the day's work, drain and flush tank,
8. Grease all moving parts to prevent rust.

- **24.6 TYPES OF SPRAYING EQUIPMENT AND SPRAYER CALIBRATION**

Most pesticides employed in chemical control require some form of carrier for applying the chemical. For dry or powdered chemicals, air is most commonly used as the carrier and the machine employing this principle is called Duster. But when the chemical to be applied is in a liquid form, water or oil is most commonly used as the carrier and the machine is called a Sprayer. Sometimes however, both air and liquids are used as carriers for the chemical and the equipment used here is the Mist Blower.

Dusters: The duster may be either manually operated or powered. The powered type may be either shoulder mounted, belly mounted or tractor mounted using the P.T.O. During dusting operation the prevailing wind direction should be used to carry the dust to the target.

Sprayers: These are machines used to spray previously mixed agricultural chemicals in the form of solutions (a chemical completely dissolved in water), suspensions (a powdered chemical floating in water-requiring constant agitation) or an emulsion (a dispersed liquid chemical in an un-dissolved form in water). There are various types of sprayers viz.

I. Hand operated sprayers

a. Sprayers with hydraulic nozzles designed with systems to generate pressures at the nozzle to achieve correct atomization (breaking liquid into droplets). There are 2 types: lever operated knapsack sprayers and compression sprayers.

i. Lever operated knapsack sprayers

These types of sprayers are made up of a 10 – 20 litre tank with a basket filter and a wide neck for easy filling and cleaning, a lever-operated pump and pressure chamber, and hose and lance with a trigger operated valve. The pumps are either diaphragm types (suitable for herbicide application when large droplets are required to minimize drift), or the piston type (more suitable for insecticide and fungicide application where smaller droplets are required). With lever operated sprayers the pressure is introduced into the tank during spraying e.g. the CP 15 and motorized knapsack sprays.

ii. The compression sprayers

This is similar in structure to the lever operated sprayer. The only difference is that the pressure is introduced into the tank before spraying—even before putting the chemical in the tank. Its main advantage is having a wide range of droplet size to take care of wide range of pest types. However it requires large volumes of water e.g. the tractor or aircraft mounted Boom Sprayers.

b. Rotary atomizers that generate spray droplets from a spinning disc or cup. These are for very low volumes of spray liquid per hectare e.g. the electrodyne sprayer. This type of sprayer must never be used for broad spectrum weed killers such as paraquat (as the concentrations may exceed the recommended dilution rates).

2. Mechanically operated sprayers

These are the tractor mounted Boom sprayers for large scale farming mentioned earlier and the Aircraft sprayers— usually owned by Federal Government for spraying pesticides over large areas in the event of an epidemic. There are the fixed wing aircraft sprayers and the Rotary wing Helicopter Sprayers.

COMPONENTS OF A SPRAYER

Major components of sprayer are the tank, filter, pump, pressure regulator, hose, shut-off valve, sprayer lance or boom and nozzles.

- 1. Tank:** Tank is an important part of the sprayer used to hold spray liquid. It must be sufficient enough to carry liquid, easy to refill, drain and clean. Tank should be corrosive resistant and equipped with appropriate opening, hoses and agitation devise and must also have marking to ensure accurate measurement. Size of the tank depends on the size of the sprayer. A good spraying tank must be made from galvanized steel, stainless steel, aluminum, fiberglass or polypropylene. Tank must have some provision for agitating the spray mixture.
- 2. Pump:** Pump provides pressure for pumping the spray mixture out of the spraying tank to the nozzles through the lance. Depending on the size of the sprayer, the pump can be powered by power take-off (in case of tractor driven sprayer), gasoline engine, airplane, battery (in case of electro dyne sprayer) or manually operated (hand and knapsack sprayer).
- 3. Pressure regulator:** This is used for pressure regulation and preventing damage to the pump that may occur when spraying is interrupted.
- 4. Hose:** Hose must have sufficient strength to withstand the pressure or vacuum expected. They are usually made from materials that will tolerate the spray chemicals.
- 5. Filter or Strains:** Filters are used at the tank opening, spray lance, and at the nozzles. They are used to remove extraneous materials and large lumps of pesticides that may block nozzles. They are of different mesh sizes. Filters are needed to prevent clogging by particulate materials.
- 6. Lance/Boom:** Lance holds the nozzle through which the spray droplets are forced out under pressure generated by pumping device. Lance carries only one nozzle (in case of knapsack of hand spryer). Where lance carries multiple nozzles, it is called boom (common in tractor driven sprayers).

7. **Nozzles:** These are devices attached to the sprayer for producing required droplets and spray patterns of the desired chemical. It is a precision device that facilitates dispersion of liquid into spray. Nozzles are used for three purposes: to distribute a liquid over an area, to increase liquid surface area, and create impact force on a solid surface. Pressure generated by the pump help in converting the spray mixtures into droplets and squeeze out through spray nozzles. The size of the droplets can be altered through the use of different nozzle sizes, or by altering the pressure under which it is forced, or a combination of both.

TYPES OF NOZZLES

1. Flood jet nozzle (also called deflector, impact or anvil nozzles): they produce droplets by the impact of a straight jet of liquid onto a deflector surface which produces a wide range of flat spray patterns. Flood jet nozzles used at low pressures are ideally suited for herbicide applications.

2. Flat fan nozzles: these have elliptical orifices which produces a narrow lens-shaped pattern with the highest spray deposit occurring immediately below the nozzle and amount of spray reducing towards edges of the fan. This requires overlapping of the swaths to achieve even deposit on the target. They are suitable on tractor or aircraft booms. They are good for spraying flat surfaces (soils, floors, walls or buildings).

3. Cone nozzles: they consist of nozzle tips (or orifice disc) and a swirl plate. They are of two types:

i. Hollow cone nozzle: this gives a hollow cone shaped spray pattern giving out droplets from more directions than in the single plane produced by the fan nozzle. This is obtained through motion of the liquid between the cone and the nozzle. They are very suitable for spraying fungicides and insecticides on to crop foliage.

ii. Solid cone nozzle: here the cone or swirl plate has a central hole in addition to the angled slot, the centre of the cone is filled with droplets to produce smaller spray angles and larger droplets. They are suitable for spot treatments of chemicals or for achieving greater downward penetration of sprays (good on tractor or air craft booms)

SPRAYER CALIBRATION

Accurate calibration of spraying equipment is essential if pesticides and/or other agro-chemicals are to be used safely and effectively. A sub lethal dose of spray will fail to give satisfactory control of pests. An overdose on the other hand, will increase cost besides killing a crop or resulting in accumulation of toxic residues in the soil. Prevention of crop injury, good pest control, good

economy and environmental considerations are among the reasons for careful calibration of sprayers. Taking time to calibrate each sprayer before use is essential to ensure that pesticides are used safely and economically at all times. Although the quantity of pesticides to be used for a given pest problem may be accurately calculated and put into a sprayer, it still has to be accurately and uniformly distributed on the target. Sprayer calibration should be taken seriously; good knowledge of sprayer calibration procedures should be made an integral part of practical training in pests' managements.

The objective of all sprayer calibrations is to ensure that sprayer uniformly distributes pesticides solution at the dose per unit area of the target and at the volume rate recommended. Since pesticides are always applied in small doses, they have to be diluted in sufficient carrier to permit a uniform distribution of the pesticide on the target. Sprayer calibration is particularly necessary for sprayers equipped with hydraulic nozzles. This is because there is a wide selection of nozzles and these have different capacities (flow rates), spray angles and spray patterns. In addition, there are differences between sprayers with respect to pump capacities and other structural features. Even for the same sprayer, operated at the same pressure and using the same nozzles, there will be variations in sprayer output in relation to the walking speed of the operator and application conditions. It is therefore important that the sprayer be calibrated in order to accurately determine its output per unit time and space.

The rate at which the pesticide solution is pushed towards the nozzle is determined by the pressure on the liquid inside the tank in the case of sprayers with pressurized tanks, or on the pressure imposed on the liquid in the pipe for powered sprayers. In the case of hand-held Controlled Droplet Application (CDA) sprayers, where the liquid is fed to the nozzle by gravity, a constant walking speed of one meter per second is all that is needed to ensure uniform application of pesticides in most field situations. However, volume rate in CDA sprayers can be altered by changing the orifice disc which controls the flow rate of the spray solution in the sprayer.

Calibration of Knapsack Sprayers

Knapsack sprayers are very easy to calibrate and use. However, it is common for farmers to have no idea of the application rate of their sprayers. Before beginning calibration it is important to check out the sprayer to make sure all parts are working properly. First clean the sprayer, set the pressure gauge to the pressure setting at which the sprayer will be operated and fill the tank with water. Pump to pressurize the tank, and check the sprayer for leaks. Give a gentle squeeze that should be noted and maintained during pesticide application. For example, an operator can maintain a swath width of 1.2m for

three nozzles of different spray angles by changing nozzle heights. There are two easy-to-follow procedures for calibrating knapsack sprayers. These are the area-volume method and the time-volume method.

a. The time-volume method

Proceed as follows:

1. Peg out a 100m² area (Test Plot), (10m x 10m, but preferably 4m x 25m to allow for a reasonable walking distance).
2. Add water to the tank, to two-thirds of full capacity.
3. Walk at a pace comfortable to you, and spray the marked-out area (test plot) using a moderate pump pressure. Record the time taken to spray the test plot.
4. Repeat step 3 at least twice for reproducibility, and each time record the time taken to spray the test plot (e.g. 30s).
5. Fill the sprayer once again, and this time spray into a measuring jug using the same operating conditions and time as used in step 3 and 4 above. Note the volume of solution collected.
6. Repeat step 5 at least twice more, and note the average volume collected (e.g. 1.5L). This is the volume rate of your knapsack sprayer.
7. Calculate the delivery rate of the sprayer from the data in steps 1 to 6 as follows:

(i) Determine area of test plot:

From step 1 above, the area of the test plot = 0.01 ha.

(ii) Determine area rate of sprayer:

From step 4, time required to spray test plot = 30s.

Therefore, area rate

$$= 0.01 \text{ ha} \div 30\text{s}$$

$$= \frac{0.01 \text{ ha} \times 60\text{s}}{30\text{s} \times 1 \text{ min}}$$

$$= 0.02 \text{ ha min}^{-1}$$

(iii) Determine volume rate:

From step 6 above, volume collected = 1.5 liters

Therefore, volume rate

$$= 1.5 \text{ L} \div 30\text{s}$$

$$= \frac{1.5 \text{ L} \times 60\text{s}}{30\text{s} \times 1 \text{ min}}$$

$$= 3.0 \text{ L min}^{-1}$$

(iv) Determine application rate of sprayer:

Application rate (l/ha)

$$= \frac{\text{Volume rate}}{\text{Area rate}}$$

$$= \frac{3.07 \text{Lmin}^{-1}}{0.02 \text{ha min}^{-1}} = 150 \text{L ha}^{-1}$$

This is the application rate of the sprayer. For pesticide solutions the 180 liters represents a solution made up of the pesticides and the diluents. The information from sprayer calibration is useful in determining the quantity of water needed for diluting herbicides during spray applications. Sprayer should be thoroughly washed with detergent after used. A sprayer will give many years of trouble-free service if properly handled and maintained.

b. Area-Volume method

1. Measure the spray swath width (e.g. 1 metre)
2. Calculate how many metres need to be sprayed to cover 100 m² (e.g. 100/1 = 100 metres)
3. Fill spray tank to the full mark
4. Spray over the required distance (100 metres in this case) at a comfortable pace and at a speed which is sustainable in a normal field spraying condition (considering trees, stones, hills etc).
5. Measure the quantity of water needed to refill the sprayer to the full mark (e.g. 2 litres)
6. To obtain the volume sprayed over 1 hectare (10,000 m²), multiply the volume sprayed over 100 m² by 100 (i.e. 2 x 100 = 200 litres per hectare).
7. Read the product label to check that this volume is similar to the recommended volume range. If achieved volume is more than 10% outside the recommended volume on the chemical label, change the nozzle to one which will give a higher or lower output. If the nozzle has to be changed, it is necessary to repeat the calibration exercise from the beginning.

Proper Mixing of Pesticides

Before mixing pesticides, read the label of the pesticides container to determine the proper mixtures. Wear protective cloth while mixing pesticides. Mix in a grassy area. Do not mix on concrete or hard surface. Only use water unless directed by the label to use another liquid. Fill the sprayer with two-third of the water needed. Then add the proper amount of pesticides. Then add the remaining one-third of water. Mix only the amount necessary to the job. Great care should be taken to prevent or minimize direct contact or exposure between the pesticides and applicator during mixing. In developed countries, pesticides mixing are done in closed pesticides mixing systems. The chemicals are provided in closed shipping containers from which the pesticides are withdrawn and mixed with water for storage in spray tank.

It is desirable to dilute chemicals before using them in the fields in order to avoid toxicity to the crops and the operator. However, the dilution or mixing requires careful understanding of the instructions in the label of the chemical container. Mixing must be done in well ventilated places. There are different mixing procedures for different pesticides –usually written on the container label.

Quantity of Pesticide Required

In commercial liquid formulations, a certain volume of the toxicant is dissolved in a certain volume of its solvent with an emulsifying agent. The concentration of the active ingredient is thus expressed in two ways.

1. As a percentage

$$\% \text{ active ingredient in EC} = \frac{\text{Weight of active ingredient} \times 100}{\text{Volume of EC}}$$

Where EC = Emulsifiable concentrate

$$2. \text{ As grams per litre} = \frac{\text{Weight of a.i.}}{\text{Volume}}$$

a.i.= Active ingredient.

Example 1: A recommendation calls for 1.5 Kg/ha of carbaryl to control rice stem borers and an emulsifiable concentrate containing 50% carbaryl is available. How many litres of this formulation are needed to treat 8000 m²?

$$\text{Amount required} = \frac{\text{Recommended rate (Kg/ha)} \times \text{Area (m}^2\text{)} \times 100\%}{\% \text{ a.i.} \times 10,000}$$

$$\text{Amount required} = \frac{1.5 \times 8000 \times 100}{50 \times 10,000} = 8 \text{ litres}$$

Example 2: You were asked to apply 0.25 Kg a.i./ha of 5% Carbofuran granules to control certain pest. What amount of the pesticides would you require in Kg per hectare?

$$\text{Quantity required} = \frac{0.25 \text{ kg} \times 100}{5} = 5 \text{ Kg granules/ha}$$

Example 3: How many Kg of Basudin 10G granules is needed to control pink stem borer in a 2500m² farm if the recommended rate is 2 Kg a.i./ha.

Solution: Basudin 10G means a 10% a.i.

$$= \frac{2\text{Kg/ha} \times 2,500 \times 100}{10 \times 10,000} = 5\text{Kg}$$

However, where there are no skilled personnel to undertake the mathematical calculations above certain agencies have suggested the use of the chemical container caps, empty milk tin or APC bottles. For most insecticides during field controls 4 chemical container caps (approximately 1 empty milk tin or 1.5 APC bottle) is dissolved in one tank full sprayer of water. For pest control in stores 2 caps or ½ empty milk tin of pesticide is dissolved in tank full if highly maximized to achieve full control. These methods are however very crude and may not be effective especially when using herbicides.

Quantity of Water Required

The quantity of water required to dilute the calculated amount of pesticides required depend on sprayer calibration. For this reason therefore it is a rule that the person that did the calibration should be the same person to spray because the volume spray depend on the working speed, pumping pressure and nozzle height (in case of knapsack sprayer)

How to Make Tank Mixtures

It is extremely important that you add the components of the mixture in the order that the label specify; sometimes whether the pesticides are physically compatible or not depend on the order in which you add them to the tank. This is especially true for pesticides that are packed in water-soluble packets. A mistake in mixing or order could prevent uniform distribution of the pesticides in the spraying tank. The label will provide mixing instruction for all registered tank mixes. Sometimes pesticides labels do not provide adequate mixing order direction. The usual method is to fill the tank one-quarter to one-half full with the carrier and begin agitation. If you need to add a compatibility buffering, or deforming agent, these product should be added before the other product. Next, slowly add and thoroughly mix the pesticides products, one at a time, beginning with those hardest to mix. Generally wettable powders (WP) and dry flowables or water dispersible granules (DF, WDG) products should be added first followed by flowable (F, FL) and microencapsulated (ME) products. Add emulsifiable concentrate (EC) next, followed by any solution (S) or soluble powder (SP) products. Any crop oil and/or surfactant should be added last. Dry formulations and EC's should be mixed with little water before adding them to the spray tank, and finally continue to add your carrier to the desired level. To make sure you have uniform spray mixture at all times, keep the mixture agitated during the entire application until the tank is empty. Do not allow it to stand overnight without agitation.

• 24.6 APPLYING PESTICIDES DURING STORAGE

The use of pesticides for storage should be done only if other cultural, biological or physical methods do not suffice. Cereals and legumes must be dried to a very safe moisture content before storage. The following is recommended for some cereals:

Maize – 12.5%; sorghum – 10.5% millet – 12%; wheat – 14%, rice – 13%.

For safe application of pesticides during storage, the following steps should be followed:

a. **Disinfesting the storage facilities:** The storage facility should be disinfested with persistent pesticides with contact action against storage pests. They can be sprayed on walls, floors and ceilings prior to storage. Examples are:

1. **Organo phosphorous compounds:** These include malathion, dichlorvos (DDVP), bromophos and pirimiphos – methyl (Actellic). The latter (actellic) is likely to replace the others because of its low toxicity to man and warm blooded animals and its non-irritant action. It kills insects by contact and the effect of its vapour. It proves effective on most insects and mites in the store. It has excellent knockdown effect and is persistent for several months. The effective dose of Actellic according to WHO is 10g a.i. per ton of grain.

2. **Chlorpyrifos –methyl (2 – 4%) 'Reldan'** This has low vapour pressure and is very persistent, therefore it is effective against larvae from eggs laid before treatment. The effective dose according to WHO is 10g a.i. per ton of grain. Disinfesting the storage facility may not kill insects already established in the grains, fumigation may be needed.

b. **Fumigation:** Fumigants are chemicals, which at the required temperature and pressure can exist in the gaseous state. They can diffuse and penetrate even tightly packed materials to kill a given insect pest. Fumigants are available in solid, liquid or gas formulations. Most fumigants are inflammable and highly toxic to humans and animals, they should therefore be handled under skilled guidance. They are not suitable for small-scale agriculture. Fumigants are effective in killing field pests carried over to the stores. The simplest fumigant that can be handled by even unskilled persons is phosphorous hydrogen (a broad spectrum insecticide) available in small pellets (phostoxin). Others are: Aluminium phosphide (rat bomb), Methyl bromide (a gaseous fumigant now replaced by propargyl bromide) and carbon tetrachloride (liquid fumigant).

Phostoxin

Phostoxin tablets or pellets required for the fumigation may be scattered over the surface or probed into the grain using a rigid PVC pipe about 5 to 7 feet in length and having a diameter of 1-1/4 inches. For smaller storage the tablet may be wrap in a piece of cotton cloth and probed into grain.

c. The use of protectants: Protectants are chemicals, which are mixed with freshly harvested products in order to prevent attack and infestation by pests. Currently the only approved protectants for cereals meant for human consumption are a mixture of pyrethrins and piperonylbutoxide (0.05%) and malathion 10ppm a. i. (1 mg/ kg of seeds). With the use of protectants fumigation may not be necessary.

HOW TO DETERMINE THE RIGHT QUANTITY OF PESTICIDES TO APPLY ON GRAINS DURING STORAGE

The first step in determining the right quantity of pesticide to apply on grains for storage is to know the capacity or volume of the store, this can be determined by:

- i – Calculating the surface area x the height of the store.
- ii -Deducting the area that is not useful (paths or gangways) within the store from the volume above to obtain the useful volume.

Example 1:

A rectangular store has a length of 50m, width of 10m and height of 4m with two 1m wide paths running along the length of the store and a central path 2m wide also running along the 34 length of the store, and two 1m paths along the walls, plus another three 2m wide paths.

The useful volume or capacity of the store will be given by:

Useful length: $50 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 2 - 2 = 42\text{m}$

Useful width: $10 - 1 - 1 - 2 = 6\text{m}$

Useful surface area: $42 \times 6 = 252 \text{ m}^2$

Useful volume (store capacity) = $252 \times 4 = 1008\text{m}^3$

Example 2:

Calculate the quantity (tons) of millet grains in bags that can be safely kept in the store in the above example:

Solution:

Since millet in bags will occupy $1.2\text{m}^3/\text{ton}$ and the capacity or useful volume of the store is 1008m^2 , then $1008/1.2 = 840$ tons of millet in bags.

The second step is to know the volume of space occupied by the products to be stored.

Volume of space occupied by principal grains

Grains	m^3/ton
Groundnut seeds in bags	1.7
Groundnuts in their shells in bulk	3.5
Wheat in bags	1.5
Wheat in bulk	1.2
Millet in bags	1.2
Maize in bulk	1.4
Maize in bags	1.6
Husked rice in bags	1.2
Paddy rice in bags	1.9

The third step is to calculate the quantities of insecticides to be used in the store as per the manufacturer's recommendation in the insecticide container label or in literature.

Because most insecticides are marketed in the concentrate form, it becomes necessary to dilute them before use in order to achieve meaningful control.

Example:

A $20,000\text{m}^3$ store is to be treated with 1% w/v E.C. at a rate of 1.7 liters mist spray per 300m^3 . What is the quantity of concentrated 75% w/v EC needed to treat the whole store?

Solution:

$$1.7 \text{ liters} = 300\text{m}^3$$

$$x \text{ liters} = 20,000\text{m}^3 \div 300 \times 1.7 = 113.3 \text{ liters for } 2000\text{m}^3$$

If the pesticide is of 75% w/v concentration we will need:

$$\text{For } 1\% \text{ w/v} = 113.3 \text{ liters required}$$

$$\text{For } 75\% = 113.3/75 = 1.5 \text{ liters}$$

PRECAUTIONS DURING GRAIN STORAGE WITH CHEMICALS

1. Ensure that the right quantities of pesticides are used for treating the foodstuff, the use of pesticides at excessive dosages or lower doses does not provide good protection.

2. Ensure proper time lag between pesticide application for storage and consumption of the foodstuff.
3. Avoid use of very poisonous or banned pesticides such as organochlorines (e.g. BHC and lindane).
4. Always wear facemasks, protective clothing and gloves when applying pesticides.
5. Operators should never work alone, smoke drink or eat during treatment.
6. Ensure absence of humans or domestic animals in the treatment area during or immediately after pesticide application.
7. Ventilate the store at the end of the treatment period.
8. Clear out residues of the pesticide at the end of the treatment period.
9. Destroy empty chemical containers to prevent its re-usage
10. Wash any area of the skin that has become contaminated with the chemical immediately.
11. Take bath with clean water and soap and wash clothes worn immediately after spraying.

• 24.7 HERBICIDE APPLICATION

What is herbicide?

Herbicide is any substance deliberately formulated and used to control weeds. They can also be called weed killers or weedicide, it may be chemicals or pathogens used to suppressor kill plants, or to severely disrupt their normal growth process.

Classification of herbicides

Herbicides are classified on the basis of:

- i. Time of application
- ii. Target of application
- iii. Mobility in plants
- iv. Chemical structure of the active ingredients

Time of application

Herbicides are classified based on the time of application into pre-plant, pre-emergence and post- emergence treatments.

- ✓ Pre-plant incorporated (PPI) herbicides are volatile thus they are applied on the soil and then incorporated.
- ✓ Pre-emergence herbicide (PE) no influence on established weeds thus they are applied before germination and emergence of weed to act on their seeds, e.g. alachlor, atrazine, diuron and metolachlor.
- ✓ Post-emergence (POE) are herbicides have no effect on the weed seeds but affect the emerged seedling/foilage. Thus, they are applied after the emergence of both weed and crop, e.g. 2,4-D, paraquat, glyphosate and propanil.

- ✓ **Note:** some herbicide can be applied either PPI, PE or POE e.g Pursuit 100 EC; imazaquin and imazapyr are applied PE or POE.

Target/point of application

Herbicides used for weed control are either applied to the foliage of the crop and weed or to the soil. All

- ✓ Foliar applied herbicides are used for post-emergence weed control, they enter the plant primarily through the foliage and can exert their toxic on the foliage or translocated to other part of the plant that are more susceptible to poison.
- ✓ Soil applied herbicide, on the other hand need to be applied on the soil for pre-emergence weed control, such that it can enter into soil solution prior to uptake.

Mobility in plants (Mode of action)

- ✓ Herbicides that kill the tissues by touch are known as contact herbicides e.g. paraquat,
- ✓ herbicides that moves from the point of application to other part of the plant where their effects are manifested are called systemic/translocated herbicides, e.g. glyphosate, dalapon and metribromuron.

Selectivity by plant

Herbicides are classified based on the types of plant they killed into selective and nonselective herbicides.

- ✓ Selective herbicides are those that will preferentially kill certain plant species at recommended rate but will not harm other plant that they come in contact with, e.g. 2,4-D, metolachlor, propanyl and acifluorfen.
- ✓ Non-selective herbicides are those that exert their toxic effects on all plants they may come in contact with, e.g. paraquat, diquat, glyphosate, NaClO₃.

Chemical structure

Herbicides can be classified into distinct chemical groups on the basis of their structural formula into:

- Organic (phytotoxic and non-phytotoxic oils; aliphatic acids organic arsenicals; phenoxy acid derivatives; phenoxy carboxylic acid derivatives; Amide derivatives; Benzotriles etc.).
- Inorganic (ammonium sulfate, NH₄SCN, CaSNH₂, CaSN₂, NaBO₄, H₂SO₄).
- Biological herbicides or mycoherbicides such as Collogo (*Collectotricumglycosporoides*); Devine (*Phytophthorapalmivora*).

A majority of the 200 herbicides in use today are organic compounds, but there are still a few inorganic herbicides in use today. In addition to this, new

types of herbicides known as biological herbicide are now available for weed control.

FACTORS AFFECTING SPRAYER CALIBRATION

1. Vegetation height/density

Low vegetation and/or scattered clumps will require less solution per hectare than taller and dense vegetation with greater leaf surface.

2. Nozzle and pressure

Solution delivery from the sprayer varies with the nozzles used and/or pressure. For most herbicide projects the suggested pressure is 100 to 140 kPa (15 - 20 psi) for backpack sprayers and 175 to 240 kPa (25 - 35 psi) for power operated sprayers.

3. Ground Conditions

For backpack projects the ground conditions (slash, slope, etc.) will affect the workers walking speed, which directly affects the delivery rate per hectare. If conditions vary substantially within the site or from site to site, the equipment should be recalibrated. The most accurate method of calibration is to actually spray an area of known size and measure the amount of solution used over this known area.

Herbicide application

Herbicides are applied in various ways to plants and soils. The choice of a method of herbicide application is influenced by herbicide formulation, the target to be treated and by the type of weed problem to be solved. Herbicide formulation has an overriding influence on method of application. The methods of herbicide application include the following:

- i. Spraying.
 - ii. Broadcasting.
 - iii. Mechanical incorporation into the top 5-15cm of the soil.
 - iv. Sub-surface layering.
 - v. Injecting into: (a) soil; (b) irrigation water and drainage canals, (c) lakes and reservoirs.
- ✓ Although a herbicide may have good efficacy, the method of application may drastically alter this in a given time and place.
 - ✓ Poor application of herbicides may increase cost of weed control through excessive use of herbicide or the additional cost of supplementary weeding; reduce weed control efficiency; increase crop injury because of irregular discharge of spray solution, or a result of improper sprayer calibration.
 - ✓ Many factors favour improvements in herbicide application methods. These factors include the need to:

- minimize drift through improvements in herbicide formulations and the use of charged droplets;
- improve safety in the use of herbicides through the use of better formulations and application equipment, and through the use of protective clothing;
- improve the precision with which the intended dosage of a herbicide is applied on the target through improvements in the design and operation of the application equipment;
- increase herbicide retention and coverage of the target
- improve the efficiency of spraying as a means of reducing the increasing cost of chemical weed control
- minimize the contamination of the environment and
- reduce crop injury through better placement of herbicides.

Proper application of herbicides will not only increase weed control efficiency, it will also reduce environmental hazards.

Farmers may need to take note of the following general points on herbicide use.

- Carefully read and fully understand the herbicide label before using the herbicide
- Rates of application are usually lower when herbicides are applied as mixtures. Some herbicides cannot be mixed. It is always advisable to consult the company that manufactures the chemical or their agents when in doubt about its use.
- Never buy unlabeled chemicals; you might damage your crop after applying a wrong chemical.
- Never buy chemicals where the expiry date is not shown. Expired chemicals do not work.
- Always consult the local Extension Worker for guidance on the use of herbicides.
- Applying the soil active (pre emergence) herbicide to well-prepared land. Poor land preparation reduces herbicide efficacy
- Applying the soil active (pre emergence) herbicide to moist soil rather than a dry or water logged soils

Safe use of herbicides requires that each herbicide be applied according to application methods and timing indicated on the label or the appropriate herbicide recommendation texts. The effectiveness of any herbicide depends partly on the application techniques.

• 24.8 PESTICIDES POISONING AND FIRST AID

Pesticides are designed to be toxic to living organisms so they can control pests (e.g., plants, insects, rodents, fungi, and bacteria). At the same time, pesticides must be used with special care to avoid harming non-target organisms, including pesticide applicators, handlers, and anyone else exposed to the product. Though many pesticides are toxic to humans, they vary significantly in the type and level of hazards they present. In many cases, something that is toxic to one species may also be toxic to other species of organisms. This is especially true if the organisms are closely related. For example, insects, rodents, and humans are all animals and have similarities in their nervous, circulatory, and respiratory systems. Because of these similarities, pesticides can affect people as well as the target pest.

Pesticides can have both short-term and long-term effects on humans. The signal word on the product label and the information contained in the “*Hazards to Humans and Domestic Animals*” section of the label indicate the human toxicity concerns and the precautions that should be taken to minimize risks. Pesticides can pose additional physical and chemical risks by being explosive and/or combustible.

Toxicity refers to the ability of a pesticide to cause short-term (**acute**) or long-term (**chronic**) injury. “Toxicity,” a measure of the pesticide’s capacity to cause injury or illness, is a combination of its chemical properties and concentration.

Hazard: or risk, is the true concern for the applicator or handler. It is the potential or probability for harm (injury, illness, or allergy) to occur because of the combination of the product’s innate toxicity and the level of human exposure. “Hazard” reflects both the pesticide’s toxicity and the likelihood that you will be exposed to the product in a particular situation. As an applicator, you can reduce your risk by choosing a less-toxic product, by reducing exposure, or both. In situations when a different product cannot be used, you can still reduce the hazard (risk) by taking steps to reduce exposure. As a result, pesticide users need to be concerned with the hazards associated with exposure to the chemical and not exclusively with the toxicity of the pesticide.

Exposure: occurs when pesticides get onto or into the body through certain known routes. Exposure routes include: dermal (skin), inhalation (respiration), oral (mouth), or ocular(eye), injection (cutaneous/sub-cutaneous).

Image showing Exposure routes. Images culled from www.googleimages.com (2020)

Fate of the toxic substances:

Product formulations differ greatly in their exposure risk. Some routine pesticide-handling procedures present an especially high likelihood of exposure. Examples include handling opened containers; mixing and loading concentrates; working around contaminated application equipment; making spray, mist, or dust applications; cleaning up spills; and reentering a recently treated area before the spray has dried or the dust has settled.

Factors that affect exposure:

- . physical state of the substance: solid, liquid, gas
- . route of exposure
- . reactivity potential of the substance
- . stability at normal atmospheric conditions
- . time and duration of exposure
- . solubility (either in water or oil)

Common ways in which pesticide handlers and other workers are exposed to pesticides

1. Dermal exposure

- Not wearing gloves or other protective clothing.
- Not washing hands after handling pesticides, product containers, or application equipment.
- Not washing hands before using the toilet.
- Splashing or spilling pesticide on skin.
- Being exposed to spray or dust drift.
- Applying pesticides in windy weather or above your head.
- Touching treated plants, soil, or livestock.

2. Eye exposure

- Rubbing eyes with contaminated gloves or hands.
- Splashing pesticide in eyes.

- Handling dry formulations when not wearing eye protection.
- Applying pesticides in windy weather.

3. Oral exposure

- Not washing hands before eating, smoking, chewing, or drinking.
- Splashing pesticide in mouth.

4. Inhalation exposure

- Handling pesticides in confined or poorly ventilated areas.
- Handling dusts or powders.
- Using an inadequate or poorly fitting respirator.
- Being exposed to spray or dust drift.

GIVING FIRST AID FOR PESTICIDE POISONING:

Images culled from www.googleimages.com (2020)

The following are a few key points to remember when administering first aid during a pesticide emergency:

- If oral or dermal exposure has occurred, the first objective is usually to rinse the exposed area with plenty of water to dilute the pesticide and prevent absorption.

- Always have a source of clean water available. In an extreme emergency, use water from a farm pond, irrigation system, or watering trough to rinse exposed areas and dilute the pesticide.
- Never try to give anything by mouth to an unconscious person.
- Do not induce vomiting unless the label tells you to.
- If inhalation exposure has occurred, get the victim to fresh air immediately.
- Become familiar with the proper techniques of artificial respiration. It may be necessary if a person's breathing has stopped or becomes impaired.
- If first responders are likely to be directly exposed to a pesticide, be sure they wear appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE's).

Pesticide on the Skin

Proper hygiene helps protect the skin from pesticide exposure. Keep an adequate water supply with you whenever skin exposure is possible. Other key points:

- Remove all contaminated clothing immediately.
- Wash the affected area, including the hair, with plenty water and soap. Rinse well. Showering is better than bathing to avoid prolonged contact with pesticide residues. Avoid harsh scrubbing, which could damage the skin and enhance pesticide absorption.
- Gently dry the affected area and wrap it in loose cloth or a blanket, if necessary.
- If the skin has chemical burns, cover the area loosely with a clean, soft cloth. Do not use ointments, greases, powders, and other medications unless instructed to do so by a medical authority.

Pesticide in the Eyes

Because eyes readily absorb material, fast action is required. Other key points:

- Hold the eyelid open and immediately begin gently washing the eye with drips of clean water. Do not use chemicals or drugs in the wash water unless instructed to do so by a medical professional or a poison control center.
- Drip the water across—not directly into—the eye, or use an eyewash dispenser.
- Continuously rinse the eye for 15 minutes. If only one eye is affected, be careful not to contaminate the other eye.
- Flush under the eyelid with water to remove debris.
- Cover the eye with a clean piece of cloth and seek medical attention immediately.

Inhaled Pesticide: The basic first aid procedure for someone who has inhaled a pesticide is to get him or her to fresh air. Other key points:

- Immediately carry the victim to fresh air to prevent suffocation (do not allow him or her to walk).

- Do not attempt to rescue someone who is in an enclosed, contaminated area unless you are wearing appropriate PPE.
- If other people are in the area, warn them of the danger.
- Have the victim lie down and loosen his or her clothing.
- Keep the victim warm and quiet. Do not allow him or her to become chilled or overheated.
- If the victim is convulsing, protect his or her head, turn the head to the side, and watch that breathing continues. Do not attempt to insert anything into the person's mouth during a seizure.
- Keep the person's chin up to ensure that air passages are open for breathing.
- If breathing stops or is irregular, give artificial respiration.

Pesticide in the Mouth or Swallowed (oral exposure)

If pesticide is in someone's mouth but has not been swallowed, rinse the mouth with plenty of water. Then give the victim large amounts (up to 1 quart) of milk or water to drink. If the pesticide is swallowed, one of the most critical first aid decisions is whether to induce vomiting. Induce vomiting only if the label instructs you to do so. Several pesticides cause more harm when vomited than if they remain in the stomach. To provide first aid for a swallowed pesticide, you must know the appropriate treatment. The decision to induce vomiting must be made quickly and accurately—the victim's life may depend on it.

Never induce vomiting if the victim is:

- unconscious or having convulsions.
- has swallowed a corrosive poison, such as a strong alkali or acid. The material burns the throat and mouth as severely coming up as it did going down. Also, it can be aspirated into the lungs and cause more damage.
- Has swallowed an emulsifiable concentrate or oil solution product, which is dissolved in petroleum solvents. Emulsifiable concentrates and oil solutions may be fatal if aspirated into the lungs during vomiting.

How to Induce Vomiting (if need arises)

Induce vomiting only as a first aid measure until you can get the victim to a hospital. Do not waste a lot of time trying to induce vomiting. Follow these steps:

- Make sure the victim is kneeling forward or lying on his or her side to prevent vomit from entering the lungs and causing additional damage.
- Give the victim at least two glasses of water to dilute the product. Do not use carbonated beverages.
- Put your finger or the blunt end of a spoon at the back of the throat. Do not use anything sharp or pointed. Do not give the victim saltwater.
- Collect some of the vomitus for the doctor, who may need it for chemical analysis.

Antidotes

Antidotes are available for only a few classes of pesticides: anticoagulant-type rodenticides and organophosphate or carbamate insecticides. Because antidotes can be extremely dangerous if misused, they should be prescribed and administered only by a qualified medical professional. Antidotes should **never** be used to prevent poisoning.

• 24.9 PRACTICALS

- i) Identification of different types of pesticides
- ii) Identification and use of personal protective equipment
- iii) Demonstrations on how to mix and apply pesticides

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF PESTICIDES

The aim here is to develop the capacity of the trainees to understand ways of developing innovative methods and indicators to monitor and assess progress in order to achieve a sustainable agriculture.

Substances used in agricultural activities can be from natural sources or synthetic sources. These substances are used as herbicides, pesticides, all for controlling competition among products; some are used as fertilizers to improve and enhance the growth of crops.

The natural substances are considered environmentally friendly because they are said to be natural and contain no additives, they are biodegradable in the environment. Therefore, they have no or less negative implications on the environment.

The synthetic substances are made up of toxic chemical combinations and are mostly required to be handled with care and expertise.

Furthermore, modern technology is constantly placing stress on biological and physical processes that sustain the ecological system in which man lives. Assessing the present practices in handling and application of agrochemicals, particularly pesticides, is the first step towards improving utilization and minimizing their harmful effect on man and the environment. The adverse effect of pesticides on the environment may be caused by the following:

3. Many of the pesticides being used are organochlorines: These chemicals have high persistence coupled with their ability to accumulate along the food chain. Most rural farmers handle these pesticide products without caution, endangering themselves, their families, livestock and the environment. These products are toxic in nature and most people are not aware of the health risk associated with their use.

4. Toxicity to non-target organisms: Pesticides directly or indirectly affect non-target organisms such as bees, especially the wild type that are very common in Nigeria, with a consequence of decrease in both plant pollination and honey production. Predators are also harmed through the consumption of poisoned prey. Consequently, their egg-shells develop abnormally causing them to break more easily.
5. Toxicity to beneficial insects: Pesticide misuse has a negative impact on beneficial insects, which other insects need for their subsistence and the preservation of their species (e.g. parasites are often destroyed along with the pest and can no longer exercise their regulatory functions). This usually leads to the development of problems with new pests or an increased outbreak of existing pest whose damage continue to increase until it becomes relatively significant. Most pesticides used in Nigeria have the disadvantage of low selectivity; they harm both beneficial organisms as well as the target pests.
7. Development of resistance by target pests: Pesticide misuse also leads to the development of pesticide resistance by the insect pests. In most instances the more the pesticide is sprayed, the more frequent the treatment and the faster the development of resistance. This is because the detoxification mechanism of the insect now responds faster and more effectively. There are about 47 resistant insect species and mites, most of which are well-known pest of crops and many of these insects are resistant to one or more substance group.
8. Interfere with decomposition process in the soil: The presence of pesticides directly or indirectly influences soil micro-fauna and can alter decomposition of organic matter. Pesticides residues in the soil can be directly toxic to soil organisms or can exert subtle effects by influencing their activities, behavior, reproduction and metabolism. Soil organisms such as earthworms suffer strong toxic reaction due to the use of chlordane, heptachlor and HCH even at the recommended dosages.
9. Reduction of soil fertility: A large proportion of pesticide being used end up in the soils and open water bodies. It is common for most pesticide users to pour away left-over without thought. The breakdown of active ingredient of pesticide into several decomposition products and from these into natural soil components occurs less quickly. Pesticide misuse contaminates soil and produce adverse effect on soil fertility in a number of ways. These include the direct effect of decimating population

of soil organisms, and indirect effects such as eradication of prey and predatory soil insects, and accumulation of toxic substances such as lead and mercury. Pesticides also bring out changes in the substances contained in plants. For example, 2, 4, D increase nitrogen content in maize plants, this leads to increase in aphid concentrations.

7. Water pollution: Pesticide contamination of ground water is of great health concern. Heavy metal pollution in the water bodies have a debilitating consequence; it attacks many organs and tissues throughout the body including digestive, nervous and excretory organs. Pollution of water bodies through run-off from farmlands. The most common impact is the formation of high BOD, which causes algae bloom and consequently death of aquatic life. Water pollution by pesticides also causes uptake by aquatic micro and macro-flora (primary producers) and fauna such as zooplanktons, arthropod larvae, as well as other larger aquatic organisms. The effect magnifies across the food chain (bio-magnification), thus, detrimental to life.

8. development of resistance by weed biotypes as a result of application of sub-lethal dose of the herbicides or constant use of the same class of herbicides.

9. Air pollution: Air pollution by pesticide is the most studied environmental hazard to human and livestock health. However, It's impact is grossly underestimated. More than half of the amount of pesticide applied may go directly into the atmosphere during spraying. Pesticides contaminate the air in the atmosphere in various ways: through wind drift during spraying, evaporation of active ingredients from the surface of plants and soil and through wind erosion of contaminated soils. These may cause adverse effects on the environment, including damage to the ozone layer leading to global warming.

10. Plants uptake of chemicals (bioaccumulation): some plants have the ability to absorb pesticides along with other nutrients available. Some of these can persist longer and can have residue in the plant tissues, therefore, consumption by man and animals could be detrimental to the health.

Mitigating measures to negative impacts of pesticides

As earlier mentioned, agrochemicals are toxic, harmful, irritant or corrosive. Therefore, needs to be handled and used with ample care. If they are allowed into the body through inhalation, ingestion or absorption, poisoning would occur as a result. Thus agrochemical users have a responsibility to ensure competence in all tasks carried out and this is only achievable by an appropriate level of training and education. The training will be dynamic, action

oriented and adjusted to the needs and peculiarities of individual communities and needs as discussed below:

Images culled from www.googleimages.com (2020)

Information: Information about agrochemicals and how they are used safely and efficiently readily available in the country will be introduced to the farmers. The information could be obtained from international agencies, governments, experts and manufacturers. This will be provided in an easy to read form i.e. leaflets with all relevant illustrations and free of charge. More so, the users will be trained on how to obtain additional information from agricultural associations, government officers, agrochemical suppliers and healthcare workers.

Education: Although agrochemical use may be self-taught, appropriate education and training will ensure that the users understand the health risk

associated with improper use and application. This includes risk to people, livestock, wildlife and the environment. Among others, they will learn;

- To understand and follow instruction on labeled products on calibration of application equipment, proper procedure for diluting concentrates and mixing formula among others.
- The use of personal protective equipment by the users to protect from exposure to toxic substances.
- The basic maintenance procedures for applicators such as knapsack sprayers in order to avoid leakages especially due to the closeness of the knapsack sprayer to the body of the applicator.
- The procedure for the safe disposal of empty containers and surplus products.
- Emergency procedures in case the need arises and be able to identify symptoms of poisoning and provide first aid.
- To observe a standard of good personal hygiene and other measures that requires observation of basic rules to ensure minimum exposure to these chemicals. This includes among others, washing hands thoroughly after work and before meals to avoid self-contamination from careless and dangerous practices.
- The meaning of hazard symbols on various labels on the information data sheets.
- The appropriate time to withdraw chemicals before harvest to avoid contamination of goods ready for markets or consumption.

MODULE 25: ENVIRONMENTAL/SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS

• 25.1 Overview

A successful Environmental/Social Impact Assessment training depends largely not only on the expertise of the trainers but also on the understanding of the local settings, and the laws and policies in the country. Hence, the specific needs of the trainees must be considered too, such as level of education and development.

Objectives:

By the end of the training, successful trainees should be able to;

- i) Explain the use of EIA as a tool.
- ii) Identify the relevant stakeholders
- iii) Understand the roles of EIA in creating awareness
- iv) Be able to identify Environmental/Social factors and their implication
- v) Proper mitigation measures and follow up plan

- **25.2 Introduction:**

Environmental/Social Impact Assessment is a tool that is used to determine the environmental and social impacts of a project or a government policy on a group of people, communities and the general public. The assessment is carried out prior to the commencement of the project or before the implementation of the policy. It includes all stakeholders' inputs, assessments of the positive impacts, prediction of possible negative impacts, as well as mitigating measures for the negative impacts.

How to prevent 'child waste':

'Child Waste' in this context refers to the unfortunate children that start life at a disadvantage; this could be simply because of who they are and where they come from. This is to make all children have equal chances of survival (health and nutrition), education, and protection from abuse, neglect and exploitation.

Tools used in EIA: observation checklist, baseline data/information, etc.

- **25.3 Identification of Local Actors**

This process involves identifying and selecting the target persons. These target persons include but not limited to:

- i. Parents: the father, the mother
- ii. The child (unborn, under 5years)

- **25.4: Creating Awareness**

This in EIA terms is referred to as **scoping**. This is the process of information dissemination from the authorities to the target persons within the communities. It also includes sharing knowledge within stakeholders. Awareness creation is considered an important obligation to contribute to

increasing knowledge and awareness on the importance of saving the children and investing in their future.

- **25.5 Identification of Environmental Factors and Implications**

Environmental factors play a vital role in a child's life right from conception to birth and until maturity. The importance of having and maintaining good positive environmental factors in a child's life cannot be over emphasized. Environmental factors that affect the wellness of a child include:

- i. Diseases
- ii. Food and nutrition
- iii. Shelter
- iv. Clean water
- v. Sanitation
- vi. Proper/good education
- vii. Good health care

Deficiency in one or more of these factors would have a negative consequence on the child. Consequences such as dropping out of school, lack of self-esteem, exposure to dangers of life and threat to survival.

- **25.6 Identification of Social Factors and Implications**

Social factors move *vis-a-vis* the environmental factors in a child's life. These factors include:

- i. Relationships: individual, family, community.
- ii. Poverty
- iii. Education
- iv. Security
- v. Migration

A fall back in any of the aforementioned factors will open ways of exposing the child to insecurities of life and adulthood. It robs the child of a bright future. A family is a group of people related by blood. Members of the same family are supposed show love and care to the child; this love and care is what is

expected to be extended to the community level. If the child is deprived of this love and care, he/she begins to look for care outside. This attempt exposes the child to so many dangers ranging from negative peer influence to accidental learning and adoption of negative behaviors.

These new traits adopted by the child becomes a threat to the child's education, good relationships and a bright future. Any negative alteration in these will ultimately open the doors of poverty, insecurity and so many negative social issues.

- **25.7 Mitigating Measures**

1. Creating an enabling environment for the parents to have access to basic social amenities such as:
 - i. Adequate primary health care facilities
 - ii. Clean and potable drinking water
 - iii. Affordable housing and proper sanitation
 - iv. Compulsory primary education (for children)
 - v. Security
2. Food security
3. Employment opportunities through:
 - i. Improved rural agriculture
 - ii. Improved rural transportation

- **25.8 Follow-up**

This aspect involves follow-up by major stakeholders to ensure that the people continue to practice all mitigating measures and abide by all environmental laws and regulations.

- **25.9 EIA ON ENERGY EFFICIENT STOVES (EES)**

At the end of this module, participants should be able to:

- Know the sources of raw materials involved in EES
- Know the sustainable processes of raw materials collection (4Rs)
- Negative impacts of their action

- Method of proper disposal of the product after use
- Mitigating measures.

25.9.1 Introduction

This will take the analysis of the whole process. Beginning with the production of the EES to the ultimate end of use of the EES, the whole life cycle is to be considered.

Raw materials involved in the production of the EES include: clay soil, iron/metallic beams, rice husk and other relevant materials.

Sources of Raw Materials:

1. **Clay soil:** this is the largest component involved in the production of the EES. The clay is to sourced locally within their immediate environment. This process involves excavation of top to subsoil layers. The process of excavation for the collection of the raw material is of course a form of land degradation which its negative impacts cannot be over emphasized. These layers are of great importance to biodiversity and yet, these activities must be carried out by man for his survival.

Negative impacts:

- i. Production/creation of pits that will ultimately expose the land to all forms of erosion.
 - ii. Displacement of biodiversity: the indigenous fauna and flora in and around the area could be displaced; some will migrate and adapt while others may face challenges of adaptation thus extinction.
 - iii. Destruction of farmlands.
2. **Iron/metallic components:** The concept of 4R's shall be adopted here. It will involve the 'reuse' of metallic components from other sources (earlier used for something else). Materials 'recycled' from other sources (scrap) can also be 'reused' for the production of the EES. And then it will be encouraged to 'recover' materials from other sources and reused for this purpose.

They should be able to learn how to derive ways that will 'reduce use' of (virgin materials) as this will encourage recycling in the nearest future. They should be able to inculcate a sustainable material for this purpose.

3. **Rice Husk:** This will be bought/collected from farmers and millers. This is a biodegradable material so it has a limited impact from source to after usage.

Mitigating Measures to these Negative Impacts

Excavation: land reclamation should be applied to excavated sites through:

- i. Landfills: filling the borrow pits with biodegradable waste. This will reclaim the land and replace the soil with a more fertile one. Agricultural practices and afforestation will go a long way in reclaiming the lost value. Thus, the reclaimed land can be put into various agricultural uses.
- ii. The pits can also be converted to ponds where fish farming can be practiced. Especially for the fact that clay soil environment is preferred for ponds, it will help a lot in the provision of food, source of income generation, job creation and ultimately poverty alleviation.
- iii. Excavated sites can be used for rain water harvesting and subsequently used as water reservoirs for dry season irrigation by farmers.
- iv. Concerned authorities (Ministry of Land and Survey and the Ministry of Environment) should be involved in the allocations of excavation site(s) to avoid issues of land management and ensure that environmental laws are abided to. These authorities should monitor their activities and ensure that they apply all the mitigation measures.